

Studied material of the updated checklist of the order Thysanoptera in Colombia with geographic distributions and associated plants

SUPPLEMENTARY DATA.

AEOLOTHRIPIDAE Uzel

***Ambaeolothrips microstriatus* (Hood)**

COLOMBIA: 2♀, Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.43483N -74.4724W, PMmf; 4/x/2017.

***Erythrothrips diabolus* Priesner**

COLOMBIA: 2♀, Nariño, Sandoná, 1.2786N -77.4855W, LMmf; 5/viii/2015.

***Erythrothrips stygicus* Hood**

COLOMBIA: 1♀, Cundinamarca, Bogotá, 4.6364N -74.0884W, LMdf; 26/i/2015.

***Franklinothrips orizabensis* Johansen**

COLOMBIA: 2♀, Cesar, Pueblo bello, 10.4201N -73.5821W, PMmf, 21/i/2016.

***Stomatothrips flavus* Hood**

COLOMBIA: 1♀, Tolima, Fresno, 5.1641N -75.0221W, Mmf; 22/iv/2015.

HETEROTHRIPIDAE Bagnall

***Heterothrips alvarezi* Johansen**

COLOMBIA: 1♀, Meta, Puerto Gaitán, 4.5735N -71.3373W, Tmf; 26/viii/2015.

***Heterothrips condei* Moulton**

COLOMBIA: 3♀ 1♂, Guaviare, San José, 2.5994N -72.7599W, Tmf; 22/ii/2015. Vichada, Puerto Carreño, 6.1256N -67.5033W, Tdf; 28/vi/2015.

***Heterothrips flavidus* Hood**

COLOMBIA: 1♀, Guaviare, San José, 2.599419N -72.759939W, Tmf; 22/ii/2015.

***Heterothrips pedicellatus* Pereyra & Cavalleri**

COLOMBIA: 1♀, Magdalena, Ciénaga (Corregimiento Palmor), 10.7684N -74.0254W, LMmf; 14/v/2015.

***Heterothrips prosopidis* Crawford JC**

COLOMBIA: 1♀, Huila, La Plata, 2.3857N -75.9138W, PMmf; 15/vii/2015.

***Heterothrips sericatus* Hood**

COLOMBIA: 63♀ 13♂, Arauca, Tame, 6.5828N -71.5006W, Tmf; 11/i/2014. Cesar, Pueblo Bello, 10.3827N -73.6666W, PMmf; 2/x/2015 y 10.4331N -73.5765W, PMmf; 21/i/2016. Cundinamarca, Soacha, 4.6112N -74.3104W, LMdf; 29/vi/2014. Meta, Granada, 3.4752N -73.8875W, Tmf; 16/vii/2014 y 3.4757N -73.7282W, Tmf; 25/iii/2015. Meta, Villavicencio, 4.0654N -73.4453W, Tmf; 20/viii/2015. Tolima, Armero, 5.1641N -75.0221W, Tdf; 22/iv/2015. Vichada, Puerto Carreño, 6.1963N -67.4831W, Tdf; 25/vi/2015.

***Scutothrips incaensis* Stannard**

COLOMBIA: 2♀ 4♂, Cundinamarca, La Mesa, 4,6358N -74,5115W, PMmf; 8/v/2014. Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4,4203N -74,4708W, PMmf; 19/vii/2013.

***Scutothrips peruvianus* (Hood)**

COLOMBIA: 7♀, Cundinamarca, Anapoima, 4.5596N -74.5208W, Tdf; 7/iii/2014. Cundinamarca, La Mesa, 4.6358N -74.5115W, PMmf; 8/v/2014. Huila, La Plata, 2.3857N -75.9138W, PMmf; 15/vii/2015.

THRIPIDAE Stevens

PANCHAETOTHRIPINAE Bagnall

***Caliothrips phaseoli* (Hood)**

COLOMBIA: 10♀ 2♂, Cundinamarca, Tocaima, 4.4977N -74.6454W, Tdf; 16/iv/2013. Cundinamarca, Tocaima, 4.4959N -74.6477W, Tdf; 16/iv/2013. Tolima, Espinal- Nataima, 4.1819N -74.9533W, Tdf; 6/v/2015.

***Heliothrips haemorrhoidalis* (Bouche)**

COLOMBIA: 6♀, Bolívar, San Jacinto, 9.92083N -75.21067W, Tdf; 24/xi/2015. Cundinamarca, La Mesa, 4.603492N -74.536718W, PMmf; 24/vi/2015. Guajira, Distracción, 11.04955N -72.90742W, Tdf; 17/iii/2014. Huila, Pitalito, 1.904372N -76.025182W, PMmf; 22/x/2015. Sucre, Colosó, 9.480617N -75.369066W, Tdf; 12/xi/2015. Tolima, Fresno, 5.15149N -75.020238W, PMvmf; 21/vi/2014.

***Selenothrips rubrocinctus* Giard**

COLOMBIA: 2♀, Magdalena, Santa Marta, 11.2051N -74.1647W, Tdf; 1/vi/2012. Santander, Barrancabermeja, 7.0671N -73.7470277W, Tmf; 12/iv/2014.

SERICOTHRIPINAE Karny

***Neohydatothrips burungae* (Hood)**

COLOMBIA: 77♀ 18♂, Boyacá, Buenavista, 5.4975N -73.9369W, LMmf; 10/xi/2016. Boyacá, Nuevo Colón, 5.3401N -73.4415W, LMdf; 3/iv/2016. Caldas, Manizales, 4.9095N -75.6238W, LMmf; 1/vii/2016. Cesar, Pueblo bello, 10.42003N -73.58217W, PMmf; 21/i/2016. Cundinamarca, Bojacá, 4.6948N -74.3713W, LMdf; 2/v/2015. Huila, La Plata, 2.3622N -75.8713W, PMmf; 23/x/2015. Meta, Granada, 3.4757N -73.7282W, Tmf; 25/iii/2015. Meta, Lejanías, 3.4765N -73.9186W, Tmf; 26/iii/2015. Meta, Mesetas, 3.3729N -74.0341W, Tmf; 27/ii/2015. Nariño, Consacá, 1.1941N -77.4675W, LMmf; 6/viii/2015. Nariño, Sandoná, 1.3134N -77.4461W, LMmf, 5/viii/2015; 1.3102N -77.4471W, LMmf, 5/viii/2015 y 1.3134N -77.4461W, LMmf; 5/viii/2015. Risaralda, Belén de Umbría, 5.1262N -75.9865W, PMmf; 19/ix/2015. Risaralda, Quinchía, 5.35325N -75.7566W, PMvmf; 14/ix/2015. Risaralda, Santa Rosa de Cabal, 4.8766N -75.5417W, PMvmf; 23/ix/2015. Santander, Girón, 6.9875N -73.1683W, Tdf; 15/iii/2015. Valle del Cauca, Sevilla, 4.2554N -75.9286W, PMmf; 17/ix/2015.

***Neohydatothrips gracilipes* Hood**

COLOMBIA: 68♀ 38♂, Cundinamarca, La Mesa, 4.5477N -74.4737W, PMmf; 7/v/2014. Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 4.6857N -74.2191W, LMdf; 6/v/2014. Cundinamarca, Tocaima, 4.4959N -74.6477W, Tdf; 16/iv/2013. Cundinamarca, Zipacón-Anolaima, 4.7631N -74.4041W, PMmf; 11/ix/2018. Huila, La Plata, 2.3758N -75.8854W, PMmf, 10/v/2010; 2.3761N -75.8761W, PMmf, 16/vii/2015; 2.38573N -75.9138W, PMmf, 15/vii/2015 y 2.3622N -75.8713W, PMmf, 23/x/2015. Meta, Granada, 3.4757N -73.7282W, Tmf, 20/xi/2014, 25/iii/2015; 3.67111N -73.71154W, Tmf, 12/viii/2015; 3.41679N -73.77958W, Tmf, 23/iv/2015 y 3.4821N -73.7382W, Tmf, 9/v/2016. Meta, Lejanías, 3.4765N -73.9186W, Tmf; 26/iii/2015. Quindío, Circasia, 4.6428N -75.6077W, PMmf; 11/iv/2014. Risaralda, Santa Rosa de Cabal, 4.8766N -

75.5417W, PMvmf; 23/ix/2015. Santander, Girón, 6.9875N -73.1683W, Tdf; 15/iii/2015. Tolima, Mariquita, 5.1806N -74.9561W, Tmf; 21/vi/2014. Valle del Cauca, Palmira, 3.5155N -76.3124W, Tdf; 15/ix/2015.

***Neohydatothrips humberto* Mound & Marullo**

COLOMBIA: 2♀, Cundinamarca, Guasca, 4.844N -73.8855W, LMdf; 7/iv/2016. Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 4.6948N -74.2017W, LMdf; 20/ii/2016.

***Neohydatothrips inversus* (Hood)**

COLOMBIA: 23♀ 15♂, Arauca, Tame, 6.5826N -71.4981W, Tmf; 11/i/2014. Cundinamarca, La Mesa, 4.5585N -74.6001W, PMmf; 25/vi/2015. Meta, Granada, 3.4757N -73.7282W, Tmf, 25/iii/2015; 3.4471N -73.7989W, Tmf, 9/vi/2016; 3.3181N -73.4317W, Tmf, 10/vi/2016 y 3.4471N -73.7989W, Tmf; 9/vi/2016. Meta, Lejanías, 3.4765N -73.9186W, Tmf; 26/iii/2015. Valle del Cauca, Sevilla, 4.2554N -75.9286W, PMmf; 17/ix/2015.

***Neohydatothrips signifer* (Priesner)**

COLOMBIA: 524♀ 97♂, Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.7378N -75.2052W, Tdf; 10/vii/2014. Cesar, Pueblo bello, 10.4201N -73.58217W, PMmf; 21/i/2016. Córdoba, San Pelayo, 8.9511N -75.8524W, Tdf; 27/x/2015. Cundinamarca: Bogotá, 4.6364N -74.0884W, LMdf; 26/i/2015; Cundinamarca, Bojacá, 4.6948N -74.3713W, LMdf; 2/v/2015. Cundinamarca, Guayabetal, 4.3533N -73.8456W, PMpf; 26/iv/2013. Cundinamarca, Gutiérrez, 4.2034N -73.8719W, LMmf; 25/iv/2013. Cundinamarca, La Mesa, 4.5477N -74.4737W, PMmf; 7/v/2014. Cundinamarca, Sylvania, 4.38957N -74.3784W, PMmf; 30/i/2015. Cundinamarca, Tocaima, 4.4977N -74.6454W, Tdf, 16/iv/2013 y 4.4959N -74.6477W, Tdf; 16/iv/2013. Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.4348N -74.4724W, PMmf; 28/viii/2012. Huila, Garzón, 2.3365N -75.5129W, Tdf; 21/x/2015. Huila, La Plata, 2.3621N -75.8711W, PMmf, 16/vii/2015; 2.3622N -75.8713W, PMmf, 23/x/2015; 2.3761N -75.8761W, PMmf, 16/vii/2015; 2.3758N -75.8854W, PMmf, 10/v/2010 y 2.3857N -75.9138W, PMmf; 15/vii/2015. Meta, Granada, 3.4757N -73.7282W, Tmf, 20/xi/2014; 3.4757N -73.728W, Tmf, 25/iii/2015; 3.4167N -73.7795W, Tmf, 23/iv/2015; 3.4757N -73.7282W, Tmf, 25/iii/2015; 3.4821N -73.7382W, Tmf, 9/v/2016 y 3.6711N -73.7115W, Tmf; 12/viii/2015. Meta, Lejanías, 3.4765N -73.9186W, Tmf; 26/iii/2015. Meta, Puerto Lleras, 3.2612N -73.3637W, Tmf; 29/iv/2015. Nariño, Consacá, 1.1941N -77.4675W, LMmf; 6/viii/2015. Nariño, Sandoná, 1.3102N -77.4471W, LMmf, 5/viii/2015; 1.3134N -77.4461W, LMmf, 5/viii/2015 y 1.3102N -77.4471W, LMmf; 5/viii/2015. Quindío, Circasia, 4.6428N -75.6077W, PMmf; 11/iv/2014. Quindío, Quimbaya, 4.6072N -75.7941W, PMmf; 10/iv/2014. Risaralda, Santa Rosa de Cabal, 4.8865N -75.6387W, PMvmf,

27/viii/2013 y 4.8625N -75.6282W, PMvmf, 27/viii/2013. Santander, Girón, 6.978N -73.1775W, Tdf; 15/iii/2015. Santander, Lebrija, 7.1256N -73.3352W, Tdf; 1/iii/2015. Tolima, Mariquita, 5.1806N -74.9561W, Tmf; 21/vi/2014. Valle del Cauca, Palmira, 3.5155N -76.3124W, Tdf; 15/ix/2015. Valle del Cauca, Sevilla, 4.2554N -75.9286W, PMmf; 17/ix/2015.

THRIPINAE Stephens

***Anaphothrips obscurus* (Muller)**

COLOMBIA: 6♀, Cundinamarca, Cogua, 5.0565N -73.929W, LMdf; 7/i/2016, 31/iii/2016, 28/vii/2016. Cundinamarca, Guasca, 4.844N -73.8855W, LMdf; 7/iv/2016.

***Anaphothrips sudanensis* Trybom**

COLOMBIA: 5♀, Cundinamarca, Tocancipá, 4.9887N -73.9043W, LMdf; 1/ix/2015.

***Aptinothrips rufus* Haliday**

COLOMBIA: 3♀ 1♂, Cundinamarca, Nemocón, 5.1181N -73.8588W, LMdf; 1/x/2015.

***Arorathrips fulvus* (Moulton)**

COLOMBIA: 3♀, Córdoba, Ciénaga de oro, 8.8746N -75.6942W, Tdf; 27/x/2015. Santander, Barrancabermeja, 7.0702N -73.7474W, Tmf; 12/iv/2014.

***Arorathrips mexicanus* (Crawford DL)**

COLOMBIA: 7♀, Tolima, Armero, 5.0531N -74.8814W, Tdf; 20/vi/2014. Tolima, Espinal, 4.1271N -74.8416W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014 y 4.20205N -74.9004W, Tdf, 6/v/2015.

***Arorathrips xanthius* (Hood)**

COLOMBIA: 21♀ 1♂, Bolívar, Mompo, 9.1519N -74.2838W, Tdf; 9/ix/2015. Tolima, Armero, 4.6806N -74.9086W, Tdf; 26/ix/2014. Tolima, Espinal, 4.7567N -74.8238W, Tdf, 6/iii/2015 y 4.1271N -74.8416W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014.

***Aurantothrips orchidaceus* Bagnall**

COLOMBIA: 4♀ 1♂, Cundinamarca, Cogua, 5.0564N -73.9289W, LMdf; 1/ix/2015.

***Baileyothrips limbatus* (Hood)**

COLOMBIA: 21♀ 7♂, Cundinamarca, Ricaurte, 4.2954N -74.7399W, Tdf; 26/ix/2014. Huila, Villavieja, 3.1961N -75.2293W, Tdf; 26/ix/2014. Santander, Barrancabermeja, 6.9623N -73.7361W, Tmf, 14/iv/2014 y 7.0887N -73.7554W, Tmf, 21/iv/2014. Tolima, Espinal, 4.1271N -74.8416W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 4.1939N -74.966W, Tdf; 26/ix/2014 y 4.1892N -74.9553W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014. Tolima, Natagaima, 3.4918N -75.1298W, Tdf; 26/ix/2014.

***Bolacothrips striatopennatus* (Schmutz)**

COLOMBIA: 7♀, Huila, La Plata, 2.4655N -75.7121W, PMmf; 16/vii/2015. Tolima, Espinal, 4.1382N -74.8627W, Tdf, 5/iii/2015; 4.7567N -74.8238W, Tdf, 6/iii/2015 y 4.1829N -74.9616W, Tdf; 4/iii/2015.

***Bravothrips kraussi* (Crawford JC)**

COLOMBIA: 3♀, Cundinamarca, Guayabetal, 4.3533N -73.8456W, PMpf; 26/iv/2013. Santander, Barrancabermeja, 6.9681N -73.7446W, Tmf, 14/iv/2014 y 7.0077N -73.7791W, Tmf; 14/iv/2014.

***Bravothrips mexicanus* (Priesner)**

COLOMBIA: 1♀, Boyacá, Nuevo Colón, 5.3401N -73.4411W, LMdf; 3/iv/2016.

***Ceratothripoides brunneus* Bagnall**

COLOMBIA: 19♀ 11♂, Cesar, Pueblo bello, 10.4331N -73.5765W, PMmf; 21/i/2016. Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.4093N -74.4885W, PMmf; 12/vi/2015. Guaviare, San José, 2.5994N -72.7599W, Tmf, 22/ii/2015 y 2.5335N -72.5926W, Tmf, 19/ii/2015. Meta, Villavicencio, 4.0607N -73.4617W, Tmf, 18/vii/2014 y 4.0611N -73.4641W, Tmf, 20/viii/2015. Santander, El Carmen de Chucurí, 6.6261N -73.6398W, PMmf; 21/v/2014.

***Ceratothripoides claratris* (Shumsher)**

COLOMBIA: 1♀, Santander, Barrancabermeja, 7.0674N -73.7491W, Tmf; 12/iv/2014.

***Chaetanaphothrips orchidii* (Moulton)**

COLOMBIA: 1♀, Cesar, Pailitas, 8.9601N -73.6322W, Tmf; 2/xii/2013.

***Charassothrips* sp**

COLOMBIA: 2♀, Cesar, Pueblo Bello, 10.4111N -73.6111W, PMmf; 1/x/2015.

***Corynothrips stenopterus* Williams**

COLOMBIA: 102♀, Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.7416N -75.2627W, Tdf; 6/x/2015. Cesar, Pueblo Bello, 10.3869N -73.6482W, PMmf, 2/x/2015 y 10.4141N -73.6195W, PMmf, 1/x/2015. Cundinamarca, Tibacuy, 4.1786N -74.3201W, PMmf; 6/08/2014. Guaviare, San José, 2.2021N -72.4808W, Tmf, 18/ii/2015 y 2.5868N -72.6259W, Tmf, 17/ii/2015. Magdalena, Ciénaga, 10.5855N -74.2486W, Tvdf; 15/v/2015. Meta, Puerto Gaitán, 4.57135N -71.3324W, Tmf; 27/viii/2015. Meta, Villavicencio, 4.0761N -73.5847W, Tmf, 15/iv/2013 y 4.0654N -73.4453W, Tmf, 20/viii/2015. Santander, Barrancabermeja, 6.9677N -73.7447W, Tmf; 14/iv/2014. Tolima, Mariquita, 5.1806N -74.9561W, Tmf; 21/vi/2014.

***Frankliniella aliaepennae* Berzosa**

COLOMBIA: 7♀, Cundinamarca, Páramo Cruz Verde, 4.5504N -73.9975W, SAp; /x/2017.

***Frankliniella aureominuta* Johansen**

COLOMBIA: 1♀, Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 4.6948N -74.2017W, LMdf; 20/ii/2016.

***Frankliniella auripes* Hood**

COLOMBIA: 91♀ 12♂, Nariño, Pasto, 1.1987N -77.3034W, LMmf; 1/viii/2015, 3/viii/2015, 1/viii/2015. Nariño, Sandoná, 1.2786N -77.4855W, LMmf; 5/viii/2015. Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 4.6909N -74.2027W, LMdf; 11/x/2016. Cundinamarca, Zipacón-Anolaima, 4.7726N -74.3770W, Mmf; 11/ix/2018. Cundinamarca, Bogotá, 4.6364N -74.0884W, LMdf; 26/i/2015. Cundinamarca, Cajicá, 4.6364N -74.0885W, LMdf; 28/i/2015. Cundinamarca, Chipaque, 4.4441N -74.0582W, LMmf; 29/xi/2014. Cundinamarca, Guasca, 4.8440N -73.8855W, LMdf; 27/vi/2016, 4/vii/2016, 11/vii/2016, 18/vii/2016, 15/viii/2016, 22/viii/2016, 12/ix/2016, 3/x/2016, 7/xi/2016, 5/xii/2016.

***Frankliniella bicolor* Moulton**

COLOMBIA: 18♀ 3♂, Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.800556N -75.12552W, Tdf; 8/vii/2014. Cundinamarca, Chipaque, 4.4441N -74.0582W, LMmf; 29/xi/2014. Cundinamarca, Anapoima, 4.5596N -74.5208W, Tdf; 7/iii/2014. Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.4338N -74.4733W, PMmf; 9/v/2014. Huila, La Plata, 2.3622N -75.8713W, PMmf, 23/x/2015; 2.3857N -75.9138W, PMmf, 15/vii/2015; 2.4209N -75.8565W, PMmf, 17/vii/2015; 2.3571N -75.8531W, PMmf, 22/x/2015. Santander, Barrancabermeja, 7.0703N -73.8551W, Tmf; 11/iv/2014. Tolima, Armero, 4.6778N -74.9052W, Tdf; 26/ix/2014.

***Frankliniella borinquen* Hood**

COLOMBIA: 1145♀ 727♂. Atlántico, Malambo, 10.8488N -74.8319W, Tvdf; 13/iii/2015. Antioquia, Cáceres, 7.4499N -75.3101W, Tmf; 8/i/2016. Antioquia, Valdivia, 7.1651N -75.4401W, PMvmf;

8/i/2016. Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.6895N -75.2923W, Tdf, 8/x/2015; 9.8127N -75.4422W, Tdf, 24/xi/2015; 9.7393N -75.2363W, Tdf, 23/xi/2015; 9.6997N -75.3151W, Tdf, 6/x/2015; 9.7341N -75.2218W, Tdf, 8/x/2015; 9.7486N -75.2351W, Tdf, 24/xi/2015; 9.7416N -75.2627W, Tdf, 6/x/2015 y 9.7286N -75.2739W, Tdf, 24/xi/2015. Bolívar, Mompos, 9.2502N -74.5326W, Tdf; 10/ix/2015. Bolívar, San Jacinto, 9.7933N -75.2271W, Tdf, 7/v/2014; 9.9105N 75.2106W, Tdf, 24/xi/2015; 9.8726N -75.1697W, Tdf, 24/xi/2015; 9.8924N -75.2128W, Tdf, 24/xi/2015; 9.8883N -75.5147W, Tdf, 24/xi/2015; 9.8622N -75.1472W, Tdf, 24/xi/2015; 9.8736N -75.1726W, Tdf, 24/xi/2015; 9.87341N -75.18856W, Tdf, 24/xi/2015; 9.8727N -75.1696W, Tdf, 24/xi/2015; 9.5239N -75.1039W, Tdf, 24/xi/2015; 9.9208N -75.2106W, Tdf, 24/xi/2015; 9.8557N -75.1988W, Tdf, 24/xi/2015; 9.8566N -75.2132W, Tdf, 24/xi/2015; 9.8726N -75.1737W, Tdf, 24/xi/2015; 9.8734N -75.1885W, Tdf, 24/xi/2015; 9.83002N -75.1591W, Tdf, 24/xi/2015; 9.8669N -75.1534W, Tdf, 24/xi/2015; 9.8259N -75.1095W, Tdf, 24/xi/2015; 9.8689N -75.2244W, Tdf, 24/xi/2015 y 9.8595N -75.2421W, Tdf, 24/xi/2015. Caldas, Marquetalia, 5.2883N -75.0682W, PMvmf; 11/ii/2015. Cesar, Astrea, 9.4753N -73.8811W, Tdf; 21/v/2015. Cesar, Chimichagua, 9.3538N -73.8851W, Tdf; 21/v/2015. Cesar, Manaure, 10.3901N -73.0093W, PMdf, 19/v/2015 y 10.3724N -73.0071W, PMdf; 19/v/2015. Cesar, Pueblo bello, 10.43307N -73.5765W, PMmf, 21/i/2016 y 10.4141N -73.6195W, PMmf, 1/x/2015. Córdoba, Ciénaga de oro, 8.9121N -75.5834W, Tdf, 27/x/2015 y 8.8746N -75.6942W, Tdf, 27/x/2015. Cundinamarca, Anapoima, 4.5414N -74.5406W, Tdf; 10/v/2014. Cundinamarca, Fusagasugá, 4.2963N -74.4642W, PMmf; 8/iii/2013. Cundinamarca, La Mesa, 4.6358N -74.5115W, PMmf, 8/v/2014; 4.6479N -74.5352W, PMmf, 8/v/2014 y 4.5365N -74.5371W, PMmf, 7/v/2014. Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.4337N -74.4732W, PMmf, 11/vi/2015; 4.4621N -74.5245W, PMmf, 12/vi/2015; 4.4338N -74.4733W, PMmf, 19/vii/2013; 4.4351N -74.4681W, PMmf, 19/vii/2013 y 4.4338N -74.4733W, PMmf, 9/v/2014. Guaviare, San José, 2.5335N -72.5926W, Tmf, 19/ii/2015; 2.2021N -72.4808W, Tmf; 18/ii/2015 y 2.4903N -72.6387W, Tmf, 21/ii/2015. Huila, Garzón, 2.3349N -75.5173W, Tdf, 21/x/2015 y 2.2255N -75.6164W, Tdf, 21/x/2015. Huila, La Plata, 2.3622N -75.8713W, PMmf; 23/x/2015. Huila, Pitalito, 2.1881N -75.8178W, Tdf, 22/x/2015 y 1.9068N -76.0235W, PMmf, 22/x/2015. Magdalena, Ciénaga, 10.7502N -74.0548W, Tvdf, 15/v/2015; 10.7658N -74.0254W, Tvdf, 14/v/2015; 10.7684N -74.0254W, Tvdf, 14/v/2015; 10.9833N -74.2062W, Tvdf, 13/v/2015; 10.9861N -74.2043W, Tvdf, 27/ii/2015 y 10.9586N -74.2470W, Tvdf, 11/v/2015. Magdalena, Zona Bananera, 10.7654N -74.1475W, Tdf; 11/v/2015. Meta, Granada, 3.4757N -73.7282W, Tmf, 25/iii/2015 y 3.4752N -73.8875W, Tmf, 16/vii/2014. Meta, Lejanías, 3.4621N -73.8811W, Tmf; 19/ii/2015. Meta, Villavicencio, 4.0607N -73.4617W, Tmf, 18/vii/2014 y 4.0610N -73.4640W, Tmf, 20/viii/2015. Nariño, Sandoná, 1.3134N -77.4461W, LMmf; 5/viii/2015. Quindío, Armenia, 4.5635N -75.6497W, PMmf; 8/iv/2014. Quindío, Buenavista, 4.3644N -75.7772W, PMmf; 19/ix/2013. Quindío, Pijao, 4.3038N -75.7281W, PMmf; 9/iv/2014. Quindío, Quimbaya, 4.6426N -75.7916W, PMmf; 15/ix/2014. Santander, Barrancabermeja,

7.0672N -73.7456W, Tmf, 12/iv/2014 y 7.0715N -73.7491W, Tmf, 12/iv/2014. Santander, Lebrija, 7.1226N -73.3414W, Tdf; 1/iii/2015. Santander, San Gil, 6.5121N -73.0602W, PMmf, 1/iii/2015 y 6.5991N -73.1516W, PMmf; 1/iii/2015. Santander, Valle de San José, 6.4348N -73.1303W, PMmf; 15/iii/2015. Sucre, Chalán, 9.4981N -75.3411W, Tdf; 12/xi/2015. Tolima, Armero, 4.9152N -74.8748W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014 y 5.0143N -74.9003W, Tdf, 24/iv/2015. Tolima, Espinal- Nataima, 4.2805N -75.0621W, Tdf; 5/v/2015. Tolima, Fresno, 5.1797N -74.9807W, PMvmf, 23/iv/2015 y 5.2349N -75.0173W, PMvmf; 1/vii/2016. Tolima, Guamo, 4.1238N -75.0123W, Tdf; 11/xi/2015. Valle del Cauca, Sevilla, 4.2582N -75.9129W, PMmf, 16/ix/2015; 4.2591N -75.9275W, PMmf, 17/ix/2015 y 4.2546N -75.9301W, PMmf, 17/ix/2015. Vichada, Puerto Carreño, 6.1963N -67.4831W, Tdf; 25/vi/2015.

***Frankliniella brevicaulis* Hood**

COLOMBIA: 1098♀ 332♂, Atlántico, Repelón, 10.5246N -75.1224W, Tvdf; 1/v/2012. Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.7267N -75.1661W, Tdf; 10/vii/2014. Bolívar, San Jacinto, 9.5239N -75.1039W, Tdf; 24/xi/2015. Cesar, Agustín Codazzi, 10.0563N -73.2393W, Tdf; 30/ix/2015. Cesar, Astrea, 9.4753N -73.8811W, Tdf; 21/v/2015. Cesar, Chimichagua, 9.3321N -73.8621W, Tdf, 21/v/2015 y 9.3538N -73.8851W, Tdf, 21/v/2015. Cesar, Chiriguana, 9.3604N -73.5767W, Tdf; 11/xii/2015. Cesar, Manaure, 10.3901N -73.0093W, PMdf; 19/v/2015. Cesar, Pueblo Bello, 10.4120N -73.6081W, PMmf; 2/x/2015. Córdoba, Cereté, 8.8525N -75.8103W, Tdf; 3/xii/2015. Córdoba, Cereté, 8.8375N -75.7983W, Tdf; 28/viii/2012. Córdoba, Ciénaga de oro, 8.8746N -75.6942W, Tdf, 27/x/2015; 8.9121N -75.5834W, Tdf, 27/x/2015 y 8.9399N -75.5641W, Tdf, 27/x/2015. Córdoba, Lorica, 9.06643N -75.8242W, Tdf, 27/x/2015 y 9.19208N -75.8162W, Tdf; 27/x/2015. Cundinamarca, La Mesa, 4.6479N -74.5352W, PMmf; 8/v/2014. Cundinamarca, Ricaurte, 4.2954N -74.7399W, Tdf; 26/ix/2014. Cundinamarca, Tocaima, 4.37629N -74.5701W, PMmf; 4/x/2018. Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.4289N -74.4827W, PMmf; 11/vi/2015. Guaviare, San José, 2.202071N -72.4808W, Tmf, 18/ii/2015; 2.490728N -72.6871W, Tmf, 20/ii/2015, 2.599419N -72.7599W, Tmf, 22/ii/2015; 2.49036N -72.6387W, Tmf, 21/ii/2015; 2.5335N -72.5926W, Tmf, 19/ii/2015 y 2.5868N -72.6259W, Tmf; 17/ii/2015. Huila, La Plata, 2.3526N -75.8858W, PMmf; 25/ii/2015. Huila, Villavieja, 3.3652N -75.1631W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014 y 3.3136N -75.2338W, Tdf, 7/v/2015. Magdalena, Ciénaga, 10.8808N -74.1833W, Tvdf, 11/v/2015; 10.9854N -74.2065W, Tvdf, 1/vi/2012; 10.9861N-74.2043W, Tvdf, 27/ii/2015; 10.7458N -74.0608W, Tvdf, 15/v/2015; 10.9586N -74.2471W, Tvdf, 11/v/2015; 10.9833N -74.2062W, Tvdf, 13/v/2015 y 10.5855N -74.2486W, Tvdf, 15/v/2015. Magdalena, Santa Marta, 11.0843N -74.0738W, Tdf; 1/vi/2012. Magdalena, Zona Bananera, 10.7643N -74.1468W, Tdf, 1/vi/2012 y 10.7654N -74.1475W, Tdf, 11/v/2015. Meta, Granada, 3.3181N -73.4317W, Tmf, 10/vi/2016; 3.4471N -73.7989W, Tmf, 9/vi/2016; 3.4757N -73.7282W, Tmf, 25/iii/2015; 3.4831N -73.7362W, Tmf; 26/iii/2015 y 3.4752N -73.8875W, Tmf, 16/vii/2014. Meta, Lejanías, 3.9991N -

73.7212W, Tmf; 20/iii/2015. Meta, Puerto Gaitán, 4.4743N -71.8233W, Tmf, 25/viii/2015 y 4.5735N -71.3373W, Tmf; 26/viii/2015. Quindío, Calarcá, 4.4075N -75.7348W, PMmf; 11/ix/2014. Quindío, Córdoba, 4.4291N -75.7185W, PMmf; 9/iv/2014. Quindío, La Tebaida, 4.4424N -75.8435W, PMmf; 19/iii/2015. Santander, Barrancabermeja, 7.0874N -73.8382W, Tmf, 2/iii/2014; 7.0887N -73.7554W, Tmf, 21/iv/2014 y 7.0668N -73.7477W, Tmf; 12/iv/2014. Sucre, Chalán, 9.4981N -75.3411W, Tdf; 12/xi/2015. Sucre, Los palmitos, 9.4523N -75.2257W, Tdf; 9/vii/2014. Tolima, Armero, 5.0063N -74.9059W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 5.0531N -74.8814W, Tdf, 20/vi/2014; 4.9849N -74.9022W, Tdf, 22/vi/2014; 4.9269N -74.8851W, Tdf, 22/iv/2015 y 5.1882N -74.8912W, Tdf; 22/iv/2015. Tolima, Espinal, 4.2021N -74.9004W, Tdf; 6/v/2015. Tolima, Espinal- Nataima, 4.1819N -74.9533W, Tdf; 6/v/2015. Tolima, Fresno, 5.17971N -74.9807W, PMvmf; 23/iv/2015. Tolima, Mariquita, 5.1534N -74.9084W, Tmf; 20/vi/2014. Tolima, Natagaima, 3.6771N -75.1027W, Tdf; 26/ix/2014. Vichada, Puerto Carreño, 6.2513N -67.5332W, Tdf, 7/ii/2015; 6.1952N -67.4831W, Tdf, 26/i/2015; 6.0985N -67.4875W, Tdf, 28/vi/2015; 6.1535N -67.6833W, Tdf, 26/vi/2015; 6.1963N -67.4831W, Tdf, 25/vi/2015; 6.1256N -67.5033W, Tdf, 28/vi/2015; 6.1741N -67.7215W, Tdf, 26/vi/2015; 6.1978N -67.5674W, Tdf, 26/vi/2015 y 6.2101N -67.7114W, Tdf; 26/vi/2015.

***Frankliniella breviseta* Moulton**

COLOMBIA: 104♀ 7♂, Cesar, Bosconia, 9.8524N -73.8308W, Tdf, 20/v/2015 y 9.8541N -73.8415W, Tdf; 20/v/2015. Cesar, Bosconia- Copey, 10.0525N -73.8687W, Tdf; 20/v/2015. Cundinamarca, Ricaurte, 4.2954N -74.7399W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014 y 4.2751N -74.7338W, Tdf; 26/ix/2014. Guajira, Cuestecita, 11.1894N -72.7418W, Tdf; 20/i/2016. Guajira, Riohacha, 11.5507N -72.9143W, Tvdf; 18/i/2016. Guaviare, San José, 2.4907N -72.6870W, Tmf; 20/ii/2015. Huila, La Plata, 2.4664N -75.7114W, PMmf; 16/vii/2015. Magdalena, Ciénaga, 10.9833N -74.2062W, Tvdf, 13/v/2015; 10.9586N -74.2471W, Tvdf, 11/v/2015 y 10.9036N -74.1545W, Tvdf, 11/v/2015.

***Frankliniella bruneri* Watson**

COLOMBIA: 10♀ 1♂, Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.7797N -75.2734W, Tdf; //. Cesar, Pueblo Bello, 10.4111N -73.6111W, PMmf; 1/x/2015. Córdoba, San Pelayo, 8.9409N -75.8286W, Tdf; 27/x/2015. Magdalena, Ciénaga, 10.9833N -74.2062W, Tvdf; 13/v/2015. Meta, Villavicencio, 4.0607N -73.4617W, Tmf; 18/vii/2014. Quindío, Pijao, 4.2986N -75.7287W, PMmf; 9/iv/2014. Tolima, Armero, 5.1641N -75.0221W, Tdf; 22/iv/2015. Tolima, Fresno, 5.1797N -74.9807W, PMvmf; 23/iv/2015.

***Frankliniella brunnea* (Priesner)**

COLOMBIA: 89♀ 15♂, Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.7416N -75.2627W, Tdf, 6/x/2015 y 9.8005N -75.1255W, Tdf, 8/vii/2014. Caldas, Marquetalia, 5.311N -75.0841W, PMvmf; 22/v/2014. Cesar, Manaure, 10.3901N -73.0093W, PMdf; 19/v/2015. Córdoba, Cereté, 8.8367N -75.7984W, Tdf; 28/viii/2012. Córdoba, Lórica, 9.3067N -75.8902W, Tdf; 27/x/2015. Córdoba, San Pelayo, 8.9409N -75.8286W, Tdf; 27/x/2015. Cundinamarca, La Mesa, 4.6358N -74.5115W, PMmf; 8/v/2014. Cundinamarca, Nemocón, 5.1181N -73.8588W, LMdf; 1/ix/2015, 1/x/2015, 23/xi/2015. Cundinamarca, Pacho, 5.1369N -74.1615W, LMmf; 29/i/2015. Cundinamarca, Ricaurte, 4.2979N -74.7421W, Tdf; 26/ix/2014. Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.4338N -74.4733W, PMmf; 9/v/2014. Huila, La Plata, 2.3376N -75.8506W, PMmf; 22/x/2015. Magdalena, Ciénaga, 10.8808N -74.1833W, Tvdf, 11/v/2015 y 10.9833N -74.2062W, Tvdf, 13/v/2015. Santander, Barrancabermeja, 7.0641N -73.8625W, Tmf, 30/iv/2014; 7.0821N -73.8552W, Tmf, 2/iv/2014 y 7.0703N -73.8551W, Tmf, 11/iv/2014. Tolima, Armero, 4.9269N -74.8851W, Tdf; 22/iv/2015. Tolima, Armero, 4.6778N -74.9052W, Tdf; 26/ix/2014. Tolima, Espinal, 4.7567N -74.8238W, Tdf, 6/iii/2015; 4.1271N -74.8416W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014 y 4.1939N -74.9661W, Tdf; 26/ix/2014. Tolima, Natagaima, 3.6711N -75.0973W, Tdf; 26/ix/2014.

***Frankliniella caseariae* Moulton**

COLOMBIA: 35♀ 7♂, Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.8127N -75.4422W, Tdf; 24/xi/2015. Bolívar, Mompo, 9.2296N -74.5033W, Tdf; 10/ix/2015. Bolívar, San Jacinto, 9.7933N -75.2271W, Tdf, 7/v/2014; 9.8622N -75.1472W, Tdf, 24/xi/2015 y 9.8734N -75.1885W, Tdf, 24/xi/2015. Cesar, San Martín, 8.0275N -73.4171W, Tmf, 13/xi/2014 y 8.0275N -73.4171W, Tmf, 14/viii/2014. Córdoba, Ciénaga de oro, 8.8746N -75.6942W, Tdf; 27/x/2015. Cundinamarca, Anapoima, 4.5596N -74.5208W, Tdf; 7/iii/2014. Cundinamarca, Fusagasugá, 4.2963N -74.4642W, PMmf; 8/iii/2013. Cundinamarca, Nilo, 4.3511N -74.5385W, PMmf; 15/xii/2018. Cundinamarca, Tocaima, 4.3762N -74.5701W, PMmf; 4/x/2018. Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.4348N -74.4724W, PMmf, 10/xi/2017 y 4.4352N -74.4708W, PMmf, 11/vi/2015. Guajira, Urumita, 10.4762N -72.9716W, Tdf; 18/iii/2014. Huila, Pitalito, 2.1881N -75.8178W, Tdf; 22/x/2015. Magdalena, Santa Marta, 11.0846N -74.0529W, Tdf; 2/vi/2012. Sucre, Ovejas, 9.6479N -75.3088W, Tdf; 8/v/2014. Sucre, Ovejas, 9.6494N -75.31223W, Tdf; 8/v/2014.

***Frankliniella cassiae* Berzosa**

COLOMBIA: 13♀, Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 4.6938N -74.2046W, LMdf; 3/x/2014. Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.4338N -74.4733W, PMmf; 9/v/2014. Meta, Granada, 3.4702N -73.7681W, Tmf; 15/iv/2013. Meta, Lejanías, 3.7461N -73.6947W, Tmf; 19/vii/2014.

***Frankliniella cephalica* (Crawford DL)**

COLOMBIA: 1556♀ 306♂. Antioquia, Fredonia, 5.8165N -75.6827W, PMvmf, 6/v/2015 y 5.8544N -75.7208W, PMvmf, 6/v/2015. Arauca, Tame, 6.5828N -71.5006W, Tmf; 11/i/2014. Atlántico, Malambo, 10.8488N -74.8319W, Tvdf; 13/iii/2015. Bolívar, Córdoba, 9.5822N -74.8270W, Tvdf; 8/x/2015. Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.6918N -75.2565W, Tdf, 5/v/2013; 9.7341N -75.2206W, Tdf, 8/x/2015; 9.7432N -75.2621W, Tdf, 6/x/2015; 9.7488N -75.2422W, Tdf, 11/vii/2014; 9.7653N -75.2868W, Tdf, 5/v/2014; 9.6997N -75.3151W, Tdf, 6/x/2015; 9.7656N -75.2872W, Tdf, 5/v/2014; 9.7274N -75.16319W, Tdf, 8/x/2015 y 9.6895N -75.2923W, Tdf, 8/x/2015. Bolívar, Magangué, 9.2714N -74.7261W, Tdf; 9/ix/2015. Bolívar, Mompo, 9.2502N -74.5326W, Tdf; 10/ix/2015. Bolívar, San Jacinto, 9.7936N -75.2266W, Tdf, 7/v/2014 y 9.8297N -75.1352W, Tdf; 7/x/2015. Bolívar, San Juan Nepomuceno, 9.9741N -75.1503W, Tdf; 7/x/2013. Cesar, Agustín Codazzi, 10.0563N -73.2393W, Tdf, 30/ix/2015; 10.0012N -73.2456W, Tdf, 21/v/2015 y 10.0512N -73.2391W, Tdf; 21/v/2015. Cesar, Astrea, 9.4753N -73.8811W, Tdf, 21/v/2015 y 9.4713N -73.8802W, Tdf; 21/v/2015. Cesar, Becerril, 9.6901N -73.2596W, Tdf; 30/ix/2015. Cesar, Bosconia, 9.8541N 73.8415W, Tdf, 20/v/2015 y 9.8524N -73.8308W, Tdf, 20/v/2015. Cesar, Bosconia- Copey, 10.0525N -73.8687W, Tdf; 20/v/2015. Cesar, Chimichagua, 9.2502N -73.8083W, Tdf, 21/v/2015; 9.3538N -73.8851W, Tdf, 21/v/2015 y 9.3321N -73.8621W, Tdf; 21/v/2015. Cesar, Chiriguana, 9.3604N -73.5767W, Tdf; 11/xii/2015. Cesar, Manaure, 10.3901N -73.0093W, PMdf, 19/v/2015 y 10.3724N -73.0071W, PMdf, 19/v/2015. Cesar, Pailitas, 8.9601N -73.6322W, Tmf; 2/xii/2013. Cesar, Pueblo Bello, 10.42266N -73.5764W, PMmf, 1/x/2015 y 10.4331N -73.5765W, PMmf; 21/i/2016. Cesar, San Diego, 10.2719N -73.2177W, Tdf; 21/v/2015. Cesar, Valledupar, 10.4291N -73.3725W, Tdf, 29/ix/2015 y 10.5674N -73.2431W, Tdf, 29/ix/2015. Córdoba, Cereté, 8.8525N -75.8103W, Tdf; 3/xii/2015. Córdoba, Ciénaga de oro, 8.8746N -75.6942W, Tdf, 27/x/2015 y 8.9121N -75.5834W, Tdf, 27/x/2015. Córdoba, Lorica, 9.3067N -75.8902W, Tdf, 27/x/2015 y 9.1921N -75.8162W, Tdf, 27/x/2015. Córdoba, Montería, 8.7721N -75.8844W, Tdf; 15/i/2016. Córdoba, San Bernardo del viento, 9.3441N -76.0366W, Tdf, 10/i/2016 y 9.3469N -76.0392W, Tdf, 10/i/2016. Cundinamarca, Anapoima, 4.5414N -74.5406W, Tdf; 10/v/2014. Cundinamarca, La Mesa, 4.5468N -74.4741W, PMmf, 7/v/2014 y 4.6514N -74.5752W, PMmf; 8/v/2014. Cundinamarca, Ricaurte, 4.2808N -74.7341W, Tdf, 29/ix/2014 y 4.2921N -74.7367W, Tdf, 29/ix/2014; 4.2974N -74.7418W, Tdf, 29/ix/2014; 4.3035N -74.7443W, Tdf, 29/ix/2014; 4.3077N -74.748W, Tdf, 29/ix/2014; 4.2751N -74.7338W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 4.2979N -74.7421W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 4.2954N -74.7399W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 4.2888N -74.7337W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014 y 4.2849N -74.7394W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014. Cundinamarca, Tocaima, 4.4883N -74.6233W, Tdf; 10/v/2014. Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.4203N -74.4708W, PMmf, 19/vii/2013; 4.4338N -74.4733W, PMmf, 9/v/2014 y 4.4348N -74.4724W, PMmf, 28/viii/2012. Guajira, Cuestecita, 11.1866N -72.7281W, Tdf, 20/i/2016 y 11.1894N -72.7418W, Tdf, 20/i/2016. Guajira, Manaure, 10.4106N -73.0273W, Tdf; 19/iii/2014. Guajira, Riohacha, 11.5507N -72.9143W, Tvdf; 18/i/2016. Guaviare, San José, 2.5137N -

72.6428W, Tmf, 20/ii/2015 y 2.4907N -72.6871W, Tmf, 20/ii/2015. Huila, Aipe 3.221454N -75.245126W, Tdf; 17/vii/2015. Huila, Campoalegre, 2.6847N -75.3667W, Tdf, 28/ix/2014; 2.6921N -75.3618W, Tdf, 28/ix/2014; 2.6998N -75.3552W, Tdf, 28/ix/2014 y 2.7108N -75.3358W, Tdf; 28/ix/2014. Huila, Pitalito, 2.1881N -75.8178W, Tdf; 22/x/2015. Huila, Villavieja, 3.2047N -75.2377W, Tdf, 28/ix/2014; 3.2163N -75.2309W, Tdf, 28/ix/2014; 3.3544N -75.1988W, Tdf, 28/ix/2014; 3.3558N -75.2304W, Tdf, 28/ix/2014; 3.3754N -75.1716W, Tdf, 28/ix/2014; 3.3803N -75.1703W, Tdf, 28/ix/2014; 3.3817N -75.1711W, Tdf, 28/ix/2014; 3.2098N -75.2252W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 3.3136N -75.2338W, Tdf, 7/v/2015; 3.3757N -75.1627W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 3.1961N -75.2293W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 3.36525N -75.1631W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014 y 3.3393N -75.1721W, Tdf, 7/v/2015. Magdalena, Ciénaga, 10.7684N -74.0254W, Tvdf, 14/v/2015; 10.7658N -74.0254W, Tvdf, 14/v/2015; 10.9833N -74.2062W, Tvdf, 13/v/2015; 10.9586N -74.2470W, Tvdf, 11/v/2015; 10.9861N -74.2043W, Tvdf, 27/ii/2015; 10.5855N -74.2486W, Tvdf, 15/v/2015; 10.7502N -74.0548W, Tvdf, 15/v/2015; 10.8635N -74.1931W, Tvdf, 11/v/2015; 10.8808N -74.1833W, Tvdf, 11/v/2015; 10.9214N -74.2048W, Tvdf, 11/v/2015 y 10.9036N -74.1545W, Tvdf, 11/v/2015. Magdalena, Santa Marta (PNN Tayrona), 11.3117N -73.9382W, Tmf, 17/i/2016 y 11.3074N -73.9312W, Tmf, 17/i/2016. Magdalena, Zona Bananera, 10.7654N -74.1475W, Tdf, 11/v/2015; 10.7643N -74.1468W, Tdf, 1/vi/2012 y 10.7658N -74.1474W, Tdf, 6/xi/2013. Meta, Granada, 3.4757N -73.7282W, Tmf, 25/iii/2015 y 3.4831N -73.7362W, Tmf, 26/iii/2015. Meta, Lejanías, 3.4620N -73.8811W, Tmf, 19/ii/2015; 3.5095N -73.9761W, Tmf, 19/ii/2015 y 3.4922N -73.9421W, Tmf, 19/ii/2015. Meta, Villavicencio, 4.0607N -73.4617W, Tmf; 18/vii/2014. Quindío, Armenia, 4.5635N -75.6497W, PMmf; 8/iv/2014. Quindío, Córdoba, 4.4358N -75.6716W, PMmf; 9/iv/2014. Quindío, Genova, 4.2991N -75.7879W, PMmf; 15/ix/2014. Quindío, Montenegro, 4.5621N -75.8212W, PMmf; 15/ix/2014. Quindío, Pijao, 4.298N -75.7287W, PMmf, 9/iv/2014 y 4.3322N -75.7675W, PMmf, 15/ix/2014. Quindío, Quimbaya, 4.5738N -75.6572W, PMmf; 10/iv/2014. Santander, Barrancabermeja, 7.0673N -73.7476W, Tmf, 12/iv/2014; 7.0885N -73.7561W, Tmf, 21/iv/2014; 7.0216N -73.8105W, Tmf, 2/iii/2014; 7.0703N -73.8551W, Tmf, 11/iv/2014; 7.0874N -73.8382W, Tmf, 2/iii/2014; 7.0676N -73.7458W, Tmf, 12/iv/2014; 7.0674N -73.7491W, Tmf, 12/iv/2014; 6.9669N -73.7446W, Tmf, 14/iv/2014; 7.0881N -73.7509W, Tmf, 21/iv/2014 y 7.0672N -73.7456W, Tmf, 12/iv/2014. Santander, Girón, 6.9875N -73.1683W, Tdf; 15/iii/2015. Sucre, Chalán, 9.4980N -75.3411W, Tdf; 12/xi/2015. Sucre, Colosó, 9.4621N -75.3834W, Tdf, 12/xi/2015 y 9.4806N -75.3691W, Tdf, 12/xi/2015. Sucre, Los palmitos, 9.4523N -75.2257W, Tdf, 9/vii/2014 y 9.4628N -75.1626W, Tdf, 22/vii/2013. Sucre, Sampués, 9.1373N -75.2691W, Tdf; 10/xi/2015. Tolima, Armero, 5.0142N -74.9051W, Tdf, 24/ix/2014; 5.1114N -74.8941W, Tdf, 24/ix/2014; 4.6778N -74.9052W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 5.0142N -74.9051W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 4.9152N -74.874W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 5.0063N -74.9059W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 5.164067N -75.0220W, Tdf, 22/iv/2015 y 4.6806N -74.9086W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014. Tolima, Espinal, 4.1341N -74.8472W, Tdf,

26/ix/2014; 4.1343N -74.8470W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 4.1397N -74.8661W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 4.1521N -74.8544W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 4.1533N -74.8676W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 4.1771N -74.9264W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 4.2011N -74.9767W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 4.1271N -74.8416W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 4.1939N -74.966W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 4.1892N -74.9553W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014. Tolima, Espinal- Nataima, 4.2805N -75.0621W, Tdf; 5/v/2015. Tolima, Fresno, 5.1797N -74.9807W, PMvmf, 23/iv/2015 y 5.1514N -75.0202W, PMvmf, 21/vi/2014. Tolima, Guamo, 4.1238N -75.01235W, Tdf, 11/xi/2015 y 4.0197N -74.9843W, Tdf, 15/iii/2016. Tolima, Natagaima, 3.4724N -75.1366W, Tdf, 27/ix/2014; 3.4845N -75.1391W, Tdf, 27/ix/2014; 3.4903N -75.1318W, Tdf, 27/ix/2014; 3.4975N -75.1386W, Tdf, 27/ix/2014; 3.5027N -75.1411W, Tdf, 27/ix/2014; 3.6743N -75.1067W, Tdf, 27/ix/2014; 3.6765N -75.1016W, Tdf, 27/ix/2014; 3.6841N -75.1045W, Tdf, 27/ix/2014; 3.6659N -75.0945W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 3.4808N -75.1257W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 3.4918N -75.1298W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 3.6711N -75.0973W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014 y 3.6771N -75.1027W, Tdf; 26/ix/2014. Valle del Cauca, Palmira, 3.5131N -76.3152W, Tdf; 15/ix/2015. Valle del Cauca, Sevilla, 4.2582N -75.9129W, PMmf, 16/ix/2015 y 4.2546N -75.9301W, PMmf; 17/ix/2015. Vichada, Puerto Carreño, 6.20784N -67.48207W, Tdf, 12/i/2014; 6.24989N -67.5318W, Tdf, 21/xii/2014; 6.3026N -67.82993W, Tdf, 4/xii/2014; 6.25174N -67.53298W, Tdf, 12/xii/2014; 6.25243N -67.53352W, Tdf, 12/xii/2014; 6.25305N -67.53381W, Tdf, 12/xii/2014; 6.25127N -67.53256W, Tdf, 12/xii/2014; 6.17417N -67.72156W, Tdf, 26/vi/2015; 6.25331N -67.53373W, Tdf, 12/xii/2014; 6.25171N -67.53292W, Tdf, 5/xii/2014; 6.19523N -67.48317W, Tdf, 26/i/2015; 6.19682N -67.4649W, Tdf, 29/i/2015; 6.24934N -67.5321W, Tdf, 21/xii/2015; 6.2511N -67.53228W, Tdf, 12/xii/2014; 6.25124N -67.53229W, Tdf, 7/ii/2015; 6.25148N -67.53225W, Tdf; 19/ii/2015; 6.19735N -67.46611W, Tdf, 29/i/2015; 6.15356N -67.68333W, Tdf, 26/vi/2015; 6.25139N -67.53322W, Tdf, 7/ii/2015; 6.30257N -67.82973W, Tdf, 4/xii/2014; 6.19766N -67.46526W, Tdf, 29/i/2015; 6.30784N -67.83994W, Tdf, 4/xii/2014; 6.19768N -67.46557W, Tdf, 29/i/2015; 6.25049N -67.53206W, Tdf, 21/xii/2014; 6.25184N -67.53304W, Tdf, 4/xii/2014; 6.25208N -67.53323W, Tdf, 12/xii/2014; 6.25155N -67.53242W, Tdf, 19/ii/2015; 6.19734N -67.4664W, Tdf, 29/i/2015; 6.2502N -67.53194W, Tdf, 21/xii/2014; 6.19769N -67.46581W, Tdf, 29/i/2015 y 6.30788N -67.84026W, Tdf, 4/xii/2012.

***Frankliniella colombiana* Moulton**

COLOMBIA: 5♀, Cundinamarca, Vía Bogotá - Choachí, 4.5618N -74.0078W, Mmf; 5/ii/2017.

***Frankliniella condei* John**

COLOMBIA: 1♀, Cundinamarca, Sibaté, 4.3771N -74.2490W, LMdf; 17/i/2015.

***Frankliniella cotobrusensis* Retana & Mound**

COLOMBIA: 1♀ 1♂, Huila, Pitalito, 1.906868N -76.023548W, PMmf; 22/x/2015.

***Frankliniella curta* (Hood)**

COLOMBIA: 6♀, Arauca, Tame, 6.5828N -71.5006W, Tmf, 11/i/2014. Cundinamarca, Pacho, 5.1369N -74.1615W, LMmf, 29/i/2015. Nariño, Sandoná, 1.2786N -77.4855W, LMmf, 5/viii/2015. Norte de Santander, Labateca, 7.2469N -72.4918W, LMmf, 26/viii/2016 y 7.2959N -72.4952W, LMmf, 26/viii/2016. Tolima, Fresno, 5.1797N -74.9807W, PMvmf, 23/iv/2015.

***Frankliniella davidsoni* Moulton**

COLOMBIA: 1♀, Cundinamarca, Vía Bogotá-Choachí, 4.5618N -74.0078W, Mmf, 5/ii/2017.

***Frankliniella desmodii* Mound & Marullo**

COLOMBIA: 44♀ 33♂, Boyacá, Nuevo Colón, 5.3401N -73.4411W, LMdf, 3/iv/2016. Cesar, Pueblo Bello, 10.3911N -73.6435W, PMmf, 2/x/2015. Guaviare, San José, 2.4903N -72.6387W, Tmf, 21/ii/2015. Santander, Barrancabermeja, 7.0676N -73.7458W, Tmf, 12/iv/2014. Tolima, Espinal- Nataima, 4.2805N -75.0621W, Tdf, 5/v/2015.

***Frankliniella distinguenda* Bagnall**

COLOMBIA: 58♀ 10♂. Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.7274N -75.1631W, Tdf, 8/x/2015. Cesar, Bosconia- Copey, 10.05258N -73.8687W, Tdf, 20/v/2015. Cesar, Chimichagua, 9.2502N -73.8083W, Tdf, 21/v/2015 y 9.3538N -73.8851W, Tdf, 21/v/2015. Cundinamarca, Ricaurte, 4.2954N -74.7399W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014. Cundinamarca, Soacha, 4.6112N -74.3104W, LMdf, 29/vi/2014. Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.4093N -74.4885W, PMmf, 12/vi/2015 y 4.4338N -74.4733W, PMmf, 9/v/2014. Guaviare, San José, 2.5868N -72.6259W, Tmf, 17/ii/2015. Huila, La Plata, 2.4664N -75.7114W, PMmf, 16/vii/2015. Magdalena, Ciénaga, 10.9833N -74.2062W, Tvdf, 13/v/2015; 10.7684N -74.0254W, Tvdf, 14/v/2015 y 10.7658N -74.0254W, Tvdf, 14/v/2015. Santander, Barrancabermeja, 7.0821N -73.8552W, Tmf, 2/iv/2014. Vichada, Puerto Carreño, 6.2512N -67.5325W, Tdf, 12/xii/2014.

***Frankliniella diversa* Hood**

COLOMBIA: 1♀ 1♂, Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.6997N -75.3151W, Tdf, 6/x/2015. Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 4.6909N -74.2027W, LMdf, 11/x/2016.

***Frankliniella espeletiae* Berzosa**

COLOMBIA: 15♀ 3♂, Cundinamarca, Páramo Cruz Verde, 4.550N -73.9972W, SAp, /x/2017. Cundinamarca, Sibaté, 4.3771N -74.2491W, SAp, 17/i/2015. Santander, Cerrito, 6.8063N -72.6249W, SAp, 3/vi/2016.

***Frankliniella fallaciosa* Priesner**

COLOMBIA: 21♀, Boyacá, Tinjacá, 5.5989N -73.6581W, LMdf, 2/v/2013. Boyacá, Tunja, 5.4836N -73.46775W, LMdf, 11/ii/2015. Cundinamarca, Chipaque, 4.4441N -74.0582W, LMmf, 29/xi/2014. Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 4.6909N -74.2027W, LMdf, 11/x/2016 y 4.6792N -74.2581W, LMdf, 4/v/2015. Quindío, Córdoba- Rioverde, 4.4075N -75.7348W, PMmf, 15/ix/2014. Quindío, Quimbaya, 4.6426N -75.7916W, PMmf, 15/ix/2014.

***Frankliniella fulvipennis* Moulton**

COLOMBIA: 2♀, Antioquia, Marinilla, 5.22941N -75.27625W, LMvmf, 12/ii/2014. Huila, Garzón, 2.3349N -75.5173W, Tdf, 21/x/2015.

***Frankliniella fulvipes* Bagnall**

COLOMBIA: 2♀, Boyacá, Tinjacá, 5.5989N -73.6581W, LMdf, 2/v/2013. Magdalena, Ciénaga, 10.7502N -74.0548W, Tvdf, 15/v/2015.

***Frankliniella gardeniae* Moulton**

COLOMBIA: 3446♀ 1267♂, Antioquia, Fredonia, 5.8544N -75.7208W, PMvmf, 6/v/2015. Antioquia, Jericó, 5.8219N -75.7154W, LMvmf, 19/iii/2015. Antioquia, La Ceja, 6.0324N -75.3804W, LMvmf, 12/ii/2014. Antioquia, Marinilla, 5.2294N -75.2762W, LMvmf, 12/ii/2014. Antioquia, Valdivia, 7.1651N -75.4401W, PMvmf, 8/i/2016. Antioquia, Venecia, 5.9227N -75.7816W, PMmf, 6/v/2015 y 5.97952N -75.78286W, PMmf, 6/v/2015. Arauca, Tame, 6.5828N -71.5006W, Tmf, 11/i/2014. Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.7393N -75.2363W, Tdf, 23/xi/2015; 9.6997N -75.3151W, Tdf, 6/x/2015 y 9.734N -75.2218W, Tdf, 8/x/2015. Bolívar, San Jacinto, 9.8297N -75.1352W, Tdf, 7/x/2015. Bolívar, San Juan Nepomuceno, 9.9675N -75.1541W, Tdf, 7/x/2015. Boyacá, Buenavista, 5.4975N -73.9369W, LMmf, 10/xi/2016. Boyacá, Tunja, 5.5751N -73.6484W, LMdf, 11/ii/2015. Caldas, Anserma, 5.2885N -75.0491W, LMmf, 10/iv/2014. Caldas, Aranzazu, 5.2706N -75.4792W, LMvmf, 12/iii/2015; 5.3105N -75.4788W, LMvmf, 22/v/2014; 5.2903N -75.4751W, LMvmf, 22/v/2014; 5.2741N -75.4972W, LMvmf, 3/iii/2015 y 5.2652N -75.5175W, LMvmf, 7/iii/2014. Caldas, Manizales, 4.9095N -75.6238W, LMmf, 1/vii/2016. Caldas, Manzanares, 5.2474N -75.1617W, LMvmf, 12/ii/2015 y 5.2568N -75.1555W, LMvmf, 12/ii/2015. Caldas, Marquetalia, 5.3001N -75.0515W, PMvmf, 10/ii/2015; 5.2931N -75.0614W, PMvmf,

11/ii/2015; 5.2802N -75.0535W, PMvmf, 11/ii/2015; 5.2581N -75.0512W, PMvmf, 14/iv/2010 y 5.3148N -75.1049W, PMvmf, 22/v/2014. Caldas, Pácora, 5.5292N -75.4531W, PMvmf, 10/ii/2015; 5.5252N -75.4661W, PMvmf, 16/ii/2015; 5.531231N -75.471362W, PMvmf, 17/ii/2015; 5.532272N -75.466645W, PMvmf, 18/ii/2015; 5.51206N -75.47656W, PMvmf, 22/v/2014; 5.507166N -75.444087W, PMvmf, 26/i/2015; 5.524966N -75.433199W, PMvmf, 26/i/2015; 5.529272N -75.445401W, PMvmf, 5/ii/2015 y 5.521155N -75.443529W, PMvmf, 6/vi/2015. Caldas, Salamina, 5.29417N -75.0834W, PMvmf, 22/v/2014; 5.36294N -75.45788W, PMvmf, 22/v/2014 y 5.42877N -75.46059W, PMvmf, 27/iii/2014. Caldas, Victoria, 5.317755N -74.910711W, Tmf, 18/ii/2015; 5.286693N -74.93235W, Tmf, 18/ii/2015; 5.305818N -74.927951W, Tmf, 18/ii/2015; 5.316083N -74.899828W, Tmf, 18/ii/2015; 5.31698N -74.918822W, Tmf, 18/ii/2015; 5.319836N -74.915234W, Tmf, 18/ii/2015; 5.3497N -74.931067W, Tmf, 19/ii/2015 y 5.363794N -74.899494W, Tmf, 19/ii/2015. Cesar, Manaure, 10.390196N -73.009308W, PMdf, 19/v/2015 y 10.372499N -73.00702W, PMdf, 19/v/2015. Cesar, Pueblo Bello, 10.414197N -73.619566W, PMmf, 1/x/2015; 10.382741N -73.666643W, PMmf, 2/x/2015; 10.41209N -73.608156W, PMmf, 2/x/2015; 10.420034N -73.58217W, PMmf, 21/i/2016 y 10.433076N -73.576577W, PMmf, 21/i/2016. Córdoba, Ciénaga de oro, 8.91216N -75.58347W, Tdf, 27/x/2015 y 8.9399N -75.56412W, Tdf, 27/x/2015. Córdoba, Lorica, 9.19208N -75.8162W, Tdf, 27/x/2015 y 9.30671N -75.89022W, Tdf, 27/x/2015. Córdoba, San Pelayo, 8.94091N -75.82869W, Tdf, 27/x/2015. Cundinamarca, Anapoima, 4.541428N -74.540683W, Tdf, 10/v/2014 y 4.559642N -74.52085W, Tdf, 7/iii/2014. Cundinamarca, Anolaima, 4.78079N -74.4216W, LMmf, 20/iii/2019. Cundinamarca, Bogotá, 4.636461N -74.088482W, LMdf, 26/i/2015 y 4.66807N -74.100225W, LMdf, 26/i/2015. Cundinamarca, Bojacá, 4.694889N -74.371386W, LMdf, 2/v/2015. Cundinamarca, Cajicá, 4.636479N -74.088501W, LMdf, 28/i/2015. Cundinamarca, Chipaque, 4.444161N -74.058234W, LMmf, 29/xi/2014. Cundinamarca, Fusagasugá, 4.29634N -74.46428W, PMmf, 8/iii/2013. Cundinamarca, Guasca, 4.844N -73.8855W, LMdf, 16/xi/2015. Cundinamarca, Guayabetal, 4.353319N -73.845666W, PMpf, 26/iv/2013 y 4.353319N -73.84566W, PMpf, 26/iv/2013. Cundinamarca, La Mesa, 4.536586N -74.537189W, PMmf, 7/v/2014; 4.546858N -74.474013W, PMmf, 7/v/2014; 4.651471N -74.575204W, PMmf, 8/v/2014; 4.627529N -74.485337W, PMmf, 8/v/2014; 4.63804N -74.517138W, PMmf, 8/v/2014; 4.651161N -74.569623W, PMmf, 8/v/2014; 4.63588N -74.511552W, PMmf, 8/v/2014; 4.647982N -74.535279W, PMmf, 8/v/2014 y 4.635878N -74.511538W, PMmf, 8/v/2014. Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 4.690965N -74.202702W, LMdf, 11/x/2016; 4.6948N -74.20173W, LMdf, 20/ii/2016 y 4.693848N -74.204646W, LMdf, 3/x/2014. Cundinamarca, Pacho, 5.136915N -74.161523W, LMmf, 29/i/2015. Cundinamarca, Soacha, 4.611284N -74.310401W, LMdf, 29/vi/2014. Cundinamarca, Sopó, 4.917166N -73.965532W, LMdf, 26/xii/2014. Cundinamarca, Tibacuy, 4.35324N -74.47045W, PMmf, 19/xi/2014. Cundinamarca, Tocaima, 4.488333N -74.623333W, Tdf, 10/v/2014. Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.43483N -74.4724W, PMmf, 28/08/2017; 4.428985N -

74.482743W, PMmf, 11/vi/2015; 4.433786N -74.473294W, PMmf, 11/vi/2015; 4.435288N -74.470878W, PMmf, 11/vi/2015; 4.409371N -74.488582W, PMmf, 12/vi/2015; 4.462159N -74.524544W, PMmf, 12/vi/2015; 4.44884N -74.55662W, PMmf, 16/viii/2013; 4.4351N -74.4678W, PMmf, 16/viii/2013; 4.4350N -74.4678W, PMmf, 18/iv/2013; 4.435083N -74.467833W, PMmf, 18/iv/2013; 4.43519N -74.46811W, PMmf, 19/vii/2013; 4.43386N -74.47334W, PMmf, 19/vii/2013; 4.43715N -74.468297W, PMmf, 2/xi/2012; 4.43483N -74.4724W, PMmf, 28/viii/2012; 4.43533N -74.47079W, PMmf, 28/viii/2012; 4.444161N -74.058234W, PMmf, 29/xi/2014 y 4.433831N -74.473306W, PMmf, 9/v/2014. Guaviare, San José, 2.202071N -72.480836W, Tmf, 18/ii/2015; 2.533573N -72.592642W, Tmf, 19/ii/2015; 2.490728N -72.687032W, Tmf, 20/ii/2015 y 2.49036N -72.638702W, Tmf, 21/ii/2015. Huila, Garzón, 2.225581N -75.616487W, Tdf, 21/x/2015 y 2.334901N -75.517346W, Tdf, 21/x/2015. Huila, La Plata, 2.385731N -75.913811W, PMmf, 15/vii/2015; 2.46748N -75.789218W, PMmf, 17/vii/2015; 2.420086N -75.856514W, PMmf, 17/vii/2015; 2.45992N -75.75938W, PMmf, 17/vii/2015; 2.325581N -75.842122W, PMmf, 22/x/2015; 2.357041N -75.853029W, PMmf, 22/x/2015; 2.362296N -75.871304W, PMmf, 23/x/2015 y 2.352677N -75.8858W, PMmf, 25/ii/2015. Huila, Pitalito, 1.904521N -76.024615W, PMmf, 22/x/2015; 1.904372N -76.025182W, PMmf, 22/x/2015 y 1.906868N -76.023548W, PMmf, 22/x/2015. Huila, Villavieja, 3.3757N -75.1627W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014 y 3.313626N -75.23387W, Tdf, 7/v/2015. Magdalena, Ciénaga, 10.958634N -74.247016W, Tvdf, 11/v/2015; 10.983379N -74.206239W, Tvdf, 13/v/2015; 10.765839N -74.025427W, Tvdf, 14/v/2015 y 10.768487N -74.025438W, Tvdf, 14/v/2015. Magdalena, Zona Bananera, 10.76546N -74.14754W, Tdf, 11/v/2015. Meta, Granada, 3.475271N -73.887546W, Tmf, 16/vii/2014 y 3.475768N -73.72827W, Tmf, 25/iii/2015. Meta, Lejanías, 3.5095N -73.9761W, Tmf, 19/ii/2015 y 3.4803N -73.9551W, Tmf, 19/ii/2015. Nariño, Consacá, 1.194133N -77.467526W, LMmf, 6/viii/2015. Nariño, Pasto, 1.19872N -77.30349W, LMmf, 3/viii/2015. Nariño, Sandoná, 1.313457N -77.446074W, LMmf, 5/viii/2015; 1.298183N -77.413085W, LMmf, 5/viii/2015; 1.278632N -77.48558W, LMmf, 5/viii/2015; 1.310234N -77.447199W, LMmf, 5/viii/2015 y 1.255659N -77.483623W, LMmf, 6/viii/2015. Norte de Santander, Labateca, 7.26982N -72.49529W, LMmf, 26/viii/2016; 7.24694N -72.49185W, LMmf, 26/viii/2016; 7.29593N -72.49522W, LMmf, 26/viii/2016 y 7.26106N -72.5025W, LMmf, 26/viii/2016. Quindío, Armenia, 4.46992N -75.71111W, PMmf, 4/iii/2015; 4.44671N -75.72695W, PMmf, 6/iii/2015 y 4.56355N -75.6497W, PMmf, 8/iv/2014. Quindío, Buenavista, 4.36443N -75.77728W, PMmf, 19/ix/2013. Quindío, Calarcá, 4.40759N -75.73483W, PMmf, 11/ix/2014. Quindío, Circasia, 4.639217N -75.608994W, PMmf, 11/iv/2014. Quindío, Córdoba, 4.40805N -75.66504W, PMmf, 10/iv/2014; 4.388717N -75.692706W, PMmf, 15/ix/2014; 4.40727N -75.66975W, PMmf, 16/iv/2015 y 4.44714N -75.67395W, PMmf, 21/iv/2015. Quindío, La Tebaida, 4.26388N -75.46779W, PMmf, 16/iv/2015; 4.26443N -75.47241W, PMmf, 17/iv/2015; 4.4424N -75.84352W, PMmf, 19/iii/2015; 4.25864N -75.47503W, PMmf, 30/iii/2015;

4.47312N -75.79657W, PMmf, 5/iii/2015 y 4.467N -75.80178W, PMmf, 5/iii/2015. Quindío, Montenegro, 4.30802N -75.51703W, PMmf, 15/iv/2015; 4.56213N -75.82124W, PMmf, 15/ix/2014; 4.33497N -75.46296W, PMmf, 20/iii/2015; 4.3182N -75.48721W, PMmf, 20/iii/2015 y 4.3174N -75.48747W, PMmf, 24/iii/2015. Quindío, Pijao, 4.298613N -75.728738W, PMmf, 9/iv/2014 y 4.303824N -75.728139W, PMmf, 9/iv/2014. Quindío, Quimbaya, 4.573844N -75.657262W, PMmf, 10/iv/2014; 4.64262N -75.79166W, PMmf, 15/ix/2014; 4.39079N -75.46496W, PMmf, 24/iii/2015 y 4.39176N -75.46833W, PMmf, 24/iii/2015. Risaralda, Belén de Umbría, 5.199955N -75.86249W, PMmf, 27/viii/2013. Santander, Barichara, 6.59924N -73.16138W, PMmf, 1/iii/2015. Santander, Barrancabermeja, 7.067086N -73.7470277W, Tmf, 12/iv/2014; 7.087441N -73.838275W, Tmf, 2/iii/2014. Santander y 7.066272N -73.745411W, Tmf, 25/iv/2014. Santander, Curiti, 6.56402N -73.01203W, PMmf, 1/iii/2015. Santander, Girón, 6.97801N -73.17752W, Tdf, 15/iii/2015. Santander, Lebrija, 7.12388N -73.33955W, Tdf, 1/iii/2015; 7.12262N -73.34147W, Tdf, 1/iii/2015 y 7.08496N -73.08496W, Tdf, 14/v/2013. Santander, Paramo, 6.4053N -73.19801W, PMmf, 1/iii/2015 y 6.40215N -73.18027W, PMmf, 1/iii/2015. Santander, San Gil, 6.51209N -73.0602W, PMmf, 1/iii/2015; 6.59919N -73.15163W, PMmf, 1/iii/2015; 6.51137N -73.05621W, PMmf, 1/iii/2015; 6.58112N -73.17094W, PMmf, 15/iii/2015; 6.5941N -73.15231W, PMmf, 15/iii/2015; 6.58555N -73.15493W, PMmf, 15/iii/2015; 6.5814N -73.1632W, PMmf, 15/iii/2015 y 6.58226N -73.17181W, PMmf, 15/iii/2015. Santander, Valle de San José, 6.43489N -73.13036W, PMmf, 15/iii/2015. Tolima, Armero, 4.6778N -74.9052W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014 y 4.6806N -74.9086W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014. Tolima, Espinal- Nataima, 4.280503N -75.062185W, Tdf, 5/v/2015. Tolima, Fresno, 5.23498N -75.017303W, PMvmf, 1/vii/2016; 5.15149N -75.020238W, PMvmf, 21/vi/2014 y 5.179715N -74.980742W, PMvmf, 23/iv/2015. Tolima, Guamo, 4.028521N -74.921304W, Tdf, 15/ix/2014. Tolima, Mariquita, 5.153531N -74.908345W, Tmf, 11/i/2015; 5.153485N -74.908439W, Tmf, 20/vi/2014 y 5.182595N -74.954322W, Tmf, 21/vi/2014. Valle, Caicedonia, 4.3233N -75.87146W, PMmf, 30/iv/2013. Valle del Cauca, Sevilla, 4.258227N -75.912912W, PMmf, 16/ix/2015; 4.249836N -75.927734W, PMmf, 17/ix/2015; 4.254633N -75.930141W, PMmf, 17/ix/2015 y 4.259111N -75.927541W, PMmf, 17/ix/2015.

***Frankliniella gemina* Bagnall**

COLOMBIA: 6♀ 3♂, Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.4289N -74.4827W, PMmf, 11/vi/2015.

***Frankliniella gossypiana* (Hood)**

COLOMBIA: 83♀ 24♂, Antioquia, El Peñón- Marinilla, 6.226575N -75.266659W, PMmf, 5/i/2016. Antioquia, Valdivia, 7.165029N -75.440098W, PMvmf, 8/i/2016. Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.737875N -75.20521W, Tdf, 10/vii/2014; 9.726718N -75.166036W, Tdf, 10/vii/2014 y 9.748888N -

75.242205W, Tdf, 11/vii/2014. Bolívar, Mompos, 9.250293N -74.532616W, Tdf, 10/ix/2015. Boyacá, Buenavista, 5.4975833N -73.9369167W, LMmf, 10/xi/2016. Boyacá, Villa de Leyva, 5.637464N -73.557759W, LMdf, 21/xii/2015. Cesar, Chimichagua, 9.35384N -73.885148W, Tdf, 21/v/2015. Córdoba, Ciénaga de oro, 8.87464N -75.69423W, Tdf, 27/x/2015; 8.91216N -75.58347W, Tdf, 27/x/2015 y 8.9399N -75.56412W, Tdf, 27/x/2015. Córdoba, Lorica, 9.30671N -75.89022W, Tdf, 27/x/2015. Córdoba, San Pelayo, 8.94091N -75.82869W, Tdf, 27/x/2015 y 8.95104N -75.85246W, Tdf, 27/x/2015. Cundinamarca, Anapoima, 4.559642N -74.52085W, Tdf, 7/iii/2014. Cundinamarca, Guasca, 4.844N -73.8855W, LMdf, 25/iv/2016. Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 4.68499N -74.204043W, LMdf, 6/v/2014. Cundinamarca, Nemocón, 5.1181667N -73.8588055W, LMdf, 1/x/2015. Cundinamarca, Ricaurte, 4.2888N -74.73375W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014. Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.428985N -74.482743W, PMmf, 11/vi/2015. Huila, Pital, 2.33769N -75.85064W, Tdf, 23/x/2015. Huila, Villavieja, 3.36525N -75.1631W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014 y 3.1961N -75.2293W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014. Magdalena, Ciénaga, 10.765839N -74.025427W, Tvdf, 14/v/2015. Magdalena, Santa Marta (PNN Tairona), 11.3117N -73.9382W, Tmf, 17/i/2016. Meta, Granada, 3.475768N -73.72827W, Tmf, 25/iii/2015. Meta, Puerto Gaitán, 4.575698N -71.34536W, Tmf, 26/viii/2015. Quindío, Quimbaya, 4.573844N -75.657262W, PMmf, 10/iv/2014. Sucre, Colosó, 9.462115N -75.383417W, Tdf, 12/xi/2015. Sucre, Los palmitos, 9.452393N -75.225704W, Tdf, 9/vii/2014. Tolima, Armero, 4.926917N -74.885119W, Tdf, 22/iv/2015; 4.9152N -74.8748W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014 y 5.0142N -74.9051W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014. Tolima, Espinal, 4.20205N -74.90041W, Tdf, 6/v/2015. Tolima, Espinal- Nataima, 4.280503N -75.062185W, Tdf, 5/v/2015.

***Frankliniella insularis* (Franklin)**

COLOMBIA: 369♀ 451♂, Antioquia, Carepa, 7.7594333N -76.6686778W, Tmf, 3/iii/2017. Antioquia, Fredonia, 5.85441N -75.7208W, PMvmf, 6/v/2015. Antioquia, Jericó, 5.82198N -75.71543W, LMvmf, 19/iii/2015. Antioquia, Tarso, 5.88822N -75.8006W, PMmf, 13/iii/2015. Antioquia, Venecia, 5.96586N -75.78358W, PMmf, 16/iii/2015 y 5.97952N -75.78286W, PMmf, 6/v/2015. Arauca, Tame, 6.52025N -71.69259W, Tmf, 12/i/2014. Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.69978N -75.315197W, Tdf, 6/x/2015 y 9.6895N -75.2923W, Tdf, 8/x/2015. Boyacá, Buenavista, 5.4975833N -73.9369167W, LMmf, 10/xi/2016. Cesar, Astrea, 9.475394N -73.881196W, Tdf, 21/v/2015. Cesar, Pueblo Bello, 10.382741N -73.666643W, PMmf, 2/x/2015; 10.41209N -73.608156W, PMmf, 2/x/2015; 10.413309N -73.546733W, PMmf, 2/x/2015 y 10.433076N -73.576577W, PMmf, 21/i/2016. Córdoba, Cereté, 8.852566N -75.810333W, Tdf, 3/xii/2015. Córdoba, Ciénaga de oro, 8.87464N -75.69423W, Tdf, 27/x/2015 y 8.9399N -75.56412W, Tdf, 27/x/2015. Cundinamarca, Anapoima, 4.559642N -74.52085W, Tdf, 7/iii/2014. Cundinamarca, Fusagasugá, 4.30057N -74.46549W, PMmfM, 8/iii/2013. Cundinamarca, La Mesa, 4.635878N -74.511538W, PMmf, 8/v/2014. Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.428985N -74.482743W, PMmf, 11/vi/2015;

4.433786N -74.473294W, PMmf, 11/vi/2015 y 4.43533N -74.47079W, PMmf, 28/viii/2012. Guaviare, San José, 2.58681N -72.625979W, Tmf, 17/ii/2015 y 2.599419N -72.759939W, Tmf, 22/ii/2015. Huila, Aipe, 3.221454N -75.245126W, Tdf, 17/vii/2015. Huila, Garzón, 2.225581N -75.616487W, Tdf, 21/x/2015 y 2.336599N -75.512936W, Tdf, 21/x/2015. Huila, La Plata, 2.385731N -75.913811W, PMmf, 15/vii/2015; 2.474031N -75.795859W, PMmf, 16/vii/2015; 2.465539N -75.712068W, PMmf, 16/vii/2015; 2.45992N -75.75938W, PMmf, 17/vii/2015 y 2.362296N -75.871304W, PMmf, 23/x/2015. Huila, Pital, 2.188158N -75.817843W, Tdf, 22/x/2015 y 2.33769N -75.85064W, Tdf, 23/x/2015. Huila, Pitalito, 1.904372N -76.025182W, PMmf, 22/x/2015. Huila, Villavieja, 3.3757N -75.1627W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014. Magdalena, Ciénaga, 10.983379N -74.206239W, Tvdf, 13/v/2015; 10.768487N -74.025438W, Tvdf, 14/v/2015; 10.765839N -74.025427W, Tvdf, 14/v/2015; 10.585559N -74.248604W, Tvdf, 15/v/2015 y 10.745896N -74.060816W, Tvdf, 15/v/2015. Magdalena, Santa Marta (PNN Tairona), 11.307409N -73.931233W, Tmf, 15/v/2015. Magdalena, Zona Bananera, 10.76546N -74.14754W, Tdf, 11/v/2015. Meta, Granada, 3.475768N -73.72827W, Tmf, 25/iii/2015. Quindío, Calarcá, 4.40759N -75.73483W, PMmf, 11/ix/2014. Quindío, Circasia, 4.642803N -75.607795W, PMmf, 11/iv/2014. Quindío, Córdoba, 4.42907N -75.718566W, PMmf, 9/iv/2014. Quindío, La Tebaida, 4.4424N -75.84352W, PMmf, 19/iii/2015 y 4.26062N -75.4749W, PMmf, 30/iii/2015. Quindío, Montenegro, 4.33497N -75.46296W, PMmf, 20/iii/2015. Quindío, Quimbaya, 4.607297N -75.794192W, PMmf, 10/iv/2014 y 4.64262N -75.79166W, PMmf, 15/ix/2014. Santander, Barrancabermeja, 7.059213N -73.861266W, Tmf, 2/iv/2014. Santander, Girón, 6.9875N -73.1683W, Tdf, 15/iii/2015. Santander, Lebrija, 7.12388N -73.33955W, Tdf, 1/iii/2015. Santander, San Gil, 6.59919N -73.15163W, PMmf, 1/iii/2015. Sucre, Colosó, 9.480617N -75.369066W, Tdf, 12/xi/2015. Sucre, Sampués, 9.177651N -75.290154W, Tdf, 10/xi/2015. Tolima, Armero, 4.926917N -74.885119W, Tdf, 22/iv/2015; 5.164067N -75.022068W, Tdf, 22/iv/2015; 5.014339N -74.90034W, Tdf, 24/iv/2015 y 4.6778N -74.9052W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014. Tolima, Espinal, 4.1939N -74.9661W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014. Tolima, Espinal- Nataima, 4.280503N -75.062185W, Tdf, 5/v/2015 y 4.181953N -74.953396W, Tdf, 6/v/2015. Tolima, Natagaima, 3.6771N -75.1027W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014. Valle del Cauca, Sevilla, 4.259111N -75.927541W, PMmf, 17/ix/2015. Vichada, Puerto Carreño, 6.15356N -67.68333W, Tdf, 26/vi/2015 y 6.19768N -67.46557W, Tdf, 29/i/2015.

***Frankliniella invasor* Sakimura**

COLOMBIA: 104♀ 112♂, Cesar, Astrea, 9.471301N -73.880263W, Tdf, 21/v/2015. Cesar, Astrea, 9.475394N -73.881196W, Tdf, 21/v/2015. Cesar, Chimichagua, 9.332042N -73.862055W, Tdf, 21/v/2015. Cesar, Manaure, 10.390196N -73.009308W, PMdf, 19/v/2015. Cesar, Pueblo Bello, 10.414197N -73.619566W, PMmf, 1/x/2015; 10.433076N -73.576577W, PMmf, 21/i/2016 y 10.420034N

-73.58217W, PMmf, 21/i/2016. Córdoba, Ciénaga de oro, 8.87464N -75.69423W, Tdf, 27/x/2015 y 8.9399N -75.56412W, Tdf, 27/x/2015. Cundinamarca, Bogotá, 4.636461N -74.088482W, LMdf, 26/i/2015. Cundinamarca, Bojacá, 4.694889N -74.371386W, LMdf, 2/v/2015 y 4.64121N -74.30291W, LMdf, 2/v/2015. Cundinamarca, Cajicá, 4.636479N -74.088501W, LMdf, 28/i/2015. Cundinamarca, La Mesa, 4.63588N -74.511552W, PMmf, 8/v/2014 y 4.627529N -74.485337W, PMmf, 8/v/2014. Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 4.685778N -74.219114W, LMdf, 6/v/2014. Cundinamarca, Pacho, 5.136915N -74.161523W, LMmf, 29/i/2015. Cundinamarca, Tocancipá, 4.98875N -73.904388W, LMdf, 1/viii/2015. Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.435288N -74.470878W, PMmf, 11/vi/2015 y 4.409371N -74.488582W, PMmf, 12/vi/2015. Huila, Garzón, 2.334901N -75.517346W, Tdf, 21/x/2015. Huila, La Plata, 2.45992N -75.75938W, PMmf, 17/vii/2015. Magdalena, Ciénaga, 10.88087N -74.183388W, Tvdf, 11/v/2015; 10.92145N -74.204832W, Tvdf, 11/v/2015; 10.958634N -74.247016W, Tvdf, 11/v/2015; 10.983379N -74.206239W, Tvdf, 13/v/2015; 10.765839N -74.025427W, Tvdf, 14/v/2015; 10.768487N -74.025438W, Tvdf, 14/v/2015 y 10.750274N -74.054876W, Tvdf, 15/v/2015. Magdalena, Santa Marta (PNN Tairona), 11.307409N -73.931233W, Tmf, 9/xii/2015. Magdalena, Zona Bananera, 10.76546N -74.14754W, Tdf, 11/v/2015. Nariño, Consacá, 1.194133N -77.467526W, LMmf, 6/viii/2015. Nariño, Pasto, 1.19872N -77.30349W, LMmf, 3/viii/2015. Nariño, Sandoná, 1.310234N -77.447199W, LMmf, 5/viii/2015. Quindío, Circasia, 4.642803N -75.607795W, PMmf, 11/iv/2014 y 4.639217N -75.608994W, PMmf, 11/iv/2014. Quindío, La Tebaida, 4.26388N -75.46779W, PMmf, 16/iv/2015 y 4.26443N -75.47241W, PMmf, 17/iv/2015. Risaralda, Belén de Umbría, 5.192092N -75.862612W, PMmf, 27/viii/2013. Santander, Barrancabermeja, 7.087441N -73.838275W, Tmf, 2/iii/2014 y 7.066272N -73.745411W, Tmf, 25/iv/2014. Santander, Girón, 6.9875N -73.1683W, Tdf, 15/iii/2015. Santander, Lebrija, 7.12263N -73.34147W, Tdf, 1/iii/2015 y 7.08496N -73.08496W, Tdf, 14/v/2013. Santander, San Gil, 6.51137N -73.05621W, PMmf, 1/iii/2015. Tolima, Armero, 5.014339N -74.90034W, Tdf, 24/iv/2015. Valle, Sevilla, 4.258227N -75.912912W, PMmf, 16/ix/2015 y 4.254633N -75.930141W, PMmf, 17/ix/2015.

***Frankliniella kelliæ* Sakimura**

COLOMBIA: 182♀ 46♂, Bolívar, San Jacinto, 9.8734N -75.1885W, Tdf, 24/xi/2015. Cesar, Manaure, 10.3901N -73.0093W, PMdf, 19/v/2015. Cesar, Pueblo bello, 10.4201N -73.58217W, PMmf, 21/i/2016 y 10.4331N -73.5765W, PMmf, 21/i/2016. Cundinamarca, Tocancipá, 4.9887N -73.9043W, LMdf, 1/viii/2015. Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.4093N -74.4885W, PMmf, 12/vi/2015. Huila, Garzón, 2.3349N -75.5173W, Tdf, 21/x/2015. Huila, La Plata, 2.3622N -75.8713W, PMmf, 23/x/2015. Huila, Pitalito, 1.9043N -76.02518W, PMmf, 22/x/2015. Magdalena, Ciénaga, 10.9833N -74.2062W, Tvdf, 13/v/2015. Magdalena, Zona Bananera, 10.7654N -74.1475W, Tdf, 11/v/2015. Nariño, Pasto, 1.1987N -77.3034W, LMmf, 3/viii/2015. Nariño, Sandoná, 1.2786N -77.4855W, LMmf, 5/viii/2015. Santander, Barichara,

6.5992N -73.1613W, PMmf, 1/iii/2015. Santander, Lebrija, 7.1226N -73.3414W, Tdf, 1/iii/2015. Santander, Valle de San José, 6.4348N -73.1303W, PMmf, 15/iii/2015. Valle del Cauca, Sevilla, 4.2582N -75.9129W, PMmf, 16/ix/2015 y 4.2546N -75.9301W, PMmf, 17/ix/2015.

***Frankliniella lorena* Mound & Marullo**

COLOMBIA: 1♀, Huila, Garzón, 2.3349N -75.5173W, Tdf, 21/x/2015.

***Frankliniella mekokara* Mound & Marullo**

COLOMBIA: 7♀, Cundinamarca, Soacha, 4.6112N -74.3104W, LMdf, 29/vi/2014.

***Frankliniella melanommata* Williams**

COLOMBIA: 129♀ 28♂, Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.7272N -75.1633W, Tdf, 7/x/2015; 9.7307N -75.2095W, Tdf, 8/x/2015 y 9.8005N -75.1255W, Tdf, 8/vii/2014. Cesar, Manaure, 10.3724N -73.0071W, PMdf, 19/v/2015. Cesar, Valledupar, 10.4291N -73.3725W, Tdf, 29/ix/2015. Córdoba, Ciénaga de oro, 8.8746N -75.6942W, Tdf, 27/x/2015 y 8.9121N -75.5834W, Tdf, 27/x/2015. Córdoba, San Pelayo, 8.9409N -75.8286W, Tdf, 27/x/2015. Guaviare, San José, 2.5868N -72.62597W, Tmf, 17/ii/2015 y 2.2021N -72.4808W, Tmf, 18/ii/2015. Huila, Villavieja, 3.3136N -75.2338W, Tdf, 7/v/2015. Magdalena, Ciénaga, 10.5855N -74.2486W, Tvdf, 15/v/2015. Magdalena, Zona Bananera, 10.7654N -74.1475W, Tdf, 11/v/2015. Meta, Granada, 3.4757N -73.7282W, Tmf, 25/iii/2015. Meta, Lejanías, 3.4803N -73.9551W, Tmf, 19/ii/2015. Meta, Villavicencio, 4.0761N -73.5847W, Tmf, 15/iv/2013 y 4.0654N -73.4453W, Tmf, 20/viii/2015. Quindío, Quimbaya, 4.5738N -75.6572W, PMmf, 10/iv/2014. Santander, Barrancabermeja, 6.9625N -73.7364W, Tmf, 14/iv/2014 y 6.9677N -73.7447W, Tmf, 14/iv/2014. Santander, Lebrija, 7.1238N -73.3395W, Tdf, 1/iii/2015. Sucre, Sampués, 9.1776N -75.2901W, Tdf, 10/xi/2015. Tolima, Armero, 5.0142N -74.9051W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 5.0063N -74.9059W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014 y 4.9152N -74.8748W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014. Tolima, Fresno, 5.1797N -74.9807W, PMvmf, 23/iv/2015.

***Frankliniella minuta* (Moulton)**

COLOMBIA: 16♀ 2♂, Arauca, Tame, 6.58287N -71.5006W, Tmf, 11/i/2014. Cesar, Pueblo bello, 10.4331N -73.5765W, PMmf, 21/i/2016. Cundinamarca, Cogua, 5.0565N -73.929W, LMdf, 19/xi/2015, 8/x/2015. Cundinamarca, La Mesa, 4.6518N -74.5549W, PMmf, 8/v/2014. Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 4.6938N -74.2046W, LMdf, 3/x/2014. Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.4203N -74.4708W, PMmf, 19/vii/2013 y 4.4338N -74.4733W, PMmf, 9/v/2014. Quindío, Circasia, 4.6392N -75.6089W, PMmf, 11/iv/2014.

***Frankliniella musaepeda* Hood**

COLOMBIA: 118♀ 40♂, Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.7274N -75.1631W, Tdf, 8/x/2015. Cesar, Pueblo Bello, 10.3827N -73.6666W, PMmf, 2/x/2015. Cundinamarca, Guayabetal, 4.2207N -73.8027W, PMpf, 26/iv/2013. Cundinamarca, Tocancipá, 4.9887N -73.9043W, LMdf, 1/viii/2015. Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.4351N -74.4678W, PMmf, 18/iv/2013 y 4.4338N -74.4733W, PMmf, 9/v/2014. Guaviare, San José, 2.5994N -72.7599W, Tmf, 22/ii/2015. Huila, Garzón, 2.3349N -75.5173W, Tdf, 21/x/2015. Huila, La Plata, 2.4674N -75.7892W, PMmf, 17/vii/2015; 2.3376N -75.8506W, PMmf, 22/x/2015 y 2.3622N -75.8713W, PMmf, 23/x/2015. Huila, Pitalito, 1.9043N -76.0251W, PMmf, 22/x/2015. Magdalena, Zona Bananera, 10.7654N -74.1475W, Tdf, 11/v/2015. Meta, Granada, 3.4757N -73.7282W, Tmf, 25/iii/2015. Nariño, Pasto, 1.1987N -77.3034W, LMmf, 3/viii/2015. Nariño, Sandoná, 1.3102N -77.4471W, LMmf, 5/viii/2015; 1.2786N -77.4855W, LMmf, 5/viii/2015; 1.3134N -77.4461W, LMmf, 5/viii/2015 y 1.2784N -77.4848W, LMmf, 5/viii/2015. Quindío, Armenia, 4.5635N -75.6497W, PMmf, 8/iv/2014. Quindío, La Tebaida, 4.4424N -75.84352W, PMmf, 19/iii/2015. Quindío, Quimbaya, 4.57384N -75.6572W, PMmf, 10/iv/2014. Santander, Barrancabermeja, 7.0874N -73.8382W, Tmf, 2/iii/2014. Tolima, Espinal- Nataima, 4.2805N -75.0621W, Tdf, 5/v/2015. Tolima, Mariquita, 5.1535N -74.9083W, Tmf, 11/i/2015. Valle del Cauca, Sevilla, 4.2582N -75.9129W, PMmf, 16/ix/2015.

***Frankliniella nakaharai* Sakimura & O'Neill**

COLOMBIA: 1♀, Cundinamarca, Cogua, 5.0565N -73.929W, LMdf, 6/x/2016.

***Frankliniella nigricauda* Hood**

COLOMBIA: 3♀, Magdalena, Ciénaga, 10.7684N -74.0254W, Tvdf, 14/v/2015.

***Frankliniella occidentalis* (Pergande)**

COLOMBIA: 383♀ 178♂, Antioquia, El Peñón- Marinilla, 6.2265N -75.2666W, PMmf, 5/i/2016. Antioquia, Rionegro, 6.1903N -75.3549W, LMmf, 3/x/2014 y 6.1903N -75.3549W, LMmf, 3/x/2014. Boyacá, Buenavista, 5.4975N -73.9369W, LMmf, 10/xi/2016. Boyacá, Tinjacá, 5.5989N -73.6582W, LMdf, 2/v/2013. Boyacá, Tunja, 5.4836N -73.4677W, LMdf, 11/ii/2015. Boyacá, Villa de Leyva, 5.6323N -73.5594W, LMdf, 2/v/2013 y 5.4992N -73.4914W, LMdf, 21/xii/2015. Caldas, Aranzazu, 5.2658N -75.4991W, LMvmf, 3/iii/2015. Cundinamarca, Bogotá, 4.6361N -74.0884W, LMdf, 26/i/2015. Cundinamarca, Bojacá, 4.6948N -74.3713W, LMdf, 2/v/2015. Cundinamarca, Cajicá, 4.9088N -74.0097W, LMdf, 3/x/2014. Cundinamarca, Choachí, 4.4767N -73.9181W, PMmf, 18/ix/2016; 4.5211N -73.9228W, PMmf, 22/iii/2013 y 4.5223N -73.9205W, PMmf, 22/iii/2013. Cundinamarca, Cogua, 5.0564N -73.9289W, LMdf, 1/ix/2015. Cundinamarca, Cucunubá, 5.2523N -73.7768W, LMdf, 19/ii/2016. Cundinamarca, El rosal, 4.8419N -74.2633W, LMdf, 21/x/2014. Cundinamarca, Facatativá, 4.7779N -

74.3234W, LMdf, 22/viii/2016, 19/ix/2016, 12/ix/2016, 26/ix/2016, 3/x/2016, 14/xi/2016, 21/xi/2016, 28/xii/2016. Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 4.6806N -74.2167W, LMdf, 1/xi/2016; 4.6909N -74.2027W, LMdf, 11/x/2016; 4.6912N -74.2024W, LMdf, 18/iv/2015; 4.6947N -74.2017W, LMdf, 18/iv/2015; 4.6948N -74.2017W, LMdf, 20/ii/2016; 4.6944N -74.2047W, LMdf, 29/v/2013; 4.6867N -74.2043W, LMdf, 29/vii/2015; 4.6839N -74.1992W, LMdf, 29/vii/2015; 4.6728N -74.2045W, LMdf, 29/vii/2015; 4.6938N -74.2046W, LMdf, 3/x/2014; 4.6806N -74.2167W, LMdf, 3/vi/2016; 4.6943N -74.2023W, LMdf, 30/xii/2015; 4.6912N -74.2024W, LMdf, 30/xii/2015; 4.6792N -74.2582W, LMdf, 4/v/2015; 4.68499N -74.204043W, LMdf, 6/v/2014 y 4.6857N -74.2191W, LMdf, 6/v/2014. Cundinamarca, Mosquera- Mondoñedo, 4.6536N -74.2866W, LMdf, 4/v/2015. Cundinamarca, Nemocón, 5.1181N -73.8588W, LMdf, 1/viii/2015, 1/ix/2015, 1/x/2015, 2/xi/2015, 23/xi/2015, 7/xii/2015, 14/xii/2015, 30/xii/2015, 4/iv/2016, 11/iv/2016, 18/iv/2016, 25/iv/2016, 2/v/2016, 16/v/2016, 23/v/2016, 6/vi/2016, 7/iii/2016, 13/vi/2016, 20/vi/2016, 27/vi/2016, 4/vii/2016, 18/vii/2016, 8/viii/2016, 24/x/2016, 7/xi/2016, 31/xi/2016, 5/xii/2016. Cundinamarca, Soacha, 4.5841N -74.2651W, LMdf, 4/v/2015. Cundinamarca, Sopó, 4.9171N -73.9655W, LMdf, 26/xii/2014. Cundinamarca, Subachoque, 5.0021N -74.1293W, LMdf, 23/viii/2014. Cundinamarca, Tocancipá, 4.9887N -73.9043W, LMdf, 1/viii/2015, 1/ix/2015, 12/x/2015, 26/x/2015, 28/x/2015, 9/v/2016, 16/v/2016, 18/vii/2016. Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.4441N -74.0582W, PMmf, 29/xi/2014. Huila, La Plata, 2.3376N -75.8506W, PMmf, 22/x/2015. Nariño, Pasto, 1.1987N -77.3034W, LMmf, 1/viii/2015 y 1.1987N -77.3034W, LMmf, 3/viii/2015. Quindío, Circasia, 4.6392N -75.6089W, PMmf, 11/iv/2014.

***Frankliniella oxyura* Bagnall**

COLOMBIA: 2♀ 2♂, Cundinamarca, Guasca, 4.844N -73.8855W, LMdf, 19/ix/2016, 7/iv/2016. Cundinamarca, Tocancipá, 4.9887N -73.9043W, LMdf; 21/iii/2016.

***Frankliniella panamensis* Hood**

COLOMBIA: 2683♀ 416♂. Antioquia, Barbosa, 6.43404N -75.280422W, PMmf, 3/ii/2017. Antioquia, El Peñón- Marinilla, 6.226575N -75.266659W, PMmf, 5/i/2016. Antioquia, Rionegro, 6.19032N -75.35494W, LMmf, 3/x/2014 y 6.19032N -75.35495W, LMmf, 3/x/2014. Boyacá, Buenavista, 5.4975833N -73.9369167W, LMmf, 10/xi/2016. Boyacá, Nuevo Colón, 5.340106N -73.441045W, LMdf, 3/iv/2016 y 5.340108N -73.441557W, LMdf, 3/iv/2016. Boyacá, Tinjacá, 5.598916N -73.658027W, LMdf, 2/v/2013. Boyacá, Tunja, 5.483666N -73.46775W, LMdf, 11/ii/2015; 5.479472N -73.454416W, LMdf, 11/ii/2015 y 5.575055N -73.648416W, LMdf, 11/ii/2015. Boyacá, Villa de Leyva, 5.499238N -73.491408W, LMdf, 21/xii/2015. Caldas, Pácora, 5.521155N -75.443529W, PMvmf, 6/vi/2015. Cundinamarca, Anolaima, 4.78079N -74.4216W, PMmf, 20/iii/2019. Cundinamarca, Bogotá, 4.636461N -

74.088482W, LMdf, 26/i/2015. Cundinamarca, Bojacá, 4.64121N -74.30291W, LMdf, 2/v/2015; 4.69489N -74.37138W, LMdf, 2/v/2015 y 4.694889N -74.371386W, LMdf, 2/v/2015. Cundinamarca, Cajicá, 4.636479N -74.088501W, LMdf, 28/i/2015. Cundinamarca, Chía, 4.862632N -74.033083W, LMdf, 3/vi/2016. Cundinamarca, Chipaque, 4.444161N -74.058234W, LMmf, 29/xi/2014. Cundinamarca, Choachí, 4.47678N -73.91819W, PMmf, 18/ix/2016; 4.47941N -73.91868W, PMmf, 18/ix/2016; 4.52105N -73.92287W, PMmf, 22/iii/2013; 4.52238N -73.9205W, PMmf, 22/iii/2013 y 4.56473N -73.9079W, PMmf, 22/iii/2013. Cundinamarca, Cogua, 5.0565N -73.929W, LMdf, 19/xi/2015. 31/xii/2015. 18/ii/2016. 25/ii/2016. 10/iii/2016. 24/iii/2016. 31/iii/2016. 14/iv/2016. 17/xi/2016. Cundinamarca, Facatativá, 4.77797N -74.32347W, LMdf, 8/viii/2016. 22/viii/2016. 12/ix/2016. 19/ix/2016. 26/ix/2016. 3/x/2016. 10/x/2016. 17/x/2016. 24/x/2016 .14/xi/2016 .21/xi/2016. 5/xii/2016. 28/xii/2016. Cundinamarca, Guachetá, 5.361215N -73.748191W, LMdf, 21/ix/2016. Cundinamarca, Guasca, 4.8439N -73.8855W, LMdf, 1/viii/2015. 16/xi/2015. 1/viii/2016. 10/x/2016. 11/iv/2016. 11/vii/2016. 14/xi/2016. 15/viii/2016. 18/iv/2016. 18/vii/2016. 22/viii/2016. 23/v/2016. 25/iv/2016. 26/ix/2016. 30/vi/2016. 31/xi/2016. 5/xii/2016. 6/vi/2016. 7/xi/2016. 7/iv/2016. 8/viii/2016. 9/xi/2015. 9/v/2016. Cundinamarca, Guayabetal, 4.3533N -73.8456W, PMpf, 26/iv/2013. 26/iv/2013. Cundinamarca, Gutiérrez, 4.203433N -73.871955W, LMmf, 25/iv/2013. Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 4.6806N -74.2167W, LMdf, 1/xi/2016. 13/vi/2014; 4.690965N -74.202702W, LMdf, 11/x/2016; 4.691246N -74.202484W, LMdf, 18/iv/2015; 4.68217N -74.20377W, LMdf, 18/iv/2015; 4.6948N -74.20173W, LMdf, 18/iv/2015. 29/v/2013. 20/ii/2016; 4.683919N -74.199206W, LMdf, 29/vii/2015; 4.672852N -74.204577W, LMdf, 29/vii/2015; 4.694444N -74.20469W, LMdf, 3/x/2014; 4.691178N -74.20265W, LMdf, 3/x/2014; 4.693848N -74.204646W, LMdf, 3/x/2014; 4.6806N -74.2167W, LMdf, 3/vi/2016; 4.69433N -74.20237W, LMdf, 30/xii/2015; 4.691235N -74.202481W, LMdf, 30/xii/2015; 4.67929N -74.25802W, LMdf, 4/v/2015; 4.68499N -74.204043W, LMdf, 6/v/2014; 4.685778N -74.219114W, LMdf, 6/v/2014. Cundinamarca, Mosquera- Mondoñedo, 4.6536N -74.2866W, LMdf, 4/v/2015. Cundinamarca, Silvania, 4.468472N -74.385196W, PMmf, 14/i/2017 y 4.419131N -74.418957W, PMmf, 30/i/2015. Cundinamarca, Soacha, 4.611284N -74.310401W, LMdf, 29/vi/2014 y 4.58412N -74.26501W, LMdf, 4/v/2015. Cundinamarca, Sopó, 4.917166N -73.965532W, LMdf, 26/xii/2014. Cundinamarca, Subachoque, 5.002036N -74.129326W, LMdf, 23/viii/2014. Cundinamarca, Tocancipá, 4.98875N -73.904388W, LMdf, 1/viii/2015. 1/ix/2015. 22/ii/2016. Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.444161N -74.058234W, PMmf, 29/xi/2014. Huila, La Plata, 2.273111N -76.036741W, PMmf, 10/xi/2015. Huila, Pital, 2.33769N -75.85064W, LMmf, 23/x/2015. Nariño, Pasto, 1.19872N -77.30349W, LMmf, 1/viii/2015 y 1.19872N -77.30349W, LMmf, 3/viii/2015. Nariño, Sandoná, 1.278632N -77.485586W, LMmf, 5/viii/2015. Quindío, Circasia, 4.639217N -75.608994W, PMmf, 11/iv/2014 y 4.642803N -75.607795W, PMmf, 11/iv/2014. Quindío, Córdoba, 4.394218N -75.684358W, PMmf, 15/ix/2014. Quindío, Córdoba, 4.385378N -

75.679527W, PMmf, 15/ix/2014 y 4.384449N -75.691928W, PMmf, 16/viii/2014. Quindío, Quimbaya, 4.583221N -75.701433W, PMmf, 11/iv/2014. Risaralda, Apía, 5.1259N -75.9864W, LMvmf, 21/ix/2015. Risaralda, Belén de Umbría, 5.1262N -75.9865W, PMmf, 19/ix/2015. Risaralda, Quinchía, 5.3532N -75.7566W, PMvmf, 14/ix/2015. Santander, Carcasí, 6.6959N -72.5477W, LMmf, 21/v/2016. Santander, Guaca, 6.8683N -72.82745W, LMmf, 12/x/2016. Santander, Molagavita, 6.6903N -72.7817W, LMmf, 28/iv/2016. Tolima, Cajamarca, 4.3866N -75.4839W, PMmf, 3/ix/2014; 4.3877N -75.5129W, PMmf, 6/xi/2016; 4.3884N -75.5065W, PMmf, 25/iii/2014 y 4.3955N -75.4657W, PMmf, 4/iv/2018. Valle del Cauca, Sevilla, 4.2498N -75.9277W, PMmf, 17/ix/2015.

***Frankliniella paramorum* Berzosa**

COLOMBIA: 4♀, Santander, Carcasí, 6.7273N -72.5765W, SAp, 3/vi/2016. Santander, Cerrito, 6.8063N -72.6249W, SAp, 3/vi/2016.

***Frankliniella parvula* Hood**

COLOMBIA: 1894♀ 355♂. Antioquia, Apartadó, 7.9711N -76.6492W, Tmf, 1/xi/2016; 7.85435N -76.7429W, Tmf, 18/x/2016; 7.9341N -76.70032W, Tmf, 18/x/2016; 7.8231N -76.7253W, Tmf, 19/x/2016 y 8.0095N -76.6927W, Tmf, 26/x/2016. Antioquia, Carepa, 7.7794N -76.6731W, Tmf, 25/x/2016 y 7.7594333N -76.6686778W, Tmf; 3/iii/2017. Antioquia, Chigorodó, 7.70237778N -76.7329333W, Tmf, 19/x/2016 y 7.706513889N -76.7417694W, Tmf, 31/x/2016. Antioquia, El Peñón- Marinilla, 6.2265N -75.2666W, PMmf, 5/i/2016. Antioquia, Fredonia, 5.85441N -75.7208W, PMvmf, 6/v/2015. Antioquia, Venecia, 5.96586N -75.7835W, PMmf, 16/iii/2015 y 5.97952N -75.7828W, PMmf, 6/v/2015. Arauca, Tame, 6.5828N -71.5006W, Tmf, 11/i/2014 y 6.5826N -71.4981W, Tmf, 11/i/2014. Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.741646N -75.262765W, Tdf, 6/x/2015; 9.743273N -75.262019W, Tdf, 6/x/2015; 9.7341N -75.2206W, Tdf, 8/x/2015 y 9.6895N -75.2923W, Tdf, 8/x/2015. Bolívar, San Jacinto, 9.8766N -75.2159W, Tdf, 12/x/2015; 9.8924N -75.2128W, Tdf, 24/xi/2015; 9.83002N -75.1591W, Tdf, 24/xi/2015; 9.8734N -75.18854W, Tdf, 24/xi/2015; 9.87262N -75.1737W, Tdf, 24/xi/2015 y 9.7915N -75.2296W, Tdf, 7/v/2014. Cesar, Manaure, 10.3901N -73.0093W, PMdf, 19/v/2015. Cesar, Pueblo Bello, 10.4141N -73.6195W, PMmf, 1/x/2015; 10.3827N -73.6666W, PMmf, 2/x/2015; 10.41209N -73.6081W, PMmf, 2/x/2015; 10.4201N -73.5821W, PMmf, 21/i/2016 y 10.4331N -73.5765W, PMmf, 21/i/2016. Córdoba, Ciénaga de oro, 8.91216N -75.5834W, Tdf, 27/x/2015 y 8.9131N -75.5828W, Tdf, 27/x/2015. Cundinamarca, Fusagasugá, 4.2963N -74.4642W, PMmf, 8/iii/2013. Cundinamarca, Guayabetal, 4.2207N -73.8027W, PMpf, 26/iv/2013. Cundinamarca, La Mesa, 4.63804N -74.5171W, PMmf, 8/v/2014 y 4.635878N -74.5115W, PMmf, 8/v/2014. Cundinamarca, Nilo, 4.3511N -74.5385W, PMmf, 15/xii/2018. Cundinamarca, Tocaima, 4.3762N -74.5701W, PMmf, 4/x/2018. Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.4317N -

74.4703W, PMmf, 1/xi/2012; 4.4621N -74.5245W, PMmf, 12/vi/2015; 4.4351N -74.4678W, PMmf, 18/iv/2013; 4.4317N -74.47034W, PMmf, 2/xi/2012; 4.4348N -74.4724W, PMmf, 28/viii/2012 y 4.4338N -74.4733W, PMmf, 9/v/2014. Cundinamarca, Yacopí, 5.45487N -74.3394W, PMvmf, 22/ii/2019. Guaviare, San José, 2.58681N -72.6259W, Tmf, 17/ii/2015; 2.49036N -72.6387W, Tmf, 21/ii/2015 y 2.5994N -72.7599W, Tmf, 22/ii/2015. Huila, Aipe, 3.3138N -75.2326W, Tdf, 21/x/2015. Huila, Garzón, 2.2255N -75.6164W, Tdf, 21/x/2015 y 2.3349N -75.5173W, Tdf, 21/x/2015. Huila, La Plata, 2.3857N -75.9138W, PMmf, 15/vii/2015; 2.4201N -75.8565W, PMmf, 17/vii/2015; 2.3622N -75.8713W, PMmf, 23/x/2015 y 2.3526N -75.8858W, PMmf, 25/ii/2015. Huila, Pital, 2.1881N -75.8178W, Tdf, 22/x/2015. Huila, Pitalito, 1.9068N -76.0235W, PMmf, 22/x/2015. Magdalena, Ciénaga, 10.8808N -74.1833W, Tvdf, 11/v/2015; 10.9586N -74.2471W, Tvdf, 11/v/2015 y 10.9214N -74.2048W, Tvdf, 11/v/2015. Magdalena, Santa Marta, 11.20511N -74.1647W, Tdf, 1/vi/2012. Meta, Granada, 3.4961N -73.9405W, Tmf, 17/vii/2014 y 3.4757N -73.7282W, Tmf, 25/iii/2015. Meta, Lejanías, 3.4803N -73.9551W, Tmf, 19/ii/2015; 3.4922N -73.9421W, Tmf, 19/ii/2015; 3.5041N -73.9926W, Tmf, 19/ii/2015 y 3.4821N -73.9594W, Tmf, 19/ii/2015. Meta, Villavicencio, 4.0607N -73.4617W, Tmf, 18/vii/2014 y 4.0654N -73.4453W, Tmf, 20/viii/2015. Nariño, Pasto, 1.19872N -77.3034W, LMmf, 3/viii/2015. Nariño, Sandoná, 1.3134N -77.4460W, LMmf, 5/viii/2015; 1.2786N -77.4855W, LMmf, 5/viii/2015; 1.3102N -77.4471W, LMmf, 5/viii/2015 y 1.2784N -77.4848W, LMmf, 5/viii/2015. Quindío, Armenia, 4.5635N -75.6497W, PMmf, 8/iv/2014. Quindío, La Tebaida, 4.4038N -75.8041W, PMmf, 15/iv/2015 y 4.26062N -75.4749W, PMmf, 30/iii/2015. Quindío, Montenegro, 4.5621N -75.82124W, PMmf, 15/ix/2014 y 4.3349N -75.4629W, PMmf, 20/iii/2015. Quindío, Pijao, 4.3322N -75.7675W, PMmf, 15/ix/2014. Quindío, Quimbaya, 4.5738N -75.6572W, PMmf, 10/iv/2014; 4.3907N -75.4649W, PMmf, 24/iii/2015; 4.3917N -75.4683W, PMmf, 24/iii/2015. Santander, Barrancabermeja, 7.0216N -73.8105W, Tmf, 2/iii/2014; 7.0874N -73.8382W, Tmf, 2/iii/2014; 7.0592N -73.8612W, Tmf, 2/iv/2014 y 7.0662N -73.7448W, Tmf, 25/iv/2014. Santander, El Carmen de Chucurí, 6.7261N -73.5531W, PMmf, 20/v/2014. Santander, Girón, 6.9875N -73.1683W, Tdf, 15/iii/2015 y 6.9781N -73.1775W, Tdf, 15/iii/2015. Santander, Lebrija, 7.1226N -73.3414W, Tdf, 1/iii/2015; 7.0849N -73.0849W, Tdf, 14/v/2013 y 7.1475N -73.2066W, Tdf, 14/v/2013. Tolima, Armero, 4.9269N -74.8851W, Tdf, 22/iv/2015. Tolima, Coello, 4.3038N -74.9294W, Tdf, 7/v/2012; 4.351N -74.9022W, Tdf, 7/v/2012 y 4.2794N -75.0031W, Tdf, 8/v/2012. Tolima, Fresno, 5.1797N -74.9807W, PMvmf, 23/iv/2015. Tolima, Guamo, 3.9925N -74.9031W, Tdf, 9/v/2012. Valle del Cauca, Palmira, 3.51559N -76.3124W, Tdf, 15/ix/2015. Vichada, Puerto Carreño, 6.2101N -67.7114W, Tdf, 26/vi/2015.

***Frankliniella peruviana* Hood**

COLOMBIA: 29♀ 7♂, Antioquia, Medellín, 6.2701N -75.5629W, PMmf, 6/i/2016. Caldas, Manizales, 4.9095N -75.6238W, LMmf, 1/vii/2016. Cundinamarca, Tocaima, 4.3762N -74.5701W, PMmf, 4/x/2018. Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.4093N -74.4885W, PMmf, 12/vi/2015. Guaviare, San José, 2.5335N -72.5926W, Tmf, 19/ii/2015. Huila, Pitalito, 1.9045N -76.0246W, PMmf, 22/x/2015. Meta, Puerto Gaitán, 4.5735N -71.3373W, Tmf, 26/viii/2015. Quindío, Córdoba, 4.3942N -75.6843W, PMmf, 15/ix/2014. Santander, Barrancabermeja, 7.0716N -73.7494W, Tmf, 12/iv/2014 y 7.0216N -73.8105W, Tmf, 2/iii/2014.

***Frankliniella pulchella* Hood**

COLOMBIA: 0♀ 1♂, Cundinamarca, La Mesa, 4.6358N -74.5115W, PMmf, 8/v/2014.

***Frankliniella regentis* Berzosa**

COLOMBIA: 3♀ 2♂, Cundinamarca, Chipaque, 4.4441N -74.0582W, LMmf, 29/xi/2014. Cundinamarca, Guachetá, 5.3738N -73.6589W, SAp, 10/xii/2018. Cundinamarca, Sibaté, 4.3771N -74.2491W, SAp, 17/i/2015.

***Frankliniella rostrata* Priesner**

COLOMBIA: 51♀ 24♂, Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.8005N -75.1255W, Tdf, 8/vii/2014. Cesar, Pueblo Bello, 10.3869N -73.6482W, PMmf, 2/x/2015. Cesar, Valledupar, 10.6061N -73.2301W, Tdf, 29/ix/2015. Córdoba, Ciénaga de oro, 8.9121N -75.5834W, Tdf, 27/x/2015. Córdoba, Lórica, 9.1921N -75.8162W, Tdf, 27/x/2015 y 9.3067N -75.8902W, Tdf, 27/x/2015. Córdoba, San Bernardo del viento, 9.3441N -76.0366W, Tdf, 10/i/2016. Cundinamarca, Choachí, 4.4794N -73.9186W, PMmf, 18/ix/2016. Huila, Villavieja, 3.3136N -75.233W, Tdf, 7/v/2015. Quindío, Quimbaya, 4.5738N -75.6572W, PMmf, 10/iv/2014. Tolima, Fresno, 5.1797N -74.9807W, PMvmf, 23/iv/2015. Tolima, San Luis, 4.1283N -75.0922W, Tdf, 7/iv/2016.

***Frankliniella schultzei* (Trybom)**

COLOMBIA: 157♀ 26♂, Atlántico, Malambo, 10.8488N -74.8319W, Tvdf, 13/iii/2015. Bolívar, Córdoba, 9.5675N -74.8254W, Tvdf, 8/x/2015 y 9.5822N -74.8271W, Tvdf, 8/x/2015. Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.7488N -75.2422W, Tdf, 11/vii/2014; 9.6997N -75.3151W, Tdf, 6/x/2015; 9.7274N -75.1631W, Tdf, 8/x/2015 y 9.8005N -75.1255W, Tdf, 8/vii/2014. Bolívar, San Jacinto, 9.8297N -75.1352W, Tdf, 7/x/2015 y 9.7915N -75.2296W, Tdf, 7/v/2014. Cesar, Agustín Codazzi, 10.0012N -73.2456W, Tdf, 21/v/2015. Cesar, Becerril, 9.6901N -73.2596W, Tdf, 30/ix/2015. Cesar, Bosconia-

Copey, 10.0525N -73.8687W, Tdf, 20/v/2015. Cesar, Chimichagua, 9.3538N -73.8851W, Tdf, 21/v/2015. Cesar, Manaure, 10.3901N -73.0093W, PMdf, 19/v/2015. Cesar, Pueblo bello, 10.433076N -73.5765W, PMmf, 21/i/2016. Cesar, Valledupar, 10.4291N -73.3725W, Tdf, 29/ix/2015. Córdoba, San Pelayo, 8.9409N -75.8286W, Tdf, 27/x/2015. Cundinamarca, Ricaurte, 4.2849N -74.7394W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 4.2751N -74.7338W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014 y 4.2954N -74.7399W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014. Cundinamarca, Tocaima, 4.3991N -74.7341W, Tdf, 7/iii/2014. Guajira, Cuestecita, 11.1894N -72.7418W, Tdf, 20/i/2016. Guajira, Distracción, 11.0209N -72.9492W, Tdf, 29/vii/2014. Guajira, Manaure, 10.41101N -73.0306W, Tdf, 18/iii/2014. Magdalena, Ciénaga, 10.8808N -74.1833W, Tvdf, 11/v/2015 y 10.9586N -74.2471W, Tvdf, 11/v/2015. Magdalena, Santa Marta (PNN Tairona), 11.3115N -73.9344W, Tmf, 16/v/2015. Sucre, Los palmitos, 9.4523N -75.22570, Tdf, 9/vii/2014. Tolima, Armero, 4.6778N -74.9052W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014 y 4.6806N -74.9086W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014. Tolima, Espinal, 4.1939N -74.9661W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 4.1271N -74.8416W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014 y 4.1892N -74.9553W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014. Vichada, Puerto Carreño, 6.1968N -67.4649W, Tdf, 29/i/2015; 6.1976N -67.4652W, Tdf, 29/i/2015 y 6.3026N -67.8299W, Tdf, 4/xii/2014.

***Frankliniella senckenbergiana* Berzosa & Maroto**

COLOMBIA: 1♀, Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.4441N -74.0582W, PMmfM, 29/xi/2014.

***Frankliniella serrata* Moulton**

COLOMBIA: 2♀, Cundinamarca, vía Bogotá - Choachí, 4.561808N -74.007859W, Mmf, 5/ii/2017.

***Frankliniella simplex* Priesner**

COLOMBIA: 12♀ 16♂, Antioquia, Fredonia, 5.8165N -75.6827W, PMvmf, 6/v/2015. Caldas, Marquetalia, 5.3107N -75.0841W, PMvmf, 22/v/2014. Caldas, Pácora, 5.5221N -75.4625W, PMvmf, 17/ii/2015. Cundinamarca, Bogotá, 4.6364N -74.0884W, LMdf, 26/i/2015. Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 4.6849N -74.2041W, LMdf, 6/v/2014. Risaralda, Belén de Umbría, 5.1262N -75.9865W, PMmf, 19/ix/2015.

***Frankliniella sueoa* Mound & Marullo**

COLOMBIA: 7♀, Cundinamarca, Tocaima-Viota, 4.3762N -74.5701W.

***Frankliniella trisetosa* Hood**

COLOMBIA: 12♀, Cundinamarca, Guasca, 4.844N -73.8855W, LMdf, 7/iv/2016, 9/v/2016, 1/viii/2016, 19/ix/2016, 25/iv/2016, 26/ix/2016, 3/x/2016, 31/xi/2016.

***Frankliniella tritici* (Fitch)**

COLOMBIA: 2♀ 0♂. Cesar, Manaure, 10.3901N -73.0093W, PMdf, 19/v/2015. Huila, Pital, 2.3376N -75.8506W, Tdf, 23/x/2015.

***Frankliniella tuberosi* Moulton**

COLOMBIA: 5♀, Nariño, Pasto, 1.1987N -77.3034W, LMmf, 1/viii/2015.

***Frankliniella vargasi* Retana & Mound**

COLOMBIA: 24♀, Arauca, Tame, 6.5828N -71.5006W, Tmf, 11/i/2014. Cundinamarca, Chipaque, 4.4441N -74.0582W, LMmf, 29/xi/2014. Cundinamarca, La Mesa, 4.6518N -74.5549W, PMmf, 8/v/2014. Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.4093N -74.4885W, PMmf, 12/vi/2015 y 4.4338N -74.4733W, PMmf, 9/v/2014. Nariño, Sandoná, 1.3102N -77.4471W, LMmf, 5/viii/2015.

***Frankliniella varipes* Moulton**

COLOMBIA: 25♀ 21♂, Cundinamarca, Bogotá, 4.6364N -74.0884W, LMdf, 26/i/2015. Cundinamarca, Chipaque, 4.4441N -74.0582W, LMmf, 29/xi/2014.

***Frankliniella williamsi* Hood**

COLOMBIA: 35♀ 3♂. Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.7267N -75.1661, Tdf, 10/vii/2014; 9.7378N -75.2052W, Tdf, 10/vii/2014; 9.7488N -75.2422W, Tdf, 11/vii/2014 y 9.8005N -75.1255W, Tdf, 8/vii/2014. Boyacá, Tunja, 5.4836N -73.4677W, LMdf, 11/ii/2015. Cesar, Manaure, 10.3724N -73.0071W, PMdf, 19/v/2015. Córdoba, Ciénaga de oro, 8.9399N -75.56412W, Tdf, 27/x/2015. Cundinamarca, Nemocón, 5.1181N -73.8588W, LMdf, 14/xii/2015, 2/xi/2015, 28/xii/2015, 30/xii/2015, 11/i/2016, 22/ii/2016. Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.4289N -74.4827W, PMmf, 11/vi/2015. Guaviare, San José, 2.5868N -72.6259W, Tmf, 17/ii/2015. Huila, La Plata, 2.3526N -75.8858W, PMmf, 25/ii/2015. Magdalena, Ciénaga, 10.7671N -74.0234W, Tvdf, 15/v/2015. Magdalena, Zona Bananera, 10.7658N -74.1474W, Tdf, 6/xi/2013. Tolima, Espinal, 4.1939N -74.9661W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014.

***Frankliniella xanthomelaena* Hood**

COLOMBIA: 60♀ 18♂, Cundinamarca, Pacho, 5.1369N -74.1615W, LMmf, 29/i/2015. Cundinamarca, Sopó, 4.9171N -73.9655W, LMdf, 26/xii/2014. Nariño, Pasto, 1.1987N -77.3034W, LMmf, 3/viii/2015. Risaralda, Belén de Umbría, 5.1262N -75.9865W, PMmf, 19/ix/2015. Santander, Barrancabermeja,

6.9623N -73.7361W, Tmf, 14/iv/2014. Santander, Lebrija, 7.1238N -73.3395W, Tdf, 1/iii/2015. Valle del Cauca, Sevilla, 4.2498N -75.9277W, PMmf, 17/ix/2015.

***Frankliniella zeteki* Hood**

COLOMBIA: 61♀ 8♂, Antioquia, Fredonia, 5.8544N -75.7208W, PMvmf, 6/v/2015. Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.6997N -75.3151W, Tdf, 6/x/2015. Bolívar, Mompo, 9.2296N -74.5033W, Tdf, 10/ix/2015. Cesar, Astrea, 9.4713N -73.8802W, Tdf, 21/v/2015. Cesar, Bosconia, 9.8541N -73.8415W, Tdf, 20/v/2015. Cesar, Chimichagua, 9.2502N -73.8083W, Tdf, 21/v/2015. Cesar, San Diego, 10.2719N -73.2177W, Tdf, 21/v/2015. Córdoba, Ciénaga de oro, 8.8746N -75.6942W, Tdf, 27/x/2015 y 8.9399N -75.5641W, Tdf, 27/x/2015. Córdoba, Lorica, 9.3067N -75.8902W, Tdf, 27/x/2015. Cundinamarca, La Mesa, 4.6358N -74.5115W, PMmf, 8/v/2014. Guaviare, San José, 2.5335N -72.5926W, Tmf, 19/ii/2015; 2.4907N -72.6871W, Tmf, 20/ii/2015; 2.4903N -72.6387W, Tmf, 21/ii/2015 y 2.5994N -72.7599W, Tmf, 22/ii/2015. Huila, Garzón, 2.3349N -75.5173W, Tdf, 21/x/2015. Huila, La Plata, 2.4201N -75.8565W, PMmf, 17/vii/2015 y 2.4599N -75.7593W, PMmf, 17/vii/2015. Magdalena, Ciénaga, 10.9586N -74.2471W, Tvdf, 11/v/2015 y 10.8808N -74.1833W, Tvdf, 11/v/2015. Magdalena, Zona Bananera, 10.7654N -74.1475W, Tdf, 11/v/2015. Santander, Barrancabermeja, 7.0676N -73.7458W, Tmf, 12/iv/2014 y 7.0874N -73.8382W, Tmf, 2/iii/2014. Tolima, Armero, 4.92697N -74.8851W, Tdf, 22/iv/2015 y 5.0143N -74.901W, Tdf, 24/iv/2015. Tolima, Espinal, 4.1939N -74.9661W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014. Tolima, Fresno, 5.1514N -75.0202W, PMvmf, 21/vi/2014. Tolima, Mariquita, 5.1534N -74.9084W, Tmf, 20/vi/2014. Valle del Cauca, Palmira, 3.5155N -76.3124W, Tdf, 15/ix/2015. Valle del Cauca, Sevilla, 4.2582N -75.9129W, PMmf, 16/ix/2015 y 4.2546N -75.9301W, PMmf, 17/ix/2015.

***Microcephalothrips abdominalis* (Crawford DL)**

COLOMBIA: 79♀ 4♂, Arauca, Tame, 6.5828N -71.5006W, Tmf; 11/i/2014. Cesar, Chimichagua, 9.2502N -73.8083W, Tdf; 21/v/2015. Huila, Villavieja, 3.1961N -75.2293W, Tdf; 26/ix/2014. Quindío, Córdoba, 4.4358N -75.67169W, PMmf; 9/iv/2014. Santander, Barrancabermeja, 7.0703N -73.8551W, Tmf; 11/iv/2014; 7.0672N -73.7496W, Tmf; 12/iv/2014 y 7.0672N -73.7456W, Tmf; 12/iv/2014. Tolima, Armero, 4.9152N -74.8748W, Tdf; 26/ix/2014 y 4.9849N -74.9022W, Tdf; 22/vi/2014.

***Nexothrips perseae* Marullo & Mound**

COLOMBIA: 9♀, Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.4351N -74.4678W, PMmf; 16/viii/2013. Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.4348N -74.4724W, PMmf; 4/x/2017. Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.4351N -74.4678W, PMmf; 18/iv/2013.

***Oxythrips* sp**

COLOMBIA: 7♀ 6♂, Magdalena, Ciénaga, 10.9586N -74.2471W, Tvdf; 11/v/2015. Cesar, Valledupar, 10.4291N -73.3725W, Tdf; 29/ix/2015.

***Psectrothrips delostomae* Hood**

COLOMBIA: 16♀ 2♂, Cundinamarca, Bogotá, 4.6355N -74.0867W, LMdf; 16/vii/2014. Cundinamarca, Bogotá, 4.6356N -74.0878W, LMdf; 1/xii/2016.

***Psectrothrips palmerae* Mound & Marullo**

COLOMBIA: 0♀ 1♂, Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.4338N -74.4733W, PMmf; 9/v/2014.

***Rhamphothrips pandens* Sakimura**

COLOMBIA: 4♀, Cesar, Pueblo bello, 10.4201N -73.58217W, PMmf; 21/i/2016. Santander, Barrancabermeja, 7.0702N -73.7474W, Tmf; 12/iv/2014.

***Salpingothrips minimus* Hood**

COLOMBIA: 2♀, Huila, Villavieja, 3.3757N -75.1627W, Tdf; 26/ix/2014. Tolima, Natagaima, 3.6771N -75.1027W, Tdf; 26/ix/2014.

***Scirtidothrips torquatus* Hood**

COLOMBIA: 1♀, Cesar, Chiriguana, 9.360461N -73.576781W, Tdf; 11/xii/2015.

***Scirtothrips bisbravae* Johansen**

COLOMBIA: 1♀, Meta, Villavicencio, 4.0629N -73.4482W, Tmf; 20/viii/2015.

***Scirtothrips dorsalis* Hood**

COLOMBIA: 1150♀ 31♂, Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.7341N -75.2206W, Tdf; 8/x/2015. Bolívar, San Jacinto, 9.829723N -75.135257W, Tdf; 7/x/2015. Cesar, Bosconia- Copey, 10.052581N -73.868754W, Tdf; 20/v/2015. Córdoba, Montería, 8.74107N -75.803493W, Tdf; 15/i/2016; 8.782757N -75.854089W, Tdf; 15/i/2016 y 8.772095N -75.8844W, Tdf; 15/i/2016. Cundinamarca, Ricaurte, 4.303555N -74.744361W, Tdf; 29/ix/2014; 4.289416N -74.734027W, Tdf; 29/ix/2014; 4.297472N -74.741833W, Tdf; 29/ix/2014; 4.286027N -74.743527W, Tdf; 29/ix/2014; 4.292111N -74.736777W, Tdf; 29/ix/2014; 4.292472N -74.73575W, Tdf; 29/ix/2014; 4.283972N -74.740888W, Tdf; 29/ix/2014;

4.284972N -74.742194W, Tdf; 29/ix/2014; 4.30775N -74.748W, Tdf; 29/ix/2014 y 4.280833N -74.734194W, Tdf; 29/ix/2014. Huila, Campoalegre, 2.692081N -75.361881W, Tdf; 28/ix/2014; 2.699861N -75.355222W, Tdf; 28/ix/2014; 2.703527N -75.356444W, Tdf; 28/ix/2014; 2.688138N -75.360944W, Tdf; 28/ix/2014; 2.710888N -75.335852W, Tdf; 28/ix/2014; 2.705138N -75.350861W, Tdf; 28/ix/2014; 2.684722N -75.366777W, Tdf; 28/ix/2014; 2.692388N -75.360083W, Tdf; 28/ix/2014; 2.722305N -75.317083W, Tdf; 28/ix/2014 y 2.699277N -75.352138W, Tdf; 28/ix/2014. Huila, Pital, 2.188158N -75.817843W, Tdf; 22/x/2015. Huila, Villavieja, 3.20475N -75.237777W, Tdf; 28/ix/2014; 3.355888N -75.230416W, Tdf; 28/ix/2014; 3.375444N -75.171694W, Tdf; 28/ix/2014; 3.215012N -75.234222W, Tdf; 28/ix/2014; 3.213638N -75.227888W, Tdf; 28/ix/2014; 3.218777N -75.230012W, Tdf; 28/ix/2014; 3.354444N -75.198861W, Tdf; 28/ix/2014; 3.38175N -75.171194W, Tdf; 28/ix/2014; 3.1961N -75.2293W, Tdf; 26/ix/2014 y 3.216388N -75.230983W, Tdf; 28/ix/2014. Magdalena, Zona Bananera, 10.76546N -74.14754W, Tdf; 11/v/2015. Sucre, Sampués, 9.126202N -75.258591W, Tdf; 10/xi/2015. Tolima, Armero, 5.0142N -74.9051W, Tdf; 24/ix/2014; 5.111444N -74.894055W, Tdf; 24/ix/2014 y 4.6806N -74.9086W, Tdf; 26/ix/2014. Tolima, Espinal, 4.152194N -74.854444W, Tdf; 26/ix/2014; 4.134305N -74.847083W, Tdf; 26/ix/2014; 4.156916N -74.948638W, Tdf; 26/ix/2014; 4.177138N -74.926472W, Tdf; 26/ix/2014 y 4.1271N -74.8416W, Tdf; 26/ix/2014. Tolima, Natagaima, 3.497555N -75.138638W, Tdf; 27/ix/2014; 3.50275N -75.141166W, Tdf; 27/ix/2014; 3.676527N -75.101608W, Tdf; 27/ix/2014; 3.505916N -75.135222W, Tdf; 27/ix/2014; 3.674333N -75.106722W, Tdf; 27/ix/2014; 3.684194N -75.104527W, Tdf; 27/ix/2014; 3.484527N -75.139111W, Tdf; 27/ix/2014 y 3.490305N -75.131861W, Tdf; 27/ix/2014. Vichada, Puerto Carreño, 6.19682N -67.4649W, Tdf; 29/i/2015; 6.1969N -67.46453W, Tdf; 29/i/2015; 6.25124N -67.53229W, Tdf; 7/ii/2015; 6.25074N -67.53278W, Tdf; 7/ii/2015; 6.25148N -67.53225W, Tdf; 19/ii/2015; 6.19769N -67.46581W, Tdf; 29/i/2015; 6.25049N -67.53239W, Tdf; 7/ii/2015; 6.19704N -67.46591W, Tdf; 29/i/2015; 6.19735N -67.46611W, Tdf; 29/i/2015; 6.19768N -67.46557W, Tdf; 29/i/2015.

***Scirtothrips hansonii* Mound & Hoddle**

COLOMBIA: 66♀ 17♂, Antioquia, La Ceja, 6.0324N -75.3804W, LMvmf; 12/ii/2014. Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.4348N -74.4724W, PMmf; //2017. Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.4351N -74.4678W, PMmf; 16/viii/2013. Santander, El Carmen de Chucurí, 6.6337N -73.5878W, PMmf; 20/v/2014. Tolima, Fresno, 5.2349N -75.0173W, PMvmf; 1/vii/2016. Tolima, Fresno, 5.1514N -75.0202W, PMvmf; 21/vi/2014. Tolima, Fresno, 5.2349N -75.0173W, PMvmf; 1/vii/2016. Valle del Cauca, Sevilla, 4.2582N -75.9129W, PMmf; 16/ix/2015.

***Scirtothrips ikelus* Mound & Marullo**

COLOMBIA: 1♀, Santander, Barrancabermeja, 7.0662N -73.7454W, Tmf; 25/iv/2014.

***Scirtothrips lumarius* Mound & Marullo**

COLOMBIA: 1♀ 1♂, Bolívar, Mompox, 9.1519N -74.2838W, Tdf; 9/ix/2015. Meta, Villavicencio, 4.0654N -73.4453W, Tmf; 20/viii/2015.

***Scirtothrips manihoti* (Bondar)**

COLOMBIA: 445♀ 59♂, Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.748881N -75.242212W, Tdf; 11/vii/2014. Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.748888N -75.242205W, Tdf; 11/vii/2014. Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.800556N -75.12552W, Tdf; 8/vii/2014. Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.741646N -75.262765W, Tdf; 6/x/2015. Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.73075N -75.2095W, Tdf; 8/x/2015. Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.727217N -75.163394W, Tdf; 7/x/2015. Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.800556N -75.12552W, Tdf; 8/vii/2014. Bolívar, San Jacinto, 9.829723N -75.135257W, Tdf; 7/x/2015. Cesar, Pueblo bello, 10.420034N -73.58217W, PMmf; 21/i/2016. Cesar, Pueblo Bello, 10.414197N -73.619566W, PMmf; 1/x/2015. Cesar, Valledupar, 10.429172N -73.372502W, Tdf; 29/ix/2015. Córdoba, Ciénaga de oro, 8.87464N -75.69423W, Tdf; 27/x/2015. Córdoba, Ciénaga de oro, 8.91216N -75.58347W, Tdf; 27/x/2015. Córdoba, San Bernardo del viento, 9.344123N -76.036682W, Tdf; 10/i/2016. Córdoba, San Pelayo, 8.95104N -75.85246W, Tdf; 27/x/2015. Córdoba, San Pelayo, 8.94091N -75.82869W, Tdf; 27/x/2015. Cundinamarca, La Mesa, 4.603492N -74.536718W, PMmf; 24/vi/2015. Guaviare, San José, 2.202071N -72.480836W, Tmf; 18/ii/2015. Guaviare, San José, 2.58681N -72.625979W, Tmf; 17/ii/2015. Huila, Garzón, 2.334901N -75.517346W, Tdf; 21/x/2015. Huila, Villavieja, 3.313626N -75.23387W, Tdf; 7/v/2015. Magdalena, Ciénaga, 10.765839N -74.025427W, Tvdf; 14/v/2015. Magdalena, Ciénaga, 10.585559N -74.248604W, Tvdf; 15/v/2015. Meta, Puerto Gaitán, 4.571356N -71.332493W, Tmf; 27/viii/2015. Meta, Villavicencio, 4.065498N -73.445364W, Tmf; 20/viii/2015. Meta, Villavicencio, 4.062918N -73.448213W, Tmf; 20/viii/2015. Santander, Barrancabermeja, 6.96254N -73.736469W, Tmf; 14/iv/2014. Santander, Barrancabermeja, 6.967705N -73.744733W, Tmf; 14/iv/2014. Sucre, Colosó, 9.462115N -75.383417W, Tdf; 12/xi/2015. Sucre, Sampaús, 9.177651N -75.290154W, Tdf; 10/xi/2015. Tolima, Fresno, 5.179715N -74.980742W, PMvmf; 23/iv/2015.

***Scirtothrips multistriatus* Hood**

COLOMBIA: 66♀ 7♂, Guaviare, El retorno, 2.2021N -72.4809W, Tmf; 12/xii/2014, 18/ii/2015. Guaviare, El retorno, 2.5335N -72.5926W, Tmf; 19/ii/2015. Meta, Granada, 3.4757N -73.7282W, Tmf; 25/iii/2015.

***Scirtothrips panamensis* Hood**

COLOMBIA: 265♀ 35♂, Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.7307N -75.2095W, Tdf; 8/x/2015. Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.7272N -75.1633W, Tdf; 7/x/2015. Bolívar, San Jacinto, 9.8297N -75.1352W, Tdf; 7/x/2015. Cesar, Pueblo Bello, 10.3869N -73.648263W, PMmf; 2/x/2015. Cesar, Pueblo bello, 10.4201N -73.5821W, PMmf; 21/i/2016. Cesar, Pueblo Bello, 10.4141N -73.6195W, PMmf; 1/x/2015. Guaviare, San José, 2.2021N -72.4808W, Tmf; 18/ii/2015. Guaviare, San José, 2.5868N -72.6259W, Tmf; 17/ii/2015. Guaviare, San José, 2.2021N -72.4808W, Tmf; 18/ii/2015. Huila, Garzón, 2.3349N -75.5173W, Tdf; 21/x/2015. Huila, Pitalito, 1.9045N -76.0246W, PMmf; 22/x/2015. Magdalena, Ciénaga, 10.7658N -74.0254W, Tvdf; 14/v/2015. Meta, Puerto Gaitán, 4.5713N -71.3324W, Tmf; 27/viii/2015. Meta, Villavicencio, 4.0761N -73.5847W, Tmf; 15/iv/2013. Meta, Villavicencio, 4.0629N -73.4482W, Tmf; 20/viii/2015. Meta, Villavicencio, 4.065498N -73.445364W, Tmf; 20/viii/2015. Nariño, Sandoná, 1.3134N -77.4461W, LMmf; 5/viii/2015. Nariño, Sandoná, 1.2786N -77.4855W, LMmf; 5/viii/2015. Quindío, Quimbaya, 4.5738N -75.6572W, PMmf; 10/iv/2014. Santander, Barrancabermeja, 6.9677N -73.7447W, Tmf; 14/iv/2014. Santander, Barrancabermeja, 7.0662N -73.7454W, Tmf; 25/iv/2014. Santander, Barrancabermeja, 6.9625N -73.7364W, Tmf; 14/iv/2014. Tolima, Fresno, 5.1797N -74.9807W, PMvmf; 23/iv/2015.

***Scirtothrips perseae* Nakahara**

COLOMBIA: 13♀, Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.7488N -75.2422W, Tdf; 11/vii/2014. Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.4351N -74.4678W, PMmf; 16/viii/2013. Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.4348N -74.4724W, PMmf; //2017. Risaralda, La Celia, 5.0078N -76.0089W, PMmf; 27/viii/2013. Tolima, Fresno, 5.2349N -75.0173W, PMvmf; 1/vii/2016. Tolima, Fresno, 5.2349N -75.0173W, PMvmf; 1/vii/2016.

***Scolothrips tenuipennis* zur Strassen**

COLOMBIA: 2♀, Cesar, Becerril, 9.6901N -73.2596W, Tdf; 30/ix/2015.

***Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall)**

COLOMBIA: 4♀ 1♂, Tolima, Saldaña, 3.9325N -75.0267W, Tdf; 8/ix/1998.

***Taeniothrips* sp**

COLOMBIA: 2♀, Cundinamarca, Anolaima, 4.7807N -74.4216W, LMmf; 20/iii/2019.

***Thrips australis* (Bagnall)**

COLOMBIA: 14♀ 3♂, Cundinamarca, Cogua, 5.0565N -73.9289W, LMdf; 1/ix/2015, 7/iv/2016, 17/iii/2016, 6/x/2016. Cundinamarca, Facatativá, 4.7779N -74.3234W, LMdf; 19/ix/2016, 17/x/2016. Cundinamarca, Guasca, 4.844N -73.8855W, LMdf; 25/vii/2016, 18/iv/2016, 29/ix/2016, 7/iv/2016. Cundinamarca, Tocancipá, 4.9887N -73.9043W, LMdf; 1/ix/2015. Cundinamarca, Tocancipá, 4.9887N -73.9043W, LMdf; 26/x/2015, 28/x/2015, 22/ii/2016.

***Thrips brevipilosus* Moulton**

COLOMBIA: 13♀ 5♂, Cundinamarca, Cogua, 5.0565N -73.929W, LMdf; 29/x/2015, 5/xi/2015, 14/iv/2016, 17/iii/2016, 25/ii/2016. Cundinamarca, Guasca, 4.844N -73.8855W, LMdf; 7/iv/2016, 18/iv/2016. Cundinamarca, Soacha, 4.6112N -74.3104W, LMdf; 29/vi/2014. Cundinamarca, Tocancipá, 4.9887N -73.9043W, LMdf; 1/ix/2015.

***Thrips florum* Schmutz**

COLOMBIA: 31♀ 7♂, Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 4.6857N -74.2191W, LMdf; 6/v/2014. Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 4.6948N -74.2017W, LMdf; 20/ii/2016. Cundinamarca, Soacha, 4.6112N -74.3104W, LMdf; 29/vi/2014.

***Thrips palmi* Karny**

COLOMBIA: 3939♀ 86♂, Antioquia, Medellín, 6.270198N -75.562951W, PMmf; 6/i/2016. Antioquia, Rionegro, 6.19032N -75.35494W, LMmf, 3/x/2014 y 6.19032N -75.35495W, LMmf, 3/x/2014. Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.748881N -75.242212W, Tdf, 11/vii/2014 y 9.800556N -75.12552W, Tdf, 8/vii/2014. Córdoba, Cereté, 8.852109N -75.818514W, Tdf; 2/ii/2016. Córdoba, Ciénaga de oro, 8.91216N -75.58347W, Tdf; 27/x/2015. Córdoba, Lórica, 9.19208N -75.8162W, Tdf; 27/x/2015. Córdoba, Montería, 8.74107N -75.803493W, Tdf, 15/i/2016; 8.782757N -75.854089W, Tdf, 15/i/2016; 8.74107N -75.803493W, Tdf, 15/i/2016 y 8.772095N -75.8844W, Tdf, 15/i/2016. Córdoba, San Pelayo, 8.95104N -75.85246W, Tdf; 27/x/2015. Cundinamarca, Choachí, 4.47941N -73.91868W, PMmf, 18/ix/2016 y 4.47678N -73.91819W, PMmf, 18/ix/2016. Cundinamarca, Ricaurte, 4.289416N -74.734027W, Tdf, 29/ix/2014; 4.292472N -74.73575W, Tdf, 29/ix/2014; 4.303555N -74.744361W, Tdf, 29/ix/2014 y 4.30775N -74.748W, Tdf, 29/ix/2014. Huila, Campoalegre, 2.684722N -75.366777W, Tdf, 28/ix/2014; 2.688138N -75.360944W, Tdf, 28/ix/2014; 2.692081N -75.361881W, Tdf, 28/ix/2014; 2.692388N -75.360083W, Tdf, 28/ix/2014; 2.699277N -75.352138W, Tdf, 28/ix/2014; 2.699861N -75.355222W, Tdf, 28/ix/2014; 2.703527N -75.356444W, Tdf, 28/ix/2014; 2.705138N -75.350861W, Tdf, 28/ix/2014; 2.710888N -75.335852W, Tdf, 28/ix/2014 y 2.722305N -75.317083W, Tdf, 28/ix/2014. Huila, Garzón, 2.336599N -75.512936W, Tdf; 21/x/2015. Huila, La Plata, 2.45992N -75.75938W, PMmf;

17/vii/2015. Huila, Pital, 2.254442N -75.800399W, Tdf, 22/x/2015 y 2.188158N -75.817843W, Tdf, 22/x/2015. Huila, Pitalito, 1.906868N -76.023548W, PMmf, 22/x/2015; 1.904372N -76.025182W, PMmf, 22/x/2015 y 1.904521N -76.024615W, PMmf, 22/x/2015. Huila, Villavieja, 3.20475N -75.237777W, Tdf, 28/ix/2014; 3.213638N -75.227888W, Tdf, 28/ix/2014; 3.215012N -75.234222W, Tdf, 28/ix/2014; 3.216388N -75.230983W, Tdf, 28/ix/2014; 3.218777N -75.230012W, Tdf, 28/ix/2014; 3.354444N -75.198861W, Tdf, 28/ix/2014; 3.355888N -75.230416W, Tdf, 28/ix/2014; 3.375444N -75.171694W, Tdf, 28/ix/2014; 3.380333N -75.170333W, Tdf, 28/ix/2014; 3.38175N -75.171194W, Tdf, 28/ix/2014 y 3.1961N -75.2293W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014. Magdalena, Ciénaga, 10.750274N -74.054876W, Tvdf, 15/v/2015; 10.768487N -74.025438W, Tvdf, 14/v/2015 y 10.76706N -74.02347; Tvdf, 15/v/2015. Magdalena, Santa Marta, 11.12281N -74.10966W, Tdf, 1/vi/2012 y 11.08438N -74.07381W, Tdf, 1/vi/2012. Magdalena, Zona Bananera, 10.765805N -74.14747W, Tdf, 6/xi/2013; 10.76433N -74.14688W, Tdf, 1/vi/2012 y 10.76580N -74.147475W, Tdf, 7/xi/2013. Meta, Lejanías, 3.746032N -73.69476W, Tmf; 19/vii/2014. Nariño, Sandoná, 1.298183N -77.413085W, LMmf; 5/viii/2015. Quindío, Circasia, 4.642803N -75.607795W, PMmf; 11/iv/2014. Quindío, Quimbaya, 4.583221N -75.701433W, PMmf, 11/iv/2014 y 4.607297N -75.794192W, PMmf, 10/iv/2014. Sucre, Sampués, 9.247379N -75.344878W, Tdf; 10/xi/2015. Tolima, Ambalema, 4.680611N -74.908611W, Tdf, 25/ix/2014 y 4.920638N -74.874888W, Tdf, 25/ix/2014. Tolima, Armero, 4.991416N -74.905361W, Tdf, 24/ix/2014; 5.010583N -74.909888W, Tdf, 24/ix/2014; 5.014277N -74.905111W, Tdf, 24/ix/2014 y 4.984905N -74.902224W, Tdf, 22/vi/2014. Tolima, Espinal, 4.134166N -74.847277W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 4.134305N -74.847083W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 4.139722N -74.866055W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 4.153361N -74.867694W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 4.156916N -74.948638W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 4.177138N -74.926472W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014; 4.189222N -74.955388W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014 y 4.201083N -74.976722W, Tdf, 26/ix/2014. Tolima, Natagaima, 3.472416N -75.136666W, Tdf, 27/ix/2014; 3.484527N -75.139111W, Tdf, 27/ix/2014; 3.485138N -75.141305W, Tdf, 27/ix/2014; 3.49030N -75.13186W, Tdf, 27/ix/2014; 3.497555N -75.138638W, Tdf, 27/ix/2014; 3.50275N -75.141166W, Tdf, 27/ix/2014; 3.505916N -75.135222W, Tdf, 27/ix/2014; 3.674333N -75.106722W, Tdf, 27/ix/2014 y 3.676527N -75.101608W, Tdf, 27/ix/2014. Tolima, Venadillo, 4.68525N -74.911194W, Tdf; 25/ix/2014 y 6.19766N -67.46526W, Tdf; 29/i/2015.

Thrips simplex (Morison)

COLOMBIA: 2♀, Cundinamarca, Cogua, 5.0565N -73.929W, LMdf; 11/ii/2016.

Thrips tabaci Lindeman

COLOMBIA: 216♀, Antioquia, Rionegro, 6.1903N -75.3549W, LMmf; 3/x/2014. Boyacá, Nobsa, 5.8052N -73.0055W, LMdf; 18/iii/2016. Boyacá, Paipa, 5.7915N -73.0831W, LMdf; 18/iii/2016. Boyacá,

Tibasosa, 5.7705N -72.9941W, LMdf; 18/iii/2016. Boyacá, Tunja, 5.4794N -73.4544W, LMdf; 11/ii/2015. Cundinamarca, Bogotá, 4.6364N -74.0884W, LMdf; 26/i/2015. Cundinamarca, Cajicá, 4.6364N -74.0885W, LMdf; 28/i/2015. Cundinamarca, Cogua, 5.0565N -73.929W, LMdf; 18/ii/2016. Cundinamarca, Cogua, 5.0565N -73.929W, LMdf; 21/iv/2016. Cundinamarca, Cogua, 5.0565N -73.929W, LMdf; 7/i/2016. Cundinamarca, Cogua, 5.0565N -73.929W, LMdf; 10/iii/2016. Cundinamarca, Cogua, 5.0565N -73.929W, LMdf; 17/iii/2016. Cundinamarca, Facatativá, 4.7779N -74.3234W, LMdf; 10/x/2016. Cundinamarca, Facatativá, 4.7779N -74.3234W, LMdf; 12/ix/2016. Cundinamarca, Facatativá, 4.7779N -74.3234W, LMdf; 14/xi/2016. Cundinamarca, Facatativá, 4.7779N -74.3234W, LMdf; 28/xii/2016. Cundinamarca, Facatativá, 4.7779N -74.3234W, LMdf; 19/ix/2016. Cundinamarca, Facatativá, 4.7779N -74.3234W, LMdf; 3/x/2016. Cundinamarca, Guasca, 4.844N -73.8855W, LMdf; 7/iv/2016. Cundinamarca, Guasca, 4.844N -73.8855W, LMdf; 16/xi/2015. Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 4.6806N -74.2167W, LMdf; 3/vi/2016. Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 4.6849N -74.2040W, LMdf; 6/v/2014. Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 4.6912N -74.2024W, LMdf; 18/iv/2015. Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 4.6944N -74.2047W, LMdf; 29/v/2013. Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 4.6948N -74.2017W, LMdf; 20/ii/2016. Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 4.6839N -74.1992W, LMdf; 29/vii/2015. Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 4.6806N -74.2167W, LMdf; 6/vi/2014. Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 4.6909N -74.2027W, LMdf; 11/x/2016. Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 4.6912N -74.2024W, LMdf; 18/iv/2015. Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 4.6944N -74.2047W, LMdf; 29/v/2013. Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 4.6948N -74.2017W, LMdf; 20/ii/2016. Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 4.6806N -74.2167W, LMdf; 13/vi/2014. Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 4.6806N -74.2167W, LMdf; 10/vi/2014. Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 4.6948N -74.2017W, LMdf; 20/ii/2016. Cundinamarca, Nemocón, 5.1181N -73.8588W, LMdf; 30/xii/2015. Cundinamarca, Sopó, 4.9171N -73.9655W, LMdf; 26/xii/2014. Cundinamarca, Subachoque, 5.0021N -74.1293W, LMdf; 23/viii/2014. Cundinamarca, Subachoque, 5.0021N -74.1293W, LMdf; 23/viii/2014. Huila, La Plata, 2.3255N -75.8421W, PMmf; 22/x/2015. Nariño, Consacá, 1.1941N -77.4675W, LMmf; 6/viii/2015. Nariño, Sandoná, 1.2786N -77.4855W, LMmf; 5/viii/2015. Santander, Guaca, 6.8683N -72.8274W, LMmf; 12/x/2016.

***Thrips trehernei* Priesner**

COLOMBIA: 3♀ 1♂, Cundinamarca, Mosquera, 4.6857N -74.2191W, LMdf; 6/v/2014. Cundinamarca, Soacha, 4.6112N -74.3104W, LMdf; 29/vi/2014.

PHLAEOTHRIPIDAE Uzel

PHLAEOTHRIPINAE Uzel

***Adraneothrips pulchellus* Hood**

COLOMBIA: 1♀, Santander, El Carmen de Chucuri, 6.6337N -73.5878W, PMmf; 20/v/2014.

***Haplothrips gowdeyi* (Franklin)**

COLOMBIA: 6♀, Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.7416N -75.2627W, Tdf; 6/x/2015. Bolívar, El Carmen de Bolívar, 9.7432N -75.2621W, Tdf; 6/x/2015. Córdoba, Ciénaga de oro, 8.9121N -75.5834W, Tdf; 27/x/2015. Magdalena, Zona Bananera, 10.7654N -74.1475W, Tdf; 11/v/2015.

***Holopothrips* sp**

COLOMBIA: 20♀, Cundinamarca, La Mesa, 4.6518N -74.5549W, PMmf; 8/v/2014. Santander, El Carmen de Chucurí, 6.6337N -73.5878W, PMmf; 20/v/2014. Tolima, Fresno, 5.1514N -75.0202W, PMvmf; 21/vi/2014. Tolima, Mariquita, 5.1825N -74.9543W, Tmf; 21/vi/2014. Cundinamarca, Viotá, 4.4338N -74.4733W, PMmf; 9/v/2014. Tolima, Fresno, 5.1514N -75.0202W, PMvmf; 21/vi/2014.

***Karnyothrips flavipes* (Jones)**

COLOMBIA: 1♀, Santander, Rionegro, 7.3704N -73.1774W, Tdf; 19/v/2014.

***Karnyothrips merrilli* (Watson)**

COLOMBIA: 2♀, Bolívar, San Jacinto, 9.8595N -75.2421W, Tdf; 24/xi/2015. Bolívar, San Jacinto, 9.8727N -75.1696W, Tdf; 24/xi/2015.

***Leptothrips* sp**

COLOMBIA: 2♀, Tolima, Fresno, 5.1514N -75.0202W, PMvmf; 21/vi/2014.

IDOLOTHRIPINAE Bagnall

***Elaphrothrips laevicollis* (Bagnall)**

COLOMBIA: 1♀ 2♂, Santander, El Carmen de Chucurí, 6.6337N -73.5878W, PMmf; 20/v/2014.

Classification of the life zones of Colombia, adapted from Holdridge (1967) and Gutiérrez (2002).

Ecosystem	Acronym	Average annual T° (°C)	Median annual Precipitation (mm)
Tropical thorn forest	Ttf	17 - 29	<700
Montane moist forest	Mmf	6 - 12	500 - 1000
Lower Montane moist forest	LMmf	> 12	1000 - 2000
PreMontane moist forest	PMmf	18 - 24	1100 - 1200
SubTropical moist forest	STmf	18 - 24	1000 y 2000
Tropical moist forest	Tmf	> 24	2000 y 4000
Montane very moist forest	Mvmf	6 - 12	2500 - 3000
Lower Montane very moist forest	LMvmf	12 - 18	2000 - 4000
PreMontane very moist forest	PMvmf	18 - 24	2000 y 4000
SubTropical very moist forest	STvmf	17 - 24	2000 a 4000
Tropical very moist forest	Tvmf	> 24	4000 - 8000
Tropical very dry forest	Tvdf	> 24	500 y 1000
Montane rain forest	Mrf	6 a 12	> 2000
Lower Montane rain forest	LMrf	12 a 18	> 4000
PreMontane rain forest	PMrf	18 - 24	4000 - 8000
Tropical rain forest	Trf	> 24	> 8000
Low Montane dry forest	LMdf	12 - 18	500 - 1000
PreMontane dry forest	PMdf	18 - 24	550 – 1100
SubTropical dry forest	STdf	< 24	500 - 1000
Tropical dry forest	Tdf	>24	700 - 2000
SubAlpine pluvial paramo	SApp	3 - 6	>1000
SubAndean paramo	SAP	3 - 6	500-1000

Thysanoptera for each geographic region and associated plants (C = Warm, T = Temperate, F = Cold; Cp = Cultivated plant, Wp = Wild Plant, W = Weed; F = Flower, H = Leaf, Fr = Fruit, St = Sticky trap; An = Andean, Ca = Caribbean, Or = Orinoquian), altitudinal range and thermal zone (new reports= **).

Species	Altitudinal range		Thermal zone			Botanical family	Associated Plant		System	Plant sampled structure				Geographical region			
	Min	Max	C	T	F					F	H	Fr	St	An	Ca	Or	Total
<i>Adraneothrips pulchellus</i> Hood, 1950**	1	500	X			Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp		X				1			1
<i>Ambaeothrips microstriatus</i> (Hood, 1935)	1001	1500		X		Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp		X				2			2
<i>Anaphothrips obscurus</i> (Muller, 1776)	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Sphagneticola trilobata</i>	Cp				X		6			6
<i>Anaphothrips sudanensis</i> Trybom, 1911.	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa</i> sp.	Cp				X		5			5
<i>Aptinothrips rufus</i> Haliday, 1836.	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa</i> sp.	Cp				X		4			4
<i>Arorathrips fulvus</i> (Moulton, 1936)	1	500	X			Chrysobalanaceae	<i>Chrysobalanus icaco</i>	Wp	X					2			2
	1	500	X			Poaceae	<i>Zea mays</i>	Cp	X						1		1
<i>Arorathrips mexicanus</i> (Crawford DL, 1909)	1	500	X			Poaceae	<i>Leptochloa scabra</i>	W	X					4			4
	1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Tridax procumbens</i>	W	X					1			1
	1	500	X			Poaceae	<i>Zea mays</i>	Cp	X					2			2
<i>Arorathrips xanthius</i> (Hood, 1934)	1	500	X			Cyperaceae	<i>Fimbristylis</i> sp.	W	X						5		5
	1	500	X			Poaceae	<i>Leptochloa scabra</i>	W	X					16			16
	1	500	X			Portulacaceae	<i>Talinum paniculatum</i>	W	X					1			1
<i>Aurantothrips orchidaceus</i> Bagnall, 1909.	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa</i> sp.	Cp				X		5			5
<i>Baileyothis limbatus</i> (Hood, 1935)	1	500	X			Rutaceae	<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	Cp		X				1			1
	1	500	X			Euphorbiaceae	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i>	W	X					16			16
	1	500	X			Euphorbiaceae	<i>Euphorbia hypericifolia</i>	W	X					5			5
	1	500	X			Euphorbiaceae	<i>Euphorbia postrata</i>	W	X					2			2
	1	500	X			Boraginaceae	<i>Heliotropium</i> sp.	W	X					2			2
	1	500	X			Verbenaceae	<i>Lantana camara</i> L. (1753)	W	X					1			1
	1	500	X			Poaceae	<i>Leptochloa scabra</i>	W	X					1			1
<i>Bolacothrips striatopennatus</i> (Schmutz, 1913)**	1	1000	X			Poaceae	<i>Oryza sativa</i>	Cp	X	X				7			7
<i>Bravothrips kraussi</i> (Crawford JC, 1948)**	1	500	X			Solanaceae	<i>Capsicum</i> sp.	Cp		X				2			2
	1501	2000		X		Solanaceae	<i>Solanum quitense</i>	Wp	X					1			1
<i>Bravothrips mexicanus</i> (Priesner, 1933)**	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Malus domestica</i>	Cp		X				1			1
<i>Caliothrips phaseoli</i> (Hood, 1912)**	1	500	X			Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora edulis</i> f. <i>flavicarpa</i>	Cp		X				11			11

Species	Altitudinal range		Thermal zone			Botanical family	Associated Plant	System	Plant sampled structure				Geographical region				
	Min	Max	C	T	F				F	H	Fr	St	An	Ca	Or	Total	
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>No determinada</i>	Wp	X					1			1
<i>Ceratothripoides brunneus</i> Bagnall, 1918	1001	1500				Rubiaceae	<i>Coffea arabica</i>	Cp	X					1	1		2
	1	500	X			Cucurbitaceae	<i>Cucurbita maxima</i>	Cp	X							3	3
	1	500	X			Convolvulaceae	<i>Ipomoea pes-caprae</i>	Cp	X							22	22
	1	500	X			Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X	X				1		1	2
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>No determinada</i>	Wp	X							1	1
<i>Ceratothripoides claratris</i> (Shumsher, 1946)**	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Crotalaria</i> sp.	Wp	X					1			1
<i>Chaetanaphothrips orchidii</i> (Moulton, 1907)	1	500	X			Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp		X					1		1
<i>Charassothrips</i> sp.	1001	1500		X		Asteraceae	<i>Emilia sonchifolia</i>	W	X						2		2
<i>Corynothrips stenopterus</i> Williams, 1913	1	1500	X	X		Euphorbiaceae	<i>Manihot esculenta</i>	Cp	X	X				6	16	79	101
	501	1000	X			Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora edulis</i> f. <i>flavicarpa</i>	Cp		X				1			1
<i>Elaphrothrips laevicollis</i> (Bagnall, 1910)**	1	500	X			Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp		X				3			3
<i>Erythrothrips diabolus</i> Priesner, 1932	1501	2000		X		Fabaceae	<i>Inga edulis</i>	Wp	X					2			2
<i>Erythrothrips stygicus</i> Hood, 1938**	2501	3000			X	Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora ligularis</i>	Cp				X		1			1
<i>Frankliniella aliaepennae</i> Berzosa, 2006	3001	3500		X		Asteraceae	<i>Espeletia grandiflora</i>	Wp	X					7			7
<i>Frankliniella aureominuta</i> Johansen, 1981**	2501	3000		X		Brassicaceae	<i>Raphanus raphanistrum</i>	W	X					1			1
<i>Frankliniella auripes</i> Hood, 1915	1501	2000		X		Fabaceae	<i>Inga edulis</i>	Wp	X					9			9
	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa</i> sp.	Cp				X		35			35
	2501	3000			X	Fabaceae	<i>Senna</i> sp.	Wp	X					6			6
	2501	3000			X	Solanaceae	<i>Streptosolen jamesonii</i>	Wp	X					16			16
	2501	3000			X	Fabaceae	<i>Vicia faba</i>	Cp	X	X				37			37
<i>Frankliniella bicolor</i> Moulton, 1948	1001	1500		X		Cannabaceae	<i>Cannabis</i> sp.	Cp	X					1			1
	1001	2000			X	Rubiaceae	<i>Coffea arabica</i>	Cp	X					11			11
	1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Emilia sonchifolia</i>	W	X						1		1
	1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Lagascea mollis</i>	W	X					1			1
	1001	1500		X		Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X					2			2
	501	1000	X			Fabaceae	<i>Senna</i> sp.	Wp	X					2			2
	1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Sphagnetocola trilobata</i>	Wp	X					1			1
	2501	3000			X	Solanaceae	<i>Streptosolen jamesonii</i>	Wp	X					1			1
	1001	1500		X		Fabaceae	<i>Tachigali guianensis</i>	Cp	X					1			1
<i>Frankliniella borinquen</i> Hood, 1942	1	500	X			Bixaceae	<i>Bixa orellana</i>	Wp		X				1			1
	501	1000	X			Fabaceae	<i>Caesalpinia pulcherrima</i>	Wp	X					1	1		2

Species	Altitudinal range		Thermal zone			Botanical family	Associated Plant		System	Plant sampled structure				Geographical region			
	Min	Max	C	T	F					F	H	Fr	St	An	Ca	Or	Total
	501	1000	X			Solanaceae	<i>Capsicum annuum</i>	Cp	X				1			1	
	1	500	X			Solanaceae	<i>Capsicum</i> sp.	Cp	X				19			19	
	1	500	X			Rutaceae	<i>Citrus reticulata</i>	Cp	X						1	1	
	1	1500	X	X		Rutaceae	<i>Citrus</i> sp.	Cp	X			15	4			19	
	501	1500	X	X		Rubiaceae	<i>Coffea arabica</i>	Cp	X			6	1			7	
	1	500	X			Boraginaceae	<i>Cordia dentata</i>	Wp	X				3			3	
	1	1000	X			Cucurbitaceae	<i>Cucurbita maxima</i>	Cp	X				4			4	
	1	500	X			Euphorbiaceae	<i>Delechia scandens</i>	W	X			1				1	
	1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Emilia sonchifolia</i>	W	X					1		1	
	501	1000	X	X		Euphorbiaceae	<i>Euphorbia heterophylla</i>	Wp	X				1			1	
	1	500	X			Boraginaceae	<i>Heliotropium angiospermum</i>	W	X				2			2	
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Leucaena</i> sp.	Wp	X				1			1	
	1	1000	X	X		Anacardiaceae	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Cp	X	X		2	35			37	
	1	500	X			Euphorbiaceae	<i>Manihot esculenta</i>	Cp		X			4			4	
	1	500	X			Rutaceae	<i>Murraya paniculata</i>	Cp	X				15			15	
	501	1000	X	X		Solanaceae	<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i>	Cp	X			2				2	
	501	1000	X			Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora edulis</i> f. <i>flavicarpa</i>	Cp	X				1			1	
	1	500	X			Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora maliformis</i>	Cp	X					1		1	
	1	2000	X	X		Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X	X		190	1337	28		1555	
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Pithecellobium guachapele</i>	Wp	X			3				3	
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Pithecellobium</i> sp.	Wp	X			1				1	
	1	500	X			Myrtaceae	<i>Psidium guajava</i>	Cp	X					1		1	
	1	500	X			Adoxaceae	<i>Sambucus</i> sp.	Wp	X					1		1	
	1501	2000		X		Fabaceae	<i>Senna spectabilis</i>	Wp	X			1				1	
	501	1000	X			Solanaceae	<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	Cp	X				2			2	
	1001	2000		X		Fabaceae	<i>Tachigali guianensis</i>	Cp	X			27				27	
	1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Tithonia diversifolia</i>	Wp	X			1		1		2	
	1	1500	X	X		Asteraceae	<i>Tithonia</i> sp.	Wp	X			137		8		145	
	1	2000	X	X		Poaceae	<i>Zea mays</i>	Cp	X				10	1		11	
<i>Frankliniella brevicaulis</i> Hood, 1937	1	1500	X	X		Fabaceae	<i>Bauhinia forficata</i>	Wp	X				1	4		5	
	1	1000	X			Bixaceae	<i>Bixa orellana</i>	Cp	X			10	1			11	
	1	500	X			Bixaceae	<i>Bixa orellana</i>	Wp	X			4				4	

Species	Altitudinal range		Thermal zone			Botanical family	Associated Plant		System	Plant sampled structure				Geographical region			
	Min	Max	C	T	F					F	H	Fr	St	An	Ca	Or	Total
	1	500	X			Rubiaceae	<i>Borreria capitata</i>	W		X				1			1
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Caesalpinia pulcherrima</i>	Wp		X				1			1
	1	1500	X	X		Rutaceae	<i>Citrus latifolia</i>	Cp		X			1		2		3
	1001	1500		X		Rutaceae	<i>Citrus limon</i>	Cp		X			1				1
	1001	1500		X		Rubiaceae	<i>Coffea arabica</i>	Cp		X				3			3
	1	500	X			Boraginaceae	<i>Cordia dentata</i>	Wp		X				1			1
	1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Emilia</i> sp.	W		X					5		5
	1	1500	X	X		Fabaceae	<i>Gliricidia sepium</i>	Wp		X	X		2		7		9
	1	500	X			Malvaceae	<i>Gossypium hirsutum</i>	Cp		X			2		15		17
	1	500	X			Boraginaceae	<i>Heliotropium angiospermum</i>	W		X				5			5
	501	1000	X			Fabaceae	<i>Inga edulis</i>	Wp		X			1				1
	1	500	X			Verbenaceae	<i>Lantana camara</i>	Wp		X			1				1
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Leucaena</i> sp.	Wp		X				3			3
	1	1000	X			Anacardiaceae	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Cp		X	X		1	81	58		140
	1	1500	X	X		Euphorbiaceae	<i>Manihot esculenta</i>	Cp		X	X		9	2			11
	1	500	X			Musaceae	<i>Musa paradisiaca</i>	Cp		X				5			5
	1	500	X			Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora edulis</i> f. <i>flavicarpa</i>	Cp		X					8		8
	1	1000	X			Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp		X				2	43		45
	1	500	X			Myrtaceae	<i>Psidium guajava</i>	Cp		X					11		11
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Quercus</i> sp.	Cp			X			2			2
	1	500	X			Adoxaceae	<i>Sambucus</i> sp.	Wp		X					2		2
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Senna reticulata</i>	Wp		X			5				5
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Senna</i> sp.	Wp		X			9		2		11
	1	500	X			Malvaceae	<i>Sida parviflora</i>	W		X			1				1
	1	500	X			Malvaceae	<i>Sida rhombifolia</i>	W		X			1				1
	1	500	X			Solanaceae	<i>Solanum crotonifolium</i>	W		X			1				1
	1	500	X			Solanaceae	<i>Solanum melongena</i>	Cp		X				1			1
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Tachigali guianensis</i>	Cp		X					18		18
	1	500	X			Apocynaceae	<i>Thevetia peruviana</i>	Wp		X			9				9
	1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Tithonia diversifolia</i>	Wp		X					4		4
	1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Tridax procumbens</i>	W		X			2				2
	1	2000	X	X		Poaceae	<i>Zea mays</i>	Cp		X			362	708	12		1082

Species	Altitudinal range		Thermal zone			Botanical family	Associated Plant	System	Plant sampled structure				Geographical region					
	Min	Max	C	T	F				F	H	Fr	St	An	Ca	Or	Total		
<i>Frankliniella breviseta</i> Moulton, 1948**	1	500	X			Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus dubius</i>	W	X					5			5	
	1	500	X			Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i>	W	X					5			5	
	1	500	X			Apocynaceae	<i>Calotropis gigantea</i>	W	X					4			4	
	1	500	X			Apocynaceae	<i>Calotropis procera</i>	W	X					4			4	
	1	500	X			Cleomaceae	<i>Cleome spinosa</i>	W	X					77			77	
	1	500	X			Boraginaceae	<i>Heliotropium indicum</i>	W	X					2			2	
	1	500	X			Lamiaceae	<i>Hyptis mutabilis</i>	W	X					10			10	
	1	500	X			Apocynaceae	<i>Sarcostemma clausum</i>	W	X				1				1	
	1	500	X			Portulacaceae	<i>Talinum fruticosum</i>	W	X				2				2	
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>No determinada</i>	Wp	X							1		1
<i>Frankliniella bruneri</i> Watson, 1926	1	500	X			Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus dubius</i>	W	X					2			2	
	1	500	X			Bixaceae	<i>Bixa orellana</i>	Cp	X					2			2	
	1001	1500		X		Rubiaceae	<i>Coffea arabica</i>	Cp	X				1				1	
	1	2000	X	X		Asteraceae	<i>Emilia sonchifolia</i>	W	X				3		1		4	
	1001	1500		X		Asteraceae	<i>Emilia</i> sp.	W	X				2				2	
<i>Frankliniella brunnea</i> (Priesner, 1932)	1	1000	X			Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus dubius</i>	W	X					13			13	
	1	500	X			Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i>	W	X				12				12	
	1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Bidens pilosa</i>	W	X				1				1	
	1	500	X			Bixaceae	<i>Bixa orellana</i>	Wp	X				1				1	
	501	1000	X			Fabaceae	<i>Caesalpinia pulcherrima</i>	Wp	X				1				1	
	1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Emilia sonchifolia</i>	W	X					9			9	
	1001	1500		X		Asteraceae	<i>Galinsoga parviflora</i>	Wp	X				25				25	
	1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Lagascea mollis</i>	W	X				4				4	
	1	500	X			Onagraceae	<i>Ludwigia</i> sp.	W	X				4				4	
	1	500	X			Malvaceae	<i>Melochia pyramidata</i>	W	X				4				4	
	1501	2000		X		Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X				1				1	
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Quercus</i> sp.	Cp		X					1		1	
	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa</i> sp.	Cp				X		4			4	
	501	1000	X			Solanaceae	<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	Cp	X						1			1
	1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Sphagneticola trilobata</i>	Wp	X					4			4	
	1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Tridax procumbens</i>	W	X				13	5			18	
	1501	2000	X	X		Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium</i> sp.	W	X				1				1	

Species	Altitudinal range		Thermal zone			Botanical family	Associated Plant	System	Plant sampled structure				Geographical region			Total
	Min	Max	C	T	F				F	H	Fr	St	An	Ca	Or	
<i>Frankliniella caseariae</i> Moulton, 1933	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Calliandra surinamensis</i>	Wp	X					9		9
	501	1000	X			Solanaceae	<i>Capsicum annuum</i>	Cp	X				1			1
	1001	1500		X		Rubiaceae	<i>Coffea arabica</i>	Cp	X					2		2
	1	1500	X	X		Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X	X			8	10		18
	501	1000	X			Fabaceae	<i>Senna sp</i>	Wp	X				1			1
	1	500	X			Solanaceae	<i>Solanum melongena</i>	Cp	X					1		1
	501	1000	X				<i>Theobroma cacao</i>	Cp	X	X			10			10
<i>Frankliniella cassiae</i> Berzosa, 2006	1	500	X			Rutaceae	<i>Citrus sp.</i>	Cp	X					2		2
	501	1000	X			Fabaceae	<i>Senna sp</i>	Wp	X					3		3
	2501	3000			X	Asteraceae	<i>Taraxacum officinale</i>	W	X				5			5
	2501	3000			X	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium repens</i>	W	X				3			3
<i>Frankliniella cephalica</i> (Crawford DL, 1910)	501	1000	X			Asteraceae	<i>Ageratum sp.</i>	W	X					12		12
	1	500	X			Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus dubius</i>	W	X					1		1
	1	500	X			Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i>	W	X					1		1
	501	2000	X	X		Fabaceae	<i>Arachis pintoii</i>	Cp	X				19	3		22
	1501	2000	X	X		Asteraceae	<i>Bidens pilosa</i>	W	X				1			1
	1	500	X			Bixaceae	<i>Bixa orellana</i>	Cp	X					3		3
	1	500	X			Nyctaginaceae	<i>Boerhavia decumbens</i>	W	X				1			1
	1	500	X			Nyctaginaceae	<i>Boerhavia erecta</i>	W	X				6			6
	1	500	X			Rubiaceae	<i>Borreria capitata</i>	W	X					82		82
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Caesalpinia coriaria</i>	Cp	X					37		37
	1	1000	X			Fabaceae	<i>Caesalpinia pulcherrima</i>	Wp	X					5		5
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Caesalpinia sp.</i>	Wp	X					13		13
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Calliandra trinervia</i>	Wp	X					1		1
	1	500	X			Apocynaceae	<i>Calotropis gigantea</i>	W	X					10		10
	1	500	X			Apocynaceae	<i>Calotropis procera</i>	W	X					3		3
	501	1000	X			Solanaceae	<i>Capsicum annuum</i>	Cp	X				1			1
	1	500	X			Solanaceae	<i>Capsicum sp.</i>	Cp	X					1		1
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Cassia aeschynomene</i>	W	X				7			7
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Cassia fistula</i>	Wp	X				2	28		30
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Centrosema acutifolium</i>	W	X				11			11
1	500	X			Rutaceae	<i>Citrus reticulata</i>	Cp	X						2		2

Species	Altitudinal range		Thermal zone			Botanical family	Associated Plant		System	Plant sampled structure				Geographical region			
	Min	Max	C	T	F					F	H	Fr	St	An	Ca	Or	Total
	1	1000	X			Rutaceae	<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	Cp	X				16	1	17	34	
	1	500	X			Rutaceae	<i>Citrus</i> sp.	Cp	X				8			8	
	1	500	X			Cleomaceae	<i>Cleome spinosa</i>	W	X				1			1	
	1	500	X			Cleomaceae	<i>Cleome</i> sp.	W	X				4			4	
	1001	1500		X		Rubiaceae	<i>Coffea arabica</i>	Cp	X				43	10		53	
	1	500	X			Boraginaceae	<i>Cordia dentata</i>	Wp	X				33			33	
	1	500	X			Bignoniaceae	<i>Crescentia cujete</i>	Wp	X				1			1	
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Crotalaria juncea</i>	W	X				12			12	
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Crotalaria</i> sp.	Wp	X				3			3	
	1	500	X			Euphorbiaceae	<i>Croton leptostachys</i>	W	X				1			1	
	1	500	X			Cucurbitaceae	<i>Cucumis melo</i>	Cp	X				8			8	
	1	500	X			Cucurbitaceae	<i>Cucurbita maxima</i>	Cp	X				2			2	
	1	500	X			Amaranthaceae	<i>Cyathula achyranthoides</i>	Wp	X				1			1	
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Dioclea</i> sp.	W	X				1			1	
	1	500	X			Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa colona</i>	W	X				1			1	
	1	2000		X		Asteraceae	<i>Emilia sonchifolia</i>	W	X				19			19	
	1	1500	X	X		Asteraceae	<i>Emilia</i> sp.	W	X				13			13	
	501	1000	X			Euphorbiaceae	<i>Euphorbia heterophylla</i>	Wp	X				3			3	
	1	500	X			Euphorbiaceae	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i>	W	X				1	3		4	
	1	500	X			Euphorbiaceae	<i>Euphorbia hypericifolia</i>	W	X				2			2	
	1	500	X			Apocynaceae	<i>Funastrum clausum</i>	Wp	X				1			1	
	1001	1500		X		Asteraceae	<i>Galinsoga</i> sp.	Wp	X				5			5	
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Gliricidia sepium</i>	Wp	X				5	1		6	
	1	1000	X			Malvaceae	<i>Gossypium hirsutum</i>	Cp	X	X	X		396	51	201	648	
	1	500	X			Malvaceae	<i>Guazuma ulmifolia</i>	Wp	X				5			5	
	1	500	X			Zingiberaceae	<i>Hedychium coronarium</i>	W	X				1			1	
	1501	2000		X		Asteraceae	<i>Helianthus annuus</i>	Cp	X				12			12	
	1	500	X			Boraginaceae	<i>Heliotropium angiospermum</i>	W	X				4			4	
	1	500	X			Boraginaceae	<i>Heliotropium indicum</i>	W	X				2			2	
	1	500	X			Lamiaceae	<i>Hyptis mutabilis</i>	W	X				19			19	
	501	1000	X			Convolvulaceae	<i>Ipomoea pes-caprae</i>	Cp	X					9		9	
	1	500	X			Zygophyllaceae	<i>Kallstroemia maxima</i>	W	X				2			2	

Species	Altitudinal range		Thermal zone			Botanical family	Associated Plant	System	Plant sampled structure				Geographical region			
	Min	Max	C	T	F				F	H	Fr	St	An	Ca	Or	Total
	1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Lagascea mollis</i>	W	X				4			4
	1	500	X			Verbenaceae	<i>Lantana camara</i>	W	X				8			8
	1	500	X			Verbenaceae	<i>Lantana</i> sp.	W	X				1			1
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Leucaena</i> sp.	Wp	X					1		1
	1	500	X			Chrysobalanaceae	<i>Licania</i> sp.	Wp	X					12		12
	1	500	X			Onagraceae	<i>Ludwigia</i> sp.	W	X				1			1
	1	500	X			Malvaceae	<i>Malvastrum americanum</i>	W	X				9			9
	1	500	X			Malvaceae	<i>Malvaviscus concinnus</i>	W	X				2			2
	1	1500	X	X		Anacardiaceae	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Cp	X	X			61	31		92
	1	2000	X	X		Euphorbiaceae	<i>Manihot esculenta</i>	Cp	X	X				22		22
	1	500	X			Malvaceae	<i>Melochia parvifolia</i>	W	X				54			54
	1	500	X			Malvaceae	<i>Melochia pyramidata</i>	W	X				17			17
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Mimosa pudica</i>	W	X				1			1
	1	500	X			Cucurbitaceae	<i>Momordica charantia</i>	Wp	X				7	1		8
	501	1500	X	X		Musaceae	<i>Musa paradisiaca</i>	Cp	X					7		7
	1	1000	X			Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora edulis</i> f. <i>flavicarpa</i>	Cp	X				1	7	6	14
	1	500	X			Malvaceae	<i>Pavonia sepium</i>	W	X				8			8
	1	2000	X	X		Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X	X			27	19		46
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i>	Cp	X					1		1
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Rhynchosia minima</i>	Cp	X				2			2
	1	500	X			Rosaceae	<i>Rosa</i> sp.	Cp	X		X			1		1
	1	500	X			Acanthaceae	<i>Ruellia tuberosa</i>	W	X				5			5
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Senna occidentalis</i>	W	X				2			2
	1	2000	X	X		Fabaceae	<i>Senna</i> sp	Wp	X				50	30		80
	1	500	X			Malvaceae	<i>Sida acuta</i>	W	X				1			1
	1	500	X			Malvaceae	<i>Sida parviflora</i>	W	X				5			5
	1	500	X			Malvaceae	<i>Sida rhombifolia</i>	W	X				9			9
	1	500	X			Solanaceae	<i>Solanum crotonifolium</i>	W	X				10			10
	501	1000	X			Solanaceae	<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	Cp	X					1		1
	1	500	X			Solanaceae	<i>Solanum melongena</i>	Cp	X					5		5
	1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Sphagneticola trilobata</i>	Wp	X				2			2
	1	500	X			Bignoniaceae	<i>Tabebuia rosea</i>	Wp	X					1		1

Species	Altitudinal range		Thermal zone			Botanical family	Associated Plant	System	Plant sampled structure				Geographical region			
	Min	Max	C	T	F				F	H	Fr	St	An	Ca	Or	Total
	1	500	X			Portulacaceae	<i>Talinum fruticosum</i>	W	X				2			2
	1	500	X			Portulacaceae	<i>Talinum paniculatum</i>	W	X				11			11
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Tamarindus indica</i>	Wp	X					1		1
	1	500	X			Bignoniaceae	<i>Tecoma stans</i>	Wp	X				4			4
	1	500	X			Apocynaceae	<i>Thevetia peruviana</i>	Wp	X				2			2
	1	1500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Tithonia diversifolia</i>	Wp	X				13		15	28
	1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Tithonia</i> sp.	Wp	X						1	1
	1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Tridax procumbens</i>	W	X				3			3
	1	500	X			Turneraceae	<i>Turnera ulmifolia</i>	W	X				1			1
	1	500	X			Poaceae	<i>Zea mays</i>	Cp	X					208	1	209
<i>Frankliniella colombiana</i> Moulton, 1948	3001	3500			X	Asteraceae	<i>Espeletia</i> sp.	Wp	X				5			5
<i>Frankliniella condei</i> John, 1928**	3001	3500			X	Asteraceae	<i>Espeletia</i> sp.	Wp	X				1			1
<i>Frankliniella cotobrusensis</i> Retana & Mound, 1995	1001	1500		X		Rubiaceae	<i>Coffea arabica</i>	Cp	X				2			2
<i>Frankliniella curta</i> (Hood, 1942)	1501	2000		X		Euphorbiaceae	<i>Manihot esculenta</i>	Cp		X			1			1
	1501	2000		x		Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp					2			2
	1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Tithonia diversifolia</i>	Wp	X						2	2
	1501	2000		X		Fabaceae	No determinada	Wp	X				1			1
<i>Frankliniella davidsoni</i> Moulton, 1936**	3001	3500			X	Asteraceae	<i>Espeletia</i> sp.	Wp	X				1			1
<i>Frankliniella desmodii</i> Mound & Marullo, 1996	1	500	X			Malvaceae	<i>Melochia parvifolia</i>	W	X				1			1
	501	1000	X			Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X				69			69
	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus persica</i>	Cp		X			2			2
	1	500				Fabaceae	<i>Senna</i> sp.	Wp	X						2	2
	1001	1500		X		Fabaceae	No determinada	Wp		X			3			3
<i>Frankliniella distinguenda</i> Bagnall, 1919	501	1000	X			Asteraceae	<i>Ageratum</i> sp.	W	X					1		1
	1	500	X			Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus dubius</i>	W	X					3		3
	1	500	X			Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i>	W	X				1	1		2
	501	1000	X			Rutaceae	<i>Citrus</i> sp.	Cp	X					6		6
	2001	2500			X	Boraginaceae	<i>Cordia alliodora</i>	Cp	X				2			2
	1001	1500		X		Asteraceae	<i>Emilia sonchifolia</i>	W	X				30			30
	1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Emilia</i> sp.	W	X						1	1
	501	1000	X			Euphorbiaceae	<i>Euphorbia catinifolia</i>	W	X					6		6
	1	500	X			Malvaceae	<i>Gossypium hirsutum</i>	Cp	X						1	1

Species	Altitudinal range		Thermal zone			Botanical family	Associated Plant	System	Plant sampled structure				Geographical region				
	Min	Max	C	T	F				F	H	Fr	St	An	Ca	Or	Total	
	1	500	X			Boraginaceae	<i>Heliotropium indicum</i>	W	X					7			7
	1	500	X			Anacardiaceae	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Cp	X					7			7
	1	500	X			Euphorbiaceae	<i>Manihot esculenta</i>	Cp	X					1			1
	1	500				Apocynaceae	<i>Sarcostemma clausum</i>	W	X					1			1
<i>Frankliniella diversa</i> Hood, 1935	1	500	X			Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X					1			1
	2501	3000			X	Fabaceae	<i>Senna</i> sp	W	X					1			1
<i>Frankliniella espeletiae</i> Berzosa, 2006	3001	3500			X	Asteraceae	<i>Espeletia grandiflora</i>	Wp	X					13			13
	3001	4000			X	Asteraceae	<i>Espeletia</i> sp.	Wp	X					5			5
<i>Frankliniella fallaciosa</i> Priesner, 1933	2001	2500			X	Brassicaceae	<i>Brassica rapa</i>	W	X					1			1
	1001	1500		X		Rutaceae	<i>Citrus</i> sp.	Cp	X					1			1
	2501	3000			X	Asparagaceae	<i>Furcraea andina</i>	Wp	X					1			1
	2501	3000			X	Fabaceae	<i>Senna</i> sp	W	X					1			1
	2501	3000			X	Solanaceae	<i>Streptosolen jamesonii</i>	Wp	X					1			1
	2501	3000			X	Asteraceae	No determinada	Wp	X					16			16
<i>Frankliniella fulvipennis</i> Moulton, 1933	1001	1500		X		Rubiaceae	<i>Coffea arabica</i>	Cp	X					1			1
	2001	2500			X	Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X					1			1
<i>Frankliniella fulvipes</i> Bagnall, 1919**	2001	2500			X	Brassicaceae	<i>Brassica rapa</i>	W	X					1			1
	501	1000	X			Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora edulis</i> f. <i>flavicarpa</i>	Cp	X						1		1
<i>Frankliniella gardeniae</i> Moulton, 1948	1	500	X			Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus dubius</i>	W	X				2	14			16
	1001	1500		X		Fabaceae	<i>Arachis pintoii</i>	Cp	X					1			1
	2501	3000			X	Asteraceae	<i>Baccharis prunifolia</i>	Wp	X					13			13
	501	1500	X	X		Fabaceae	<i>Bauhinia forficata</i>	Wp	X				1	1			2
	1501	2000			X	Asteraceae	<i>Bidens pilosa</i>	W	X					1			1
	501	2000			X	Bixaceae	<i>Bixa orellana</i>	Cp	X				2	1			3
	501	1000	X			Fabaceae	<i>Caesalpinia pulcherrima</i>	Wp	X						1		1
	1001	1500			X	Fabaceae	<i>Calliandra</i> sp.	Wp	X					4			4
	1	500	X			Solanaceae	<i>Capsicum</i> sp.	Cp	X						1		1
	1001	1500			X	Fabaceae	<i>Cassia fistula</i>	Wp	X					1			1
	1	2000	X	X		Rutaceae	<i>Citrus latifolia</i>	Cp	X	X			28	1	1		30
	1001	1500			X	Rutaceae	<i>Citrus limon</i>	Cp	X					2			2
	501	2000	X	X		Rutaceae	<i>Citrus reticulata</i>	Cp	X					35			35
	501	2000	X	X		Rutaceae	<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	Cp	X	X			196		3		199

Species	Altitudinal range		Thermal zone			Botanical family	Associated Plant		System	Plant sampled structure				Geographical region			
	Min	Max	C	T	F					F	H	Fr	St	An	Ca	Or	Total
	1	2000	X	X		Rutaceae	<i>Citrus</i> sp.	Cp	X				36	82		118	
	501	2000	X	X		Rubiaceae	<i>Coffea arabica</i>	Cp	X				1085	5		1090	
	1	1000	X			Cucurbitaceae	<i>Cucurbita maxima</i>	Cp	X					2	2	4	
	1501	2000		X		Asteraceae	<i>Dahlia</i> sp.	Ornamental	X				11			11	
	1001	1500		X		Asteraceae	<i>Emilia sonchifolia</i>	W	X				2			2	
	501	1000	X			Euphorbiaceae	<i>Euphorbia heterophylla</i>	Wp	X					8		8	
	1	500	X			Euphorbiaceae	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i>	W	X				1			1	
	1	500	X			Apocynaceae	<i>Funastrum clausum</i>	Wp	X					1		1	
	2501	3000			X	Asparagaceae	<i>Furcraea</i> sp.	Wp	X				1			1	
	1001	1500		X		Asteraceae	<i>Galinsoga</i> sp.	Wp	X				50			50	
	1001	1500		X		Fabaceae	<i>Gliricidia sepium</i>	W	X				1			1	
	2001	2500			X	Xanthorrhoeaceae	<i>Hemerocallis</i> sp.	Ornamental	X	X			2			2	
	1001	1500		X		Fabaceae	<i>Inga densiflora</i>	Wp	X					57		57	
	501	2000	X	X		Fabaceae	<i>Inga edulis</i>	Wp	X				82			82	
	1001	1500		X		Fabaceae	<i>Lantana camara</i>	W	X					1		1	
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	Wp	X				1			1	
	1	2000	X	X		Anacardiaceae	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Cp	X	X			678	76		754	
	1	2000	X	X		Euphorbiaceae	<i>Manihot esculenta</i>	Cp	X				4	4		8	
	1	500	X			Rutaceae	<i>Murraya paniculata</i>	Cp	X					41		41	
	1001	1500		X		Musaceae	<i>Musa paradisiaca</i>	Cp	X				2			2	
	501	2500	X	X	X	Solanaceae	<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i>	Cp	X				2			2	
	2001	2500			X	Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora edulis f. edulis</i>	Cp	X				1			1	
	1001	1500		X		Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora edulis f. flavicarpa</i>	Cp	X				1			1	
	2501	3000			X	Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora ligularis</i>	Cp					1			1	
	1	2500	X	X	X	Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X	X			1841	132	25	1998	
	1	500	X			Solanaceae	<i>Physalis</i> sp.	Wp	X				1			1	
	501	1000	X			Fabaceae	<i>Pithecellobium guachapele</i>	W	X				3			3	
	501	1000	X			Fabaceae	<i>Prosopis</i> sp.	Wp	X				10			10	
	2001	2500			X	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus</i> sp.	Cp	X				28			28	
	1	500	X			Myrtaceae	<i>Psidium guajava</i>	Cp	X						2	2	
	2501	3000			X	Brassicaceae	<i>Raphanus raphanistrum</i>	W	X				2			2	
	1501	2000		X		Euphorbiaceae	<i>Ricinus communis</i>	Wp	X				3			3	

Species	Altitudinal range		Thermal zone			Botanical family	Associated Plant	System	Plant sampled structure				Geographical region				
	Min	Max	C	T	F				F	H	Fr	St	An	Ca	Or	Total	
	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa</i> sp.	Cp					X	1			1
	1501	2000		X		Rosaceae	<i>Rubus glaucus</i>	Cp	X					9			9
	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus glaucus</i>	Wp	X					3			3
	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus</i> sp.	Wp	X					4			4
	2501	3000			X	Actinidiaceae	<i>Saurauia scabra</i>	Wp	X					4			4
	1	3000	X	X	X	Fabaceae	<i>Senna</i> sp	Wp	X					5		1	6
	501	1000	X			Solanaceae	<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	Cp	X						1		1
	1501	2000		X		Solanaceae	<i>Solanum quitoense</i>	Wp	X					1			1
	501	2000		X		Fabaceae	<i>Tachigali guianensis</i>	Cp	X					49			49
	2001	3000			X	Asteraceae	<i>Taraxacum officinale</i>	W	X					4			4
	2501	3000			X	Asteraceae	<i>Taraxacum</i> sp.	Wp	X					2			2
	1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Tithonia diversifolia</i>	Wp	X							4	4
	1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Tridax procumbens</i>	W	X					1			1
	2501	3000			X	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium</i> sp.	W	X					4			4
	1	500	X			Turneraceae	<i>Turnera ulmifolia</i>	W	X					3			3
<i>Frankliniella gemina</i> Bagnall, 1919	1	2000	X	X		Poaceae	<i>Zea mays</i>	Cp	X					4	17		21
<i>Frankliniella gossypiana</i> (Hood, 1936)	1001	1500		X		Poaceae	<i>Zea mays</i>	Cp	X					9			9
	1	500	X			Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus dubius</i>	W	X					1	1		2
	1	500	X			Cucurbitaceae	<i>Cucurbita maxima</i>	Cp	X	X					5		5
	1	500	X			Euphorbiaceae	<i>Delechampia scandens</i>	W	X					4			4
	1	500	X			Euphorbiaceae	<i>Euphorbia catinifolia</i>	Cp	X							3	3
	1	500	X			Malvaceae	<i>Gossypium hirsutum</i>	Cp		X					1		1
	1	500	X			Convolvulaceae	<i>Ipomoea</i> sp.	W	X					3			3
	1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Lagascea mollis</i>	W	X					1			1
	1	500	X			Malvaceae	<i>Malvastrum americanum</i>	W	X					1			1
	1	500	X			Anacardiaceae	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Cp	X						3		3
	1	2000	X	X		Euphorbiaceae	<i>Manihot esculenta</i>	Cp	X	X				1	8		9
	1	500	X			Cucurbitaceae	<i>Momordica charantia</i>	Wp	X						1		1
	501	1500	X	X		Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X					5	5		10
	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa</i> sp.	Cp					X	3			3
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Senna occidentalis</i>	W	X					3			3
	1	1000	X			Fabaceae	<i>Senna</i> sp	Wp	X					9	2		11

Species	Altitudinal range		Thermal zone			Botanical family	Associated Plant	System	Plant sampled structure				Geographical region				
	Min	Max	C	T	F				F	H	Fr	St	An	Ca	Or	Total	
<i>Frankliniella insularis</i> (Franklin, 1908)	1	500				Fabaceae	<i>Tamarindus indica</i>	Wp	X					4			4
	1	3000	X	X	X	Poaceae	<i>Zea mays</i>	Cp	X					36	6	1	43
	501	1000	X			Fabaceae	<i>Arachis pintoii</i>	Cp	X					4			4
	1	1500	X	X		Fabaceae	<i>Bauhinia forficata</i>	Wp	X					2	2		4
	1	500	X			Bixaceae	<i>Bixa orellana</i>	Cp	X					1			1
	1	500	X			Bixaceae	<i>Bixa orellana</i>	Wp	X					1			1
	501	1000	X			Solanaceae	<i>Capsicum annuum</i>	Cp	X					1			1
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Centrosema acutifolium</i>	W	X					1			1
	1001	1500		X		Rutaceae	<i>Citrus latifolia</i>	Cp	X					17			17
	1001	1500		X		Rutaceae	<i>Citrus limon</i>	Cp	X					9			9
	501	1500	X	X		Rutaceae	<i>Citrus reticulata</i>	Cp	X					2			2
	501	1500	X	X		Rutaceae	<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	Cp	X					44			44
	1	1500	X	X		Rutaceae	<i>Citrus</i> sp.	Cp	X					1	7		8
	1001	1500		X		Rubiaceae	<i>Coffea arabica</i>	Cp	X					4	16		20
	1	500	X			Boraginaceae	<i>Cordia dentata</i>	Wp	X					2			2
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Dioclea</i> sp.	W	X					4			4
	1	1500	X	X		Fabaceae	<i>Gliricidia sepium</i>	W	X					176		1	177
	1	500	X			Malvaceae	<i>Gossypium hirsutum</i>	Cp	X					3	54	16	73
	1001	1500		X		Fabaceae	<i>Inga densiflora</i>	Wp	X					1			1
	1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Lagascea mollis</i>	W	X					1			1
	501	1000	X			Anacardiaceae	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Cp	X					1			1
	1	500	X			Euphorbiaceae	<i>Manihot esculenta</i>	Cp	X	X				1	1		2
	1	500				Malvaceae	<i>Melochia pyramidata</i>	W	X					1			1
	501	1000	X			Solanaceae	<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i>	Cp	X					1			1
	1	1000	X			Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora edulis</i> f. <i>flavicarpa</i>	Cp	X					1		22	23
	1	2000	X	X		Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X					1	1		2
	1001	2000		X		Fabaceae	<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i>	Cp	X					326			326
501	1000	X			Fabaceae	<i>Pithecellobium guachapele</i>	W	X					1			1	
1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Pithecellobium</i> sp.	Wp	X					2			2	
1	1500	X	X		Fabaceae	<i>Rhynchosia minima</i>	Cp	X					12	1		13	
501	1500	X	X		Fabaceae	<i>Senna</i> sp.	Wp	X					5			5	
1	500	X			Bignoniaceae	<i>Tabebuia rosea</i>	Wp	X					6			6	

Species	Altitudinal range		Thermal zone			Botanical family	Associated Plant	System	Plant sampled structure				Geographical region				
	Min	Max	C	T	F				F	H	Fr	St	An	Ca	Or	Total	
<i>Frankliniella invasor</i> Sakimura, 1972	1001	2000		X		Fabaceae	<i>Tachigali guianensis</i>	Cp	X					3			3
	1	500				Bignoniaceae	<i>Tecoma stans</i>	Wp	X					1			1
	2001	2500			X	Fabaceae	<i>Tephrosia</i> sp.	Wp	X					11			11
	1	2000	X	X		Poaceae	<i>Zea mays</i>	Cp	X				4	47	1		52
	501	1000	X			Fabaceae	<i>Caesalpinia pulcherrima</i>	Wp	X				1	1			2
	1001	1500		X		Rutaceae	<i>Citrus latifolia</i>	Cp	X					2			2
	501	1500	X	X		Rutaceae	<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	Cp	X				4	21			25
	1	500	X			Rutaceae	<i>Citrus</i> sp.	Cp	X					6			6
	1001	2000			X	Rubiaceae	<i>Coffea arabica</i>	Cp	X				3	13			16
	1	500	X			Boraginaceae	<i>Cordia dentata</i>	Wp	X					5			5
	1501	2000		X		Asteraceae	<i>Dahlia</i> sp.	Cp	X				2				2
	2501	3000			X	Asteraceae	<i>Emilia sonchifolia</i>	W	X				2				2
	501	1000	X			Euphorbiaceae	<i>Euphorbia heterophylla</i>	Wp	X					1			1
	2001	2500			X	Asparagaceae	<i>Furcraea andina</i>	Wp	X				1				1
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Gliricidia sepium</i>	Wp	X					1			1
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	Wp	X				1				1
	1	500	X			Chrysobalanaceae	<i>Licania</i> sp.	Wp	X					4			4
	1	1500	X			Anacardiaceae	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Cp	X				13	15			28
	1	500	X			Musaceae	<i>Musa paradisiaca</i>	Cp	X					1			1
	501	1000	X			Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora edulis f. flavicarpa</i>	Cp	X				6	1			7
	2501	3000			X	Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora ligularis</i>	Cp	X				3				3
	501	2000		X		Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X				65	1			66
	1501	2000		X		Fabaceae	<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i>	Cp	X				6				6
	1501	2500		X	X	Fabaceae	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	Cp	X				12				12
	1	1000	X			Fabaceae	<i>Pithecellobium guachapele</i>	W	X				3				3
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Pithecellobium</i> sp.	Wp	X				1				1
	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa</i> sp.	Cp				X	1				1
	2001	2500			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus glaucus</i>	Cp	X				1				1
	1501	3000		X	X	Fabaceae	<i>Senna</i> sp.	Cp	X				4				4
	1	500	X			Apocynaceae	<i>Thevetia peruviana</i>	Wp	X				10				10
2501	3000			X	Fabaceae	<i>Vicia faba</i>	Cp		X			1				1	
1	500	X			Poaceae	<i>Zea mays</i>	Cp	X					4			4	

Species	Altitudinal range		Thermal zone			Botanical family	Associated Plant	System	Plant sampled structure				Geographical region			
	Min	Max	C	T	F				F	H	Fr	St	An	Ca	Or	Total
<i>Frankliniella kellyae</i> Sakimura, 1981	501	2000	X	X		Rutaceae	<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	Cp	X	X			8	28		36
	1	500	X			Rutaceae	<i>Citrus</i> sp.	Cp	X					137		137
	1001	2000		X		Rubiaceae	<i>Coffea arabica</i>	Cp	X				22	5		27
	1	500	X			Rutaceae	<i>Murraya paniculata</i>	Cp	X					2		2
	1	2000	X	X		Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X				10	9		19
	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa</i> sp.	Cp				X	1			1
	1501	2000		X		Fabaceae	<i>Senna</i> sp.	Cp	X				2			2
	1001	1500				Fabaceae	<i>Tachigali guianensis</i>	Cp	X				1			1
	2501	3000			X	Fabaceae	<i>Vicia faba</i>	Cp	X				3			3
<i>Frankliniella lorena</i> Mound & Marullo, 1996	1001	1500		X		Rubiaceae	<i>Coffea arabica</i>	Cp	X				1			1
<i>Frankliniella mekokara</i> Mound & Marullo, 1996**	2001	2500			X	Asteraceae	<i>Taraxacum officinale</i>	W					7			7
<i>Frankliniella melanommata</i> Williams, 1913	501	1000	X			Rutaceae	<i>Citrus reticulata</i>	Cp	X				6			6
	501	1000	X			Rutaceae	<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	Cp	X						3	3
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Crotalaria juncea</i>	W	X				3			3
	1	500	X			Verbenaceae	<i>Lantana camara</i>	W	X				2			2
	1	2000	X	X		Euphorbiaceae	<i>Manihot esculenta</i>	Cp	X	X			39	78	20	137
	1	500	X			Cucurbitaceae	<i>Momordica charantia</i>	Wp	X				1			1
	1	500	X			Rutaceae	<i>Murraya paniculata</i>	Cp	X					2		2
	1	500	X			Myrtaceae	<i>Psidium guajava</i>	Cp	X						1	1
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Senna occidentalis</i>	W	X				1			1
	1	500	X			Poaceae	<i>Zea mays</i>	Cp	X					1		1
<i>Frankliniella minuta</i> (Moulton, 1907)	1001	1500		X		Musaceae	<i>Musa paradisiaca</i>	Cp	X					4		4
	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa</i> sp.	Cp				X	4			4
	1501	2000		X		Asteraceae	<i>Taraxacum officinale</i>	W	X				1			1
	1	1500	X	X		Asteraceae	<i>Tithonia diversifolia</i>	Wp	X				1		2	3
	1001	1500		X		Asteraceae	<i>Tithonia</i> sp.	Wp	X				5			5
	2501	3000			X	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium repens</i>	W	X				1			1
<i>Frankliniella musaeparda</i> Hood, 1952	1001	1500		X		Rutaceae	<i>Citrus latifolia</i>	Cp	X				2			2
	1001	1500		X		Rutaceae	<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	Cp	X				3			3
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Gliricidia sepium</i>	Wp	X						1	1
	1001	1500		X		Fabaceae	<i>Inga edulis</i>	Cp	X				23			23
	1	1000	X			Anacardiaceae	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Cp	X	X			9			9

Species	Altitudinal range		Thermal zone			Botanical family	Associated Plant		System	Plant sampled structure				Geographical region			
	Min	Max	C	T	F					F	H	Fr	St	An	Ca	Or	Total
	1	1500	X			Euphorbiaceae	<i>Manihot esculenta</i>	Cp	X					1	1		2
	1	500	X			Rutaceae	<i>Murraya paniculata</i>	Cp	X						1		1
	1001	2000		X		Musaceae	<i>Musa paradisiaca</i>	Cp	X					45			45
	1501	2000		X		Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora edulis f. flavicarpa</i>	Cp		X				1			1
	1501	2000		X		Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X					1			1
	2501	3000			X	Brassicaceae	<i>Raphanus raphanistrum</i>	Cp	X					30			30
	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa sp.</i>	Cp				X		1			1
	501	1000	X			Fabaceae	<i>Senna sp.</i>	W	X					13			13
	1501	2000		X		Fabaceae	<i>Senna spectabilis</i>	Wp	X					3			3
	1001	1500		X		Fabaceae	<i>Tachigali guianensis</i>	Cp	X					22			22
	1501	2000		X		Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium sp.</i>	W	X					1			1
<i>Frankliniella nakaharai</i> Sakimura & O'Neill, 1979**	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa sp.</i>	Cp				X		1			1
<i>Frankliniella nigricauda</i> Hood, 1925**	501	1000	X			Fabaceae	<i>Gliricidia sepium</i>	Wp	X						3		3
<i>Frankliniella occidentalis</i> (Pergande, 1895)	2501	3000		X		Fabaceae	<i>Acacia sp.</i>	Wp	X					1			1
	2501	3000		X		Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus dubius</i>	W	X					3			3
	2501	3000		X		Asparagaceae	<i>Asparagus officinalis</i>	Cp	X					1			1
	2001	2500		X		Brassicaceae	<i>Brassica rapa</i>	W	X					3			3
	2001	3000		X		Solanaceae	<i>Capsicum annuum</i>	Cp	X	X				3			3
	2001	2500		X		Asteraceae	<i>Chrysanthemum sp.</i>	Cp	X					1			1
	2000	2500		X		Rutaceae	<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	Cp	X					1			1
	2001	3000		X		Apiaceae	<i>Coriandrum sativum</i>	Cp	X					1			1
	2501	3000		X		Cucurbitaceae	<i>Cucurbita pepo</i>	Cp	X					2			2
	1501	2000		X		Asteraceae	<i>Dahlia sp.</i>	Cp	X					2			2
	2501	3000		X		Apiaceae	<i>Daucus carota</i>	Cp	X					1			1
	2501	3000		X		Asteraceae	<i>Emilia sonchifolia</i>	W	X					2			2
	2501	3000		X		Asparagaceae	<i>Furcraea andina</i>	Wp	X					8			8
	2501	3000		X		Asteraceae	<i>Hypochaeris radicata</i>	W	X					1			1
	2501	3000		X		Asteraceae	<i>Lactuca sativa</i>	Cp		X				62			62
	1501	2000		X		Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X					3			3
	1501	3000		X		Fabaceae	<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i>	Cp	X					6			6
	2001	2500		X		Fabaceae	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	Cp	X					8			8
	2501	3000		X		Brassicaceae	<i>Raphanus raphanistrum</i>	W	X					1			1

Species	Altitudinal range		Thermal zone			Botanical family	Associated Plant		System	Plant sampled structure				Geographical region			Total
	Min	Max	C	T	F					F	H	Fr	St	An	Ca	Or	
	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa sp.</i>	Cp				X	216			216	
	2001	2500			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus glaucus</i>	Cp	X	X			14			14	
	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus glaucus</i>	Wp	X				1			1	
	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus sp.</i>	Wp	X				3			3	
	2501	3000			X	Polygonaceae	<i>Rumex crispus</i>	W	X				2			2	
	2501	3000			X	Fabaceae	<i>Senna sp.</i>	W	X				1			1	
	2501	3000			X	Fabaceae	<i>Senna viarum</i>	Wp	X				1			1	
	2501	3000			X	Asteraceae	<i>Silybum marianum</i>	Wp	X				1			1	
	1501	3000	X	X		Solanaceae	<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	Cp	X				3			3	
	2501	3000			X	Solanaceae	<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	Cp	X	X			19			19	
	2501	3000			X	Amaranthaceae	<i>Spinacia oleracea</i>	Cp	X				72			72	
	2501	3000			X	Asteraceae	<i>Taraxacum officinale</i>	W	X				1			1	
	2001	3000			X	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium pratense</i>	W	X				14			14	
	2501	3000			X	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium repens</i>	W	X				13			13	
	1501	2000	X			Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium sp.</i>	W	X				1			1	
	2501	3000			X	Fabaceae	<i>Vicia faba</i>	Cp	X	X			52			52	
	2501	3000			X	Araceae	<i>Zantedeschia aethiopica</i>	Cp	X				21			21	
	2501	3000			X	Poaceae	<i>Zea mays</i>	Cp	X				16			16	
<i>Frankliniella oxyura</i> Bagnall, 1919**	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa sp.</i>	Cp				X	4			4	
<i>Frankliniella panamensis</i> Hood, 1925	2501	3000			X	Amaryllidaceae	<i>Allium cepa</i>	Cp	X				4			4	
	2501	3000			X	Amaryllidaceae	<i>Allium fistulosum</i>	Cp	X				3			3	
	2501	3000			X	Amaryllidaceae	<i>Allium sativum</i>	Cp	X				1			1	
	2501	3000			X	Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus dubius</i>	W	X				4			4	
	1501	2000	X			Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus sp.</i>	W		X			3			3	
	2501	3000			X	Araceae	<i>Anthurium sp.</i>	Cp	X				4			4	
	2501	3000			X	Asparagaceae	<i>Asparagus officinalis</i>	Cp	X				3			3	
	2001	2500			X	Brassicaceae	<i>Brassica rapa</i>	W	X				5			5	
	2501	3000			X	Cannaceae	<i>Canna indica</i>	Cp	X				6			6	
	1501	3000			X	Solanaceae	<i>Capsicum annuum</i>	Cp	X	X			6			6	
	2501	3000			X	Solanaceae	<i>Capsicum sp.</i>	Cp	X				3			3	
	2001	3000			X	Asteraceae	<i>Chrysanthemum sp.</i>	Cp	X				17			17	
	1501	2000	X			Rubiaceae	<i>Coffea arabica</i>	Cp	X				1			1	

Species	Altitudinal range		Thermal zone			Botanical family	Associated Plant	System	Plant sampled structure				Geographical region				
	Min	Max	C	T	F				F	H	Fr	St	An	Ca	Or	Total	
	2001	3000			X	Apiaceae	<i>Coriandrum sativum</i>	Cp	X	X			3				3
	2501	3000			X	Cucurbitaceae	<i>Cucurbita maxima</i>	Cp	X				4				4
	2501	3000			X	Cucurbitaceae	<i>Cucurbita pepo</i>	Cp	X				1				1
	1501	3000		X	X	Asteraceae	<i>Dahlia</i> sp.	Ornamental	X				27				27
	2501	3000			X	Asteraceae	<i>Emilia sonchifolia</i>	W	X				1				1
	2001	3000			X	Asparagaceae	<i>Furcraea andina</i>	Wp	X				16				16
	2501	3000			X	Asparagaceae	<i>Furcraea</i> sp.	Wp	X				11				11
	2001	2500			X	Xanthorrhoeaceae	<i>Hemerocallis</i> sp.	Ornamental	X	X			7				7
	2501	3000			X	Poaceae	<i>Holcus lanatus</i>	W	X				2				2
	3001	3500			X	Rosaceae	<i>Lachemilla orbiculata</i>	Wp	X				1				1
	2501	3000			X	Fabaceae	<i>Lupinus</i> sp.	Wp	X				5				5
	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Malus sylvestris</i>	Wp	X				4				4
	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Malus domestica</i>	Cp		X			1				1
	2001	2500				Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora edulis f. edulis</i>	Cp	X	X			11				11
	1501	2000		X		Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora edulis f. flavicarpa</i>	Cp	X				9				9
	1501	3000		X	X	Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora ligularis</i>	Cp	X				19				19
	2501	3000			X	Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora tarminiana</i>	Cp	X				18				18
	2001	2500			X	Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X				1				1
	1501	3000		X	X	Fabaceae	<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i>	Cp	X	X			1347				1347
	1501	3000		X	X	Fabaceae	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	Cp	X				109				109
	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus domestica</i>	Cp	X	X			58				58
	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus persica</i>	Cp	X	X			17				17
	2001	2500			X	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus</i> sp.	Cp	X				5				5
	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Pyrus communis</i>	Cp		X			5				5
	2001	3000			X	Brassicaceae	<i>Raphanus raphanistrum</i>	W	X				15				15
	2501	3000			X	Brassicaceae	<i>Raphanus</i> sp.	Cp	X				68				68
	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa</i> sp.	Cp				X	327				327
	1501	3000		X	X	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus glaucus</i>	Cp	X	X			406				406
	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus glaucus</i>	Wp	X				126				126
	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus</i> sp.	Wp	X				11				11
	2501	3000			X	Polygonaceae	<i>Rumex crispus</i>	W	X				1				1
	2001	2500			X	Rutaceae	<i>Ruta</i> sp.	Cp	X				2				2

Species	Altitudinal range		Thermal zone			Botanical family	Associated Plant		System	Plant sampled structure				Geographical region			
	Min	Max	C	T	F					F	H	Fr	St	An	Ca	Or	Total
	2501	3000			X	Fabaceae	<i>Senna</i> sp	W		X				3			3
	2501	3000			X	Fabaceae	<i>Senna viarum</i>	Wp		X				6			6
	1501	2000		X		Solanaceae	<i>Solanum betaceum</i>	Cp		X				1			1
	1501	3000			X	Solanaceae	<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	Cp		X				14			14
	1501	2000			X	Solanaceae	<i>Solanum quitoense</i>	Cp		X				1			1
	2500	3000			X	Solanaceae	<i>Solanum quitoense</i>	Wp		X				3			3
	2501	3000			X	Solanaceae	<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	Cp		X				26			26
	2001	3000			X	Asteraceae	<i>Taraxacum officinale</i>	W		X				24			24
	2501	3000			X	Asteraceae	<i>Taraxacum</i> sp.	Wp		X				10			10
	2001	2500			X	Fabaceae	<i>Tephrosia</i> sp.	Wp		X				2			2
	2001	3000			X	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium pratense</i>	W		X				8			8
	2501	3000			X	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium repens</i>	W		X				130			130
	2501	3000			X	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium</i> sp.	W		X				56			56
	2501	3000			X	Fabaceae	<i>Vicia faba</i>	Cp		X	X			41			41
	2501	3000			X	Araceae	<i>Zantedeschia aethiopica</i>	Cp		X				8			8
	1501	3000			X	Poaceae	<i>Zea mays</i>	Cp		X				68			68
<i>Frankliniella paramorum</i> Berzosa, 2006	3500	4000			X	Asteraceae	<i>Espeletia</i> sp.	Wp		X				4			4
<i>Frankliniella parvula</i> Hood, 1925	1	1500	X	X		Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus dubius</i>	W		X					1		1
	1	1500	X	X		Fabaceae	<i>Bauhinia forficata</i>	Wp		X				1	1	1	3
	1	2000	X	X		Bixaceae	<i>Bixa orellana</i>	Cp		X				4	31	2	37
	1	500	X			Bixaceae	<i>Bixa orellana</i>	Wp		X				2		26	28
	1	1000	X			Fabaceae	<i>Caesalpinia pulcherrima</i>	Wp		X				2	1		3
	501	1000	X			Solanaceae	<i>Capsicum annuum</i>	Cp		X				1			1
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Cassia fistula</i>	Wp		X				1			1
	501	1500	X	X		Rutaceae	<i>Citrus latifolia</i>	Cp		X	X			16	2	2	20
	1001	1500		X		Rutaceae	<i>Citrus reticulata</i>	Cp		X				2			2
	501	2000	X	X		Rutaceae	<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	Cp		X	X			26	1	2	29
	1	2000	X	X		Rutaceae	<i>Citrus</i> sp.	Cp		X				1	6		7
	1001	2000		X		Rubiaceae	<i>Coffea arabica</i>	Cp		X				5	96		101
	1001	1500		X		Asteraceae	<i>Dahlia</i> sp.	Cp		X				47			47
	1	1500	X	X		Fabaceae	<i>Gliricidia sepium</i>	W		X				1		1	2
	1001	1500		X		Fabaceae	<i>Inga densiflora</i>	Wp		X					30		30

Species	Altitudinal range		Thermal zone			Botanical family	Associated Plant		System	Plant sampled structure				Geographical region			
	Min	Max	C	T	F					F	H	Fr	St	An	Ca	Or	Total
	1501	2000		X		Fabaceae	<i>Inga edulis</i>	Cp	X				5			5	
	1	500	X			Anacardiaceae	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Cp	X					1		1	
	1	1000	X			Euphorbiaceae	<i>Manihot esculenta</i>	Cp	X	X				3		3	
	1	2000	X	X		Musaceae	<i>Musa paradisiaca</i>	Cp	X			293	1399	38		1730	
	1	1000	X			Musaceae	<i>Musa sp.</i>	Cp	X				12	6		18	
	501	1000	X			Solanaceae	<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i>	Cp	X			1				1	
	501	1000	X			Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora edulis f. flavicarpa</i>	Cp	X			1				1	
	1	500	X			Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora maliformis</i>	Cp	X					1		1	
	1	2000	X	X		Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X	X		19	23			42	
	1	500				Fabaceae	<i>Pseudosamanea guachapele</i>	Wp	X			1				1	
	2501	3000			X	Brassicaceae	<i>Raphanus raphanistrum</i>	Cp	X			14				14	
	1	500	X			Rosaceae	<i>Rosa sp.</i>	Cp	X				1			1	
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Senna sp</i>	Wp	X					1		1	
	501	1000	X			Fabaceae	<i>Tachigali guianensis</i>	Cp	X			1				1	
	1	1500	X	X		Malvaceae	<i>Theobroma cacao</i>	Cp	X	X		27				27	
	1	1500	X	X		Apocynaceae	<i>Thevetia peruviana</i>	Wp	X			1				1	
	1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Tithonia diversifolia</i>	Wp	X					2		2	
	1	1500	X	X		Asteraceae	<i>Tithonia sp.</i>	Wp	X			5		1		6	
	1501	2000		X		Poaceae	<i>Zea mays</i>	Cp	X			81				81	
<i>Frankliniella peruviana</i> Hood, 1937	501	1000	X			Bixaceae	<i>Bixa orellana</i>	Cp	X			1				1	
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Cassia fistula</i>	Wp	X			1				1	
	1	500					<i>Clidemia hirta</i>	Wp		X		3				3	
	1001	2000		X		Rubiaceae	<i>Coffea arabica</i>	Cp	X			9				9	
	1	500	X			Anacardiaceae	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Cp	X					1		1	
	1501	2000		X		Solanaceae	<i>Solanum betaceum</i>	Cp	X			6				6	
	1001	1500		X		Solanaceae	<i>Solanum melongena</i>	Cp	X			1				1	
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Tachigali guianensis</i>	Cp	X					14		14	
<i>Frankliniella pulchella</i> Hood, 1935**	501	1000	X			Fabaceae	<i>Caesalpinia pulcherrima</i>	Wp	X			1				1	
<i>Frankliniella regentis</i> Berzosa, 2006	2501	3000			X	Asteraceae	<i>Dahlia sp.</i>	Wp	X			1				1	
	3001	3500			X	Asteraceae	<i>Espeletia sp.</i>	Wp	X			3				3	
	2501	3000			X	Solanaceae	<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	Cp	X			1				1	
<i>Frankliniella rostrata</i> Priesner, 1932	1	2000	X	X		Euphorbiaceae	<i>Manihot esculenta</i>	Cp	X	X		5	29			34	

Species	Altitudinal range		Thermal zone			Botanical family	Associated Plant	System	Plant sampled structure				Geographical region				
	Min	Max	C	T	F				F	H	Fr	St	An	Ca	Or	Total	
<i>Frankliniella schultzei</i> (Trybom, 1910)	1501	2000		X		Fabaceae	<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i>	Cp		X			1				1
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Senna</i> sp	Wp	X					40			40
	1	500	X			Bixaceae	<i>Bixa orellana</i>	Wp	X				1				1
	1	500	X			Rubiaceae	<i>Borreria laevis</i>	W	X				3				3
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Caesalpinia pulcherrima</i>	Wp	X					1			1
	1	500	X			Apocynaceae	<i>Calotropis procera</i>	W	X					1			1
	1	500	X			Solanaceae	<i>Capsicum annuum</i>	Cp	X					2			2
	1	500	X			Solanaceae	<i>Capsicum</i> sp.	Cp	X				2	1			3
	1	500	X				<i>Citrullus lanatus</i>	Cp	X	X				4			4
	1	500	X			Cleomaceae	<i>Cleome affinis</i>	W	X				1				1
	1001	1500		X		Rubiaceae	<i>Coffea arabica</i>	Cp	X					8			8
	1	500	X				<i>Cordia dentata</i>	Wp	X					9			9
	1	500	X				<i>Crescentia cujete</i>	Wp	X					1			1
	1	500	X				<i>Eclipta alba</i>	W	X				1				1
	1	500	X				<i>Funastrum clausum</i>	Wp	X					2			2
	1	500	X			Malvaceae	<i>Gossypium hirsutum</i>	Cp	X	X				57	5		62
	1	500	X			Boraginaceae	<i>Heliotropium angiospermum</i>	W	X					5			5
	1	500	X			Boraginaceae	<i>Heliotropium indicum</i>	W	X					1			1
	1	500	X				<i>Kallstroemia maxima</i>	W	X				11				11
	1	500	X			Chrysobalanaceae	<i>Licania</i> sp.	Wp	X					3			3
	1	500	X			Onagraceae	<i>Ludwigia</i> sp.	W	X				1				1
	1	500	X			Anacardiaceae	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Cp	X					21			21
	1	500	X			Euphorbiaceae	<i>Manihot esculenta</i>	Cp		X				2			2
	1	500	X			Malvaceae	<i>Melochia parvifolia</i>	W	X					2			2
	1	500	X			Malvaceae	<i>Melochia pyramidata</i>	W	X					1			1
	1	500	X				<i>Momordica charantia</i>	W	X					1			1
	1	500	X			Solanaceae	<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i>	Cp	X					1			1
	1	500	X			Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora edulis f. flavicarpa</i>	Cp	X					1			1
	1	1000	X			Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X	X				14			14
	1	500	X			Solanaceae	<i>Physalis</i> sp.	W	X					1			1
1	500	X				<i>Rhynchosia minima</i>	Cp	X					3			3	
1	500	X				<i>Ruellia tuberosa</i>	W	X					1			1	

Species	Altitudinal range		Thermal zone			Botanical family	Associated Plant	System	Plant sampled structure				Geographical region			
	Min	Max	C	T	F				F	H	Fr	St	An	Ca	Or	Total
	1	500	X				<i>Sarcostemma clausum</i>	W	X				4			4
	1	500	X				<i>Scoparia dulcis</i>	W	X				1			1
	1	500	X			Solanaceae	<i>Solanum melongena</i>	Cp	X					1		1
	1	500	X				<i>Sorghum bicolor</i>	Cp	X					1		1
	1	500	X				<i>Talinum fruticosum</i>	W	X				5			5
	1	500	X				<i>Talinum paniculatum</i>	W	X				1			1
	1	500	X			Poaceae	<i>Zea mays</i>	Cp	X					2		2
<i>Frankliniella senckenbergiana</i> Berzosa & Maroto, 2003	2500	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus glaucus</i>	Wp	X				1			1
<i>Frankliniella serrata</i> Moulton, 1933**	3001	3500			X	Asteraceae	<i>Espeletia</i> sp.	Wp	X				2			2
<i>Frankliniella simplex</i> Priesner, 1924	501	1000	X			Rutaceae	<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	Cp	X				1			1
	2501	3000			X	Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora ligularis</i>	Cp	X				1			1
	1501	2000		X		Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X				4			4
	2001	2500			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus glaucus</i>	Cp	X				1			1
	2501	3000			X	Poaceae	<i>Zea mays</i>	Cp	X				21			21
<i>Frankliniella sueoa</i> Mound & Marullo, 1996**	501	1000	X			Urticaceae	<i>Boehmeria nivea</i>	Wp	X				7			7
<i>Frankliniella tuberosi</i> Moulton, 1933.**	2500	3000			X	Solanaceae	<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	Cultivo	X	X			5			5
<i>Frankliniella trisetosa</i> Hood, 1942	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa</i> sp.	Cp				X	12			12
<i>Frankliniella tritici</i> (Fitch, 1855)	501	1000	X			Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X					1		1
	1501	2000		X		Poaceae	<i>Zea mays</i>	Cp	X				1			1
<i>Frankliniella vargasi</i> Retana & Mound, 1995	2501	3000			X	Asteraceae	<i>Baccharis prunifolia</i>	Wp	X				12			12
	1001	1500		X		Asteraceae	<i>Galinsoga</i> sp.	Wp	X				5			5
	1501	2000		X		Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X				1			1
	1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Tithonia diversifolia</i>	Wp	X						6	6
<i>Frankliniella varipes</i> Moulton, 1933**	2501	3000			X	Asteraceae	<i>Dahlia</i> sp.	Wp	X				45			45
	2501	3000			X	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium</i> sp.	W	X				1			1
<i>Frankliniella williamsi</i> Hood, 1915	1	500	X			Vitaceae	<i>Cissus verticillata</i>	W	X				3			3
	1	500	X			Cucurbitaceae	<i>Citrullus lanatus</i>	Cp	X					3		3
	1	500	X			Cucurbitaceae	<i>Cucumis melo</i>	Cp	X					1		1
	1	500	X			Cucurbitaceae	<i>Cucurbita maxima</i>	Cp		X				3		3
	1501	2000		X		Euphorbiaceae	<i>Manihot esculenta</i>	Cp	X					1		1
	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa</i> sp.	Cp				X	7			7
	1001	1500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Senna</i> sp	Wp	X					1		1

Species	Altitudinal range		Thermal zone			Botanical family	Associated Plant	System	Plant sampled structure				Geographical region			
	Min	Max	C	T	F				F	H	Fr	St	An	Ca	Or	Total
<i>Frankliniella xanthomelaena</i> Hood, 1937	1	500	X				<i>Tamarindus indica</i>	Wp	X					6		6
	1	2000		X		Poaceae	<i>Zea mays</i>	Cp	X					9	4	13
	501	1000	X			Rutaceae	<i>Citrus reticulata</i>	Cp	X					1		1
	1	500	X			Rutaceae	<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	Cp		X				1		1
	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Fragaria ananassa</i>	Cp	X					1		1
	1501	2500		X	X	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus glaucus</i>	Cp	X	X				31		31
<i>Frankliniella zeteki</i> Hood, 1925	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus</i> sp.	Wp	X					44		44
	1	500	X			Bixaceae	<i>Bixa orellana</i>	Wp	X					1		1
	1	1000	X			Fabaceae	<i>Caesalpinia pulcherrima</i>	Wp	X					1	3	4
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Calliandra surinamensis</i>	Wp	X						9	9
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Calliandra trinervia</i>	Wp	X						1	1
	1	500	X			Vitaceae	<i>Cissus verticillata</i>	W	X					1		1
	501	1000	X			Rutaceae	<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	Cp	X					3		3
	1	500	X			Cleomaceae	<i>Cleome spinosa</i>	W	X						1	1
	1001	1500		X		Rubiaceae	<i>Coffea arabica</i>	Cp	X					1		1
	1001	1500		X		Asteraceae	<i>Emilia sonchifolia</i>	W	X					2		2
	1	500	X			Boraginaceae	<i>Heliotropium indicum</i>	W	X						2	2
	501	1000	X			Fabaceae	<i>Inga edulis</i>	Wp	X					1		1
	1	500	X			Anacardiaceae	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Cp	X	X				5	1	6
	1	500	X			Euphorbiaceae	<i>Manihot esculenta</i>	Cp		X				1		1
	1	500	X			Malvaceae	<i>Melochia parvifolia</i>	W	X					1		1
	1	500	X			Rutaceae	<i>Murraya paniculata</i>	Cp	X						2	2
	501	1000	X			Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora edulis</i> f. <i>flavicarpa</i>	Cp		X				1		1
	1	2000	X	X		Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X					2	9	11
	1	1000	X			Fabaceae	<i>Pithecellobium guachapele</i>	W	X					12		12
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Senna</i> sp.	Wp	X						1	1
501	1000	X			Fabaceae	<i>Tachigali guianensis</i>	Cp	X					4		4	
1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Tithonia diversifolia</i>	Wp	X							2	2
1	500	X			Poaceae	<i>Zea mays</i>	Cp	X						2	2	
<i>Frankliniella orizabensis</i> Johansen, 1974	1001	1500		X		Rutaceae	<i>Citrus latifolia</i>	Cp	X					1		1
	1001	1500		X		Asteraceae	<i>Emilia sonchifolia</i>	W	X					1		1
<i>Haplothrips gowdeyi</i> (Franklin, 1908)	501	1000	X			Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus dubius</i>	W	X					1		1

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	Min	Max	C	T	F				F	H	Fr	St	An	Ca	Or	Total	
	501	1000	X			Poaceae	<i>Andropogon</i> sp.	W	X					2			2
	1	500	X			Boraginaceae	<i>Heliotropium angiospermum</i>	W	X					1			1
	1	500	X			Acanthaceae	<i>Hemigraphis alternata</i>	Cp	X					2			2
<i>Heliethrips haemorrhoidalis</i> (Bouche, 1833)	501	1000	X			Meliaceae	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	W	X				1				1
	1	500	X			Bixaceae	<i>Bixa orellana</i>	Cp	X					1			1
	1001	1500	X			Rubiaceae	<i>Coffea arabica</i>	Cp	X				1				1
	1	1500	X	X		Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X	X			1	2			3
<i>Heterothrips alvarezi</i> Johansen, 1981	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Tachigali guianensis</i>	Cp	X						1		1
<i>Heterothrips condei</i> Moulton, 1932**	1	500	X			Malpighiaceae	<i>Byrsonima bucidaefolia</i> Standl.	Wp	X						1		1
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Inga edulis</i>	Wp	X						3		3
<i>Heterothrips flavidus</i> Hood, 1954**	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Inga edulis</i>	Wp	X						1		1
<i>Heterothrips pedicellatus</i> Pereyra & Cavalleri, 2012**	501	1000	X			Fabaceae	<i>Gliricidia sepium</i>	Wp	X					1			1
<i>Heterothrips prosopidis</i> Crawford JC, 1943**	1001	1500		X		Apocynaceae	<i>Mandevilla</i> sp.	Wp	X				1				1
<i>Heterothrips sericatus</i> Hood, 1913	1	500	X			Bixaceae	<i>Bixa orellana</i>	Cp	X							3	3
	2001	2500			X	Boraginaceae	<i>Cordia alliodora</i>	Cp	X				3				3
	1001	1500		X		Asteraceae	<i>Emilia</i> sp.	W	X				1				1
	1001	1500		X		Fabaceae	<i>Inga densiflora</i>	Wp	X					1			1
	1001	1500		X		Fabaceae	<i>Lantana camara</i>	W	X					1			1
	1	500	X			Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X						1		1
	1	500	X			Myrtaceae	<i>Psidium guajava</i>	Cp	X						63		63
	1	500	X			Adoxaceae	<i>Sambucus</i> sp.	Wp	X						1		1
	1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Tithonia diversifolia</i>	Wp	X						2		2
<i>Holopothrips</i> sp.**	1	1500	X	X		Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X	X			20				20
<i>Karnyothrips flavipes</i> (Jones, 1912)**	501	1000	X			Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Wp		X			1				1
<i>Karnyothrips merrilli</i> (Watson, 1920)	1	500	X			Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X					2			2
<i>Leptothrips</i> sp.	1001	1500		X		Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X				2				2
<i>Microcephalothrips abdominalis</i> (Crawford DL, 1910)	1	500	X			Malvaceae	<i>Gossypium hirsutum</i>	Cp	X				1				1
	1501	2000		X		Asteraceae	<i>Helianthus annuus</i>	Cp	X				2				2
	1	500	X			Boraginaceae	<i>Heliotropium indicum</i>	W	X					1			1
	1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Parthenium hysterophorus</i>	W	X				1				1
	1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Sphagneticola trilobata</i>	Wp	X				21				21

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	Min	Max	C	T	F				F	H	Fr	St	An	Ca	Or	Total
<i>Neohydatothrips burungae</i> (Hood, 1935)	1	500	X			Portulacaceae	<i>Talinum fruticosum</i>	W	X				1			1
	1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Tithonia diversifolia</i>	Wp	X				54		2	56
	1501	2000		X		Rubiaceae	<i>Coffea arabica</i>	Cp	X				3			3
	1501	2000		X		Euphorbiaceae	<i>Manihot esculenta</i>	Cp		X			1			1
	2001	2500			X	Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora edulis f. edulis</i>	Cp	X							0
	1501	2000	X	X		Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora edulis f. flavicarpa</i>	Cp	X	X			58		10	68
	1001	1500		X		Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X					1		1
<i>Neohydatothrips gracilipes</i> Hood, 1924	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Prunus persica</i>	Cp	X				1			1
	2001	2500			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus glaucus</i>	Cp	X	X			21			21
	2501	3000			X	Cucurbitaceae	<i>Cucurbita maxima</i>	Cp	X				1			1
	1	1500	X	X		Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora edulis f. flavicarpa</i>	Cp	X	X			72		20	92
	1501	2500		X		Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora ligularis</i>	Cp	X	X			10			10
	1001	1500		X		Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora maliformis</i>	Cp		X			1			1
	2001	2500			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus glaucus</i>	Cp		X			2			2
<i>Neohydatothrips humberto</i> Mound & Marullo, 1996	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa</i> sp.	Cp					1			1
	2501	3000			X	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium repens</i>	W	X				1			1
<i>Neohydatothrips inversus</i> (Hood, 1928)**	1	1000	X			Fabaceae	<i>Gliricidia sepium</i>	W		X			2		33	35
<i>Neohydatothrips signifer</i> (Priesner, 1932)	1	2000		X		Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora edulis f. flavicarpa</i>	Cp	X	X			1		2	3
	1001	1500		X		Cannabaceae	<i>Cannabis</i> sp.	Cp	X				5			5
	1	500	X			Solanaceae	<i>Capsicum</i> sp.	Cp	X					1		1
	501	1000	X			Rutaceae	<i>Citrus latifolia</i>	Cp	X	X			5			5
	1501	2000		X		Rubiaceae	<i>Coffea arabica</i>	Cp	X				1			1
	1001	1500		X		Euphorbiaceae	<i>Manihot esculenta</i>	Cp		X			1	4		5
	1	500	X			Cucurbitaceae	<i>Momordica charantia</i>	Wp	X					1		1
	1	2000	X	X		Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora edulis f. flavicarpa</i>	Cp	X	X			368		101	469
	1501	3000		X	X	Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora ligularis</i>	Cp	X				107			107
	1001	1500		X		Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora maliformis</i>	Cp		X			7			7
	1001	2000		X		Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X				10			10
1001	1500		X		Fabaceae	<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i>	Cp	X				2			2	
2001	2500			X	Fabaceae	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	Cp	X				1			1	
1001	1500		X		Fabaceae	<i>Rhynchosia minima</i>	Cp	X				6			6	
1501	2000		X		Rosaceae	<i>Rubus glaucus</i>	Wp	X				1			1	

Species	Altitudinal range		Thermal zone			Botanical family	Associated Plant		System	Plant sampled structure				Geographical region			
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<i>Nexothrips perseae</i> Marullo & Mound, 2000	1001	1500		X		Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X	X			9			9	
<i>Oxythrips</i> sp.**	1	500	X			Boraginaceae	<i>Cordia dentata</i>	Wp	X					13		13	
<i>Psectrothrips delostomae</i> Hood, 1937	2501	3000			X	Bignoniaceae	<i>Tecoma stans</i>	Wp	X				18			18	
<i>Psectrothrips palmerae</i> Mound & Marullo, 1996	1001	1500		X		Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X				1			1	
<i>Rhamphothrips pandens</i> Sakimura, 1983	1	500	X			Chrysobalanaceae	<i>Chrysobalanus icaco</i>	Wp	X				3			3	
	1001	1500		X		Euphorbiaceae	<i>Manihot esculenta</i>	Cp		X				1		1	
<i>Salpingothrips minimus</i> Hood, 1935**	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Rhynchosia minima</i>	Cp	X				2			2	
<i>Scirtidothrips torquatus</i> Hood, 1954.**	1	500	X			Poaceae	<i>Zea mays</i>	Cp	X					1		1	
<i>Scirtothrips bisbravae</i> Johansen, 1983	1	500	X			Euphorbiaceae	<i>Hevea brasiliensis</i>	Cp		X					1	1	
<i>Scirtothrips dorsalis</i> Hood, 1919	1	500	X			Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i>	W	X					1		1	
	501	1000	X			Solanaceae	<i>Capsicum annuum</i>	Cp	X				2			2	
	1	500	X			Solanaceae	<i>Capsicum</i> sp.	Cp	X					4		4	
	1	500	X			Rutaceae	<i>Citrus</i> sp.	Cp		X				2		2	
	1	500	X			Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa colona</i>	W	X				4			4	
	1	500	X			Euphorbiaceae	<i>Euphorbia hypericifolia</i>	W	X				5			5	
	1	1000	X			Malvaceae	<i>Gossypium hirsutum</i>	Cp	X	X	X		812	274	40	1126	
	1	500	X			Anacardiaceae	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Cp	X					29		29	
<i>Scirtothrips hansonii</i> Mound & Hoddle, 2016	1	500	X			Rutaceae	<i>Murraya paniculata</i>	Cp	X					1		1	
	1	500	X			Euphorbiaceae	<i>Phyllanthus niruri</i> L.	W	X				4			4	
	1	500	X			Rosaceae	<i>Rosa</i> sp.	Wp	X					3		3	
	1	2500	X	X	X	Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X	X			83			83	
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	Wp	X				1			1	
	1	500	X			Euphorbiaceae	<i>Manihot esculenta</i>	Cp		X				1	1	2	
	1	500	X			Euphorbiaceae	<i>Hevea brasiliensis</i>	Cp		X					2	2	
	1	1500	X	X		Euphorbiaceae	<i>Manihot esculenta</i>	Cp	X	X			101	322	50	473	
<i>Scirtothrips multistriatus</i> Hood, 1954	1	500	X			Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora edulis</i> f. <i>flavicarpa</i>	Cp					2			2	
	1	500	X			Euphorbiaceae	<i>Hevea brasiliensis</i>	Cp	X	X					73	73	
<i>Scirtothrips panamensis</i> Hood, 1935	1	500	X			Euphorbiaceae	<i>Hevea brasiliensis</i>	Cp		X					14	14	
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	Wp	X				2			2	
	1	2000	X	X		Euphorbiaceae	<i>Manihot esculenta</i>	Cp	X	X			81	91	99	271	
<i>Scirtothrips perseae</i> Nakahara, 1997	1001	2000		X		Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp	X	X			12			12	
	1	500	X			Fabaceae	<i>Tamarindus indica</i>	Wp	X					1		1	

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<i>Scolothrips tenuipennis</i> zur Strassen, 1965	1	500	X			Euphorbiaceae	<i>Manihot esculenta</i>	Cp		X				2			2
<i>Scutothrips incaensis</i> Stannard, 1972	1001	1500		X		Asteraceae	<i>Tithonia diversifolia</i>	Wp	X					1			1
	501	1000	X			Rubiaceae	Sin determinar	Wp	X					5			5
<i>Scutothrips peruvianus</i> (Hood, 1936)**	1001	1500		X		Fabaceae	<i>Gliricidia sepium</i>	W	X					1			1
	501	1000	X			Fabaceae	<i>Senna</i> sp.	Wp	X					1			1
	501	1000	X			Rubiaceae	Sin determinar	Wp	X					5			5
<i>Selenothrips rubrocinctus</i> Giard, 1901	1	500	X			Anacardiaceae	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Cp	X				1	1			2
<i>Stenchaetothrips bififormis</i> (Bagnall, 1913)	1	500	X			Poaceae	<i>Oryza sativa</i>	Cp		X				5			5
<i>Stomatothrips flavus</i> Hood, 1912**	1001	1500		X		Fabaceae	<i>Senna</i> sp.	Wp	X					1			1
<i>Taeniothrips</i> sp.	2001	2500			X	Xanthorrhoeaceae	<i>Hemerocallis</i> sp.	Cp	X	X				2			2
<i>Thrips australis</i> (Bagnall, 1915)	2501	3000		X		Rosaceae	<i>Rosa</i> sp.	Cp					X	17			17
<i>Thrips brevipilosus</i> Moulton, 1927**	2001	2500		X		Boraginaceae	<i>Cordia alliodora</i>	Cp	X					1			1
	2501	3000		X		Rosaceae	<i>Rosa</i> sp.	Cp					X	17			17
<i>Thrips florum</i> Schmutz, 1913**	2501	3000		X		Asteraceae	<i>Emilia sonchifolia</i>	W	X					19			19
	2001	3000		X		Asteraceae	<i>Taraxacum officinale</i>	W	X					19			19
<i>Thrips palmi</i> Karny, 1925	1501	2000		X		Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus</i> sp.	W		X				4			4
	501	1000	X			Fabaceae	<i>Caesalpinia pulcherrima</i>	Wp	X					1			1
	501	2000	X	X		Solanaceae	<i>Capsicum annum</i>	Cp	X					9	7		16
	2001	2500		X		Asteraceae	<i>Chrysanthemum</i> sp.	Cp	X					4			4
	1	500	X			Cucurbitaceae	<i>Citrullus lanatus</i>	Cp	X	X				7	36		43
	501	1500	X	X		Rubiaceae	<i>Coffea arabica</i>	Cp	X					15	8		23
	1	500	X			Cucurbitaceae	<i>Cucumis melo</i>	Cp	X					32			32
	501	1000	X			Cucurbitaceae	<i>Cucurbita maxima</i>	Cp	X					5			5
	1	1000	X			Malvaceae	<i>Gossypium hirsutum</i>	Cp	X	X	X			3590	166	10	3766
	1	500	X			Boraginaceae	<i>Heliotropium angiospermum</i>	W	X					7			7
	1	500	X			Anacardiaceae	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Cp	X					5			5
	1	500	X			Euphorbiaceae	<i>Manihot esculenta</i>	Cp	X					3			3
	1501	2000		X		Solanaceae	<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i>	Cp	X					1			1
	1	500	X			Asteraceae	<i>Parthenium hysterophorus</i>	W	X					8			8
	1	1000	X			Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora edulis f. flavicarpa</i>	Cp	X					17			17
	1501	2000		X		Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i>	Cp		X				1			1
	1001	2000		X		Fabaceae	<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i>	Cp	X	X				38			38

Species	Altitudinal range		Thermal zone			Botanical family	Associated Plant	System	Plant sampled structure				Geographical region				
	Min	Max	C	T	F				F	H	Fr	St	An	Ca	Or	Total	
	501	1000	X			Fabaceae	<i>Pithecellobium guachapele</i>	W	X					2			2
	1001	1500		X		Fabaceae	<i>Rhynchosia minima</i>	Cp	X					13			13
	1001	1500		X		Solanaceae	<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	Cp	X					1			1
	1	1500	X	X		Solanaceae	<i>Solanum melongena</i>	Cp	X	X				3	19		22
	2001	2500			X	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium pratense</i>	W	X					4			4
	1	500	X			Poaceae	<i>Zea mays</i>	Cp	X						9		9
<i>Thrips simplex</i> (Morison, 1930)	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa</i> sp.	Cp					X	2			2
<i>Thrips tabaci</i> Lindeman, 1889	2001	3000			X	Amaryllidaceae	<i>Allium cepa</i>	Cp	X	X				41			41
	2501	3000			X	Amaryllidaceae	<i>Allium fistulosum</i>	Cp	X					2			2
	2501	3000			X	Amaryllidaceae	<i>Allium sativum</i>	Cp	X					81			81
	2501	3000			X	Asparagaceae	<i>Asparagus officinalis</i>	Cp	X					1			1
	2001	2500			X	Asteraceae	<i>Chrysanthemum</i> sp.	Cp	X					5			5
	1501	2000		X		Rubiaceae	<i>Coffea arabica</i>	Cp	X					4			4
	2001	3000			X	Apiaceae	<i>Coriandrum sativum</i>	Cp	X					3			3
	2501	3000			X	Cucurbitaceae	<i>Cucurbita pepo</i>	Cp	X					2			2
	2501	3000			X	Poaceae	<i>Holcus lanatus</i>	W	X					6			6
	1501	2000		X		Fabaceae	<i>Inga edulis</i>	Cp	X					5			5
	2001	2500		X		Fabaceae	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	Cp	X					17			17
	2501	3000			X	Brassicaceae	<i>Raphanus raphanistrum</i>	W	X					4			4
	2501	3000			X	Brassicaceae	<i>Raphanus</i> sp.	Cp	X					1			1
	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rosa</i> sp.	Cp					X	27			27
	2501	3000			X	Rosaceae	<i>Rubus glaucus</i>	Cp		X				1			1
	2501	3000			X	Polygonaceae	<i>Rumex crispus</i>	W	X					2			2
	2001	2500			X	Fabaceae	<i>Senna</i> sp.	Wp	X					1			1
	2501	3000			X	Solanaceae	<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	Cp	X					3			3
	2501	3000			X	Solanaceae	<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>	Cp	X					1			1
	2001	2500			X	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium pratense</i>	W	X					5			5
	2501	3000			X	Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium</i> sp.	W	X					1			1
	2501	3000			X	Araceae	<i>Zantedeschia aethiopica</i>	Cp	X					3			3
<i>Thrips trehernei</i> Priesner, 1927**	2501	3000			X	Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora tarminiana</i>	Cp	X					2			2
	2001	2500			X	Asteraceae	<i>Taraxacum officinale</i>	W	X					2			2

Species	Altitudinal range		Thermal zone			Botanical family	Associated Plant	System	Plant sampled structure				Geographical region			Total	
	Min	Max	C	T	F				F	H	Fr	St	An	Ca	Or		
Total														18093	7082	1401	26576